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DE-RISK Project

D3.6: DE-RISK LFM's Policy and Regulatory Roadmap for 10 EU Countries

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

AC	Alternating Current
AF	Application Form
aFRR	Automatic Frequency Restoration Reserve
AI	Artificial intelligence
BESS	Battery Energy Storage System
BRP	Balance Responsible Party
CCS	Carbon Capture Storage
CfD	Contract for Difference
CEC	Citizen Energy Community
D	Deliverable
DER	Distributed Energy Resources
DLR	Dynamic Line Rating
DNUT	Dynamic Network Usage Tariff
DR	Demand Response
DSF	Demand-side Flexibility
DSO	Distribution System Operator
DSR	Demand-side Response
EE	Energy Efficiency
EEA	European Economic Area
EMD	Electricity Market Design
ESCO	Energy Service Company
EU	European Union
FACTS	Flexibility Variable Transmission Solutions
FCR	Frequency Containment Reserves
FIT	Feed-in-Tariff
FS	Flexibility Services
FSP	Flexibility Service Provider
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IoT	Internet of Things
IT	Information Technologies
LFM	Local Flexibility Market
M	Month
mFRR	Manual Frequency Restoration Reserve
PFC	Primary Frequency Control
PV	Photovoltaic
RE	Renewable Energy
REC	Renewable Energy Communities
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
RRF	Recovery Resilience Fund
RRP	Recovery and Resilience Plan

SFC	Secondary Frequency Control
T	Task
ToU	Time-of-Use
TSO	Transmission System Operator
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report contains the Deliverable D3.6: “DE-RISK Local Flexibility Markets Policy and Regulatory Roadmap for 10 EU Countries” of the project DE-RISK - “DE-RISK the adoption of Local Flexibility Markets to unlock the safe and reliable mass deployment of Renewable Energy Systems”, funded by Horizon Europe programme under Grant Agreement No. 101075515. It is a result obtained from Task T3.5 - “DE-RISK LFMs Policy and Regulatory roadmap for 10 EU countries”, implemented in M24-M30 and led by Sofia Energy Agency SOFENA with the participation of all consortium partners.

The objective to prepare D3.6: “DE-RISK LFMs Policy and Regulatory Roadmap for 10 EU Countries” is to provide a basis for policymakers and stakeholders for developing more informed RES policy and for analysing market dynamics when including all renewable energies.

The document provides open, evidence based, comprehensive guidelines, targeting high impact local, national and EU policy makers, for strengthening the flexibility services (FS) and Local Flexibility Markets (LFM) policy development process, thus supporting the market uptake of renewable energy sources (RES).

The DE-RISK regulatory recommendations package will support policymakers to have active end-user participation in a system where residential and commercial buildings have traditionally remained passive.

DE-RISK will provide insight into the complexity of market arrangements for the eligibility of Demand Response (DR) to participate in various short term electricity markets; an examination and breakdown of the roles and responsibilities of existing and newly emerging market players and; recommendations on the fair allocation of costs and benefits amongst the various LFMs stakeholders.

In particular, DE-RISK will provide a basis for policymakers and stakeholders for:

- i. Developing more informed RES policy to unleash the potential of LFMs by analysing and providing recommendations for issues related with LFMs integration, coordination of flexibility, split-incentives of implementation, aggregation at each level, roles and responsibilities, intricacies of market participation for DR, model verification, validation and sensitivity, motivation and initiatives for engaging on LFMs, settlements, penalties.
- ii. Analysing market dynamics to expose all the factors that influence the LFMs functioning, such as electricity prices in Europe, price-based flexibility mechanisms, factors impacting elasticity values, assessment of distribution cost drivers and signalling of LFMs, costs, benefits and flexibility of end-user demand under current system conditions.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Overview of the DE-RISK project

Launched in September 2022, the DE-RISK project aims at supporting the market uptake of renewable energy systems by fostering the adoption of Local Flexibility Markets (LFMs) and unlocking up to 100 GW of flexibility in 2030 which will allow a safe and reliable integration of RES in the grid. The project plans to achieve this ambitious objective by minimizing the investments and implementation risk through an innovative customer behaviour change journey that will increase end users' trust and willingness to participate in the flexibility markets.

The DE-RISK project aims to facilitate the adoption of LFMs by mitigating associated risks following key strategies as:

- **End-User Engagement:** Conducting behavioural analyses to understand consumer needs and encourage active participation in LFMs.
- **Digital Twin Platform:** Deploying a cost-effective digital twin platform to assess and unlock flexibility potential across various case studies in Spain, Ireland and Türkiye.
- **Regulatory and Financial Frameworks:** Developing regulatory recommendations and innovative business models, such as crowdfunding and Energy Performance Contracts (EPCs), to ensure the long-term viability of LFMs.

DE-RISK intends to achieve the ambitious aims by minimizing the investments and implementation risk through an innovative customer behaviour change journey that influences the end users' trust and willingness to participate in the flexibility markets.

DE-RISK integrates building, citizen and grids digital twins in its flexibility platform capable of reducing the gap between simulation and real implementation thus mitigating potential technical risks during deployment and operational phase.

To maximize DE-RISK impact, innovative multi-sided business models have been developed ensuring multi-benefits, fairness and sustainability for all actors while disruptive financial schemes are validated for democratizing the access to sustainable investments.

One of the main objectives of the DE-RISK project is to develop a regulatory package to support the wide adoption of LFMs and its actors in the European Union which will simplify the access of new participants (independent aggregators) while reducing the risk of unfair competition and penalties among stakeholders.

1.2. Description of the Deliverable Content, Objectives and Purpose

The development of smart grids and Demand Response (DR) in Europe has to be accompanied by the elaboration of adequate Regulation and Standards. One of the main reasons for the low penetration of explicit DR schemes in most of the EU is the lack of supporting regulations. There is a need to accelerate the development of the standards and regulation for the smart grid in order to enhance the potential of the LFMs and RES integration in the European economy.

Lack of information and slow implementation of the DR market in Europe has the potential risk to hinder the exploitation of the DR solutions. Accounting for this, as part of DE-RISK project activities, great efforts have been allocated to policy and regulatory market analysis, seeking for the most suitable environment for the penetration of the RES and LFMs across Europe.

DE-RISK aims at bridging the regulatory gap and road-mapping the LFMs in different regulatory and policy frameworks and market maturity conditions analysed with the use cases included in the project.

Benefitting from the results of the PESTLE Analysis (D3.1) and the RIA Analysis (D3.2), an overview on RES and LFMs development in Europe has been elaborated as part of the D3.6: “DE-RISK LFMs Policy and Regulatory Roadmap for 10 EU Countries”. The D3.6 report gives guidelines for LFMs implementation in 10 countries: the DE-RISK partner countries - Bulgaria, France¹, Greece, Ireland, Spain, Portugal and Türkiye, and as defined in the Application Form (AF) - Italy, the Netherlands and Romania. The guidelines deliver the Member States and the EU Commission regulatory-related know-how and information necessary to start the full adoption of LFMs as a future core actor in the Energy Grid.

The content of the Deliverable follows the logic of the outlined topics in the AF seeking answers to the following questions:

- i. Homogenized definition of LFMs;
- ii. How should local flexibility be established to assure proper compliance and safety;
- iii. Which business models and financing mechanisms are necessary to boost stakeholder motivation to facilitate the creation (DSOs, BRPs, utilities, aggregators, TSOs);
- iv. What awareness actions (based on the outcomes of WP2 and WP5) are necessary to ensure the highest customer participation in the LFMs.

¹ Although the partner of DE-RISK from France, i.e. GRIDPOCKET has terminated their partnership from the project, required country data was already provided by them before this situation for the implementation of the PESTLE and RIA analysis. Therefore, information regarding France is available to be used for the subject deliverable, and that is why we included the country in this study.

Chapter 1 *Introduction* gives short information about the DE-RISK project outlining its main objectives, and describes the purpose and content of the Deliverable.

Chapter 2 sets out the *Methodology* that the elaboration of the report has followed.

Chapter 3 analyses the *Definition of LFMs* in the literature and points out the practical understanding of it in the DE-RISK project.

Chapter 4 includes detailed *Recommendations for Facilitating the Deployment of LFMs and the Exploitation of the Flexibility* in each of the 10 countries under scrutiny, based on the questions i-iv included in the upper paragraphs, and summarising the policy guidelines for facilitating deployment of LFMs and FS.

Chapter 5 delivers *Policy Recommendations for Enabling Regulations of the LFMs* to provide a basis for policymakers and stakeholders for developing informed RES policy in Europe. It is a summary of the enabling Regulations for the deployment of the LFMs for the European Commission and the national authorities.

Chapter 6 *Conclusions* summarises the importance of the roadmaps for the development of the regulation on energy communities and local flexibility markets, as well as the significance of consumer participation as an empowered stakeholder in the market, for supporting the EU's 2030 and 2050 energy targets achievements.

2. METHODOLOGY

The objective of the Deliverable D3.6: “DE-RISK LFMs Policy and Regulatory Roadmap for 10 EU Countries” is to provide regulatory-related know-how and information necessary to start the full adoption of LFMs in the Energy Grid.

Based on the assessment of the current regulatory framework that is acting as an enabler for or as a barrier to the large deployment of LFMs and to FS in 9 countries - members of the EU and Türkiye, and by collecting data across Europe, the report aims to outline the future regulatory developments to boost the implementation of LFMs in Europe.

In DE-RISK project, the **methodology** of the LFMs policy and regulatory road-mapping for the 10 countries under scrutiny goes through the following stages:

Stage I: Data collection

- *State-of-the-art review of EU regulations* impacting the adoption of LFMs and FS. A thorough study was conducted in order to follow the tracking of development of the transposition of the Renewable Energy (REDII) ¹ and the Internal Electricity Market (IEMD)² Directives into national legislation and their consistency with EU legislation. In this part of the research articles on scientific journals as well as official publications were used, documents and reports from European projects on the topic and dedicated websites were also reviewed.
- *Reports, results and highlights from other DE-RISK work packages* were employed following the pattern of the DE-RISK project solution, concerning demand-side FS, traditional and innovative financing mechanisms, and main outcomes from the engagement activities carried out in pilot sites in order to involve and upskill interested parties, businesses, stakeholders and citizens.

The desk research of EU and national-level legislation of Türkiye, Spain, Portugal, Bulgaria, Greece, Ireland and the Netherlands, Romania, Italy and France has been performed by the experts of Sofia Energy Agency SOFENA.

In addition, the piloting partner countries profiles have been further enriched upon thorough online consultations which were conducted with the DE-RISK project partners.

Stage II: Regulatory Impact Analysis

This stage includes the analytical tasks of developing guidelines that give:

- Homogenized definition of LFM;
- Directions about how local flexibility should be established to assure proper compliance and safety;
- Business models and financing mechanisms for boosting the stakeholder motivation to facilitate the creation (DSOs, BRPs, utilities, aggregators, TSOs) of LFMs;
- Awareness actions (based on the outcomes of WP2 and WP5) necessary to ensure the highest customer participation in the LFMs;
- Recommendations for the European Commission and for the national authorities concerning legislative changes to improve the adoption of LFMs.

This methodology of a combined learning, from literature research and on the basis of the information gathered from partners in the field, and results from work package reports, led to a set of policy recommendations imbedded in the road-mapping the LFMs in different regulatory and policy frameworks and market maturity conditions for the 10 countries under scrutiny in Europe.

3. DEFINING LOCAL FLEXIBILITY MARKETS

In 2020 Europex - the Association of European Energy Exchanges - published a Position Paper, on “A market-based approach to local flexibility – design principles”² giving directions concerning the challenge of managing the increasing share of renewable energy and more decentralised resources.

The increasing share of renewable energy generation in the energy mix has put pressure on the capacity of local and regional grids, requiring costly grid management measures from the network operators (TSOs and DSOs), and this process has been accompanied by the deployment of the decentralised resources, including storage assets and electric vehicles. Active customers also offer demand-side flexibility, either directly or through aggregation services.

All this requires effective management and harnessing the flexibility potential offered by these resources in a cost-efficient manner to increase the security of supply of the power system, and leading to effective integration with the organised wholesale energy market.

The solution is the local flexibility market that gathers parties with flexible assets (flexibility service providers) and allows them to offer flexibility towards entities, typically DSO and TSOs that need to efficiently manage congestion in the grid and ensure security of supply. This market-based approach efficiently matches supply and demand for flexibility and ensures the delivery of flexibility at the least cost and its use provides high value to the whole system.

Some of the principles, relevant for the design of flexibility markets and set out in the Clean Energy Package, are as follows:

- End-users should have access to all organised markets and products, either directly or indirectly (Electricity Market Directive (EU) 2019/944, Articles 5, 11, 15, 16, 17).
- Management of grid congestion should be market-based and should be open to all generation technologies, all energy storage and all demand response (Electricity Market Regulation (EU) 2019/943, Article 13).
- Provision of non-frequency ancillary services to system operators must be market-based (Electricity Market Directive (EU) 2019/944, Article 40 and Electricity Market Regulation, Article 59.1.d).

² A market-based approach to local flexibility – design principles - Position paper - Europex – Association of European Energy Exchanges, Brussels, 12 February 2020

There are numerous interpretations of LFM that refer to the concept in different ways. As different flexibility market and platform designs are being developed and tested, several *high-level principles can be outlined below concerning their design and implementation:*

- a. *Transparent and accessible market platforms:* All market parties should be able to compete freely for FS, via market-based platforms with non-discriminatory access thus ensuring that resources are efficiently allocated, while an accurate and visible price signal will reflect their value to market participants.
- b. *Operation of market platforms by independent, neutral third parties:* Independent, third parties, not active on the market, is the best way to avoid any risk of conflict of interest and ensure non-discriminatory access for all market parties. Market trading platforms facilitating trading and price formation in LFM should be operated by independent third parties.
- c. *Open to all technologies:* All types of flexibility including intermittent RES producers, flexible thermal assets, power-to-gas, storage, but also aggregators of industrial flexible load and “prosumers” could be eligible to participate in LFM depending on their characteristics and grid impact.
- d. *Product design:* Products should be defined so that they allow all technologies, including (distributed) generation, storage, DR, etc., to compete fairly and are not restricted to a certain type of technology or tailored to the needs of established or specific providers. Relevant stakeholders should be fully involved in the design process.
- e. *Responding to local needs:* The core of the flexibility markets is to respond to local needs for flexibility arising from the more decentralised power system. Hence, markets could be set up for each identified constrained local area, paving the way for the emergence of locational price signals for congestion management and redispatch by TSOs and DSOs. Relevant flexibility providers need to be identified and certified by system operators in the respective areas.
- f. *Integration with the existing short-term power market:* The last decades have been characterised by the integration of short-term power markets, leading to the implementation of EU-wide single day-ahead and intraday markets as envisaged in the Guideline on Capacity Allocation and Congestion Management. In addition, rules introduced by the Clean Energy Package provide a framework for the trading of products which adequately reflect the penetration of intermittent and decentralised generation and demand-side response. It is essential that LFM do complement, and are compatible with the existing cross zonal wholesale short-term markets.
- g. *Clear unbundling rules for the operation of flexibility assets:* It implies a separation between regulated grid assets, owned by the TSOs or DSOs, and commercial ‘market’ assets. This approach (in line with the recast Electricity Directive) leads to the efficient

functioning of the market, thus all market participants have fair access to the assets, the risk of the TSO or DSO treating these assets differently can be eliminated and the assets are fully utilised.

- h. System operator incentives for cost-effective system management:** While grid expansion is important, system operators, both DSOs and TSOs should be incentivised to procure flexibility via the market as an alternative to network reinforcements. Ultimately, the procurement of flexibility must be a viable alternative to grid investments.

Local Flexibility Markets can be defined as a subtype of electricity markets that are characterised by their “local” and “flexibility” indication. The term “local” refers to certain services and products that are defined by a specific geographical location. Flexibility providers connected to the given location in the electricity grid can provide the required service. The term “flexibility” refers to a range of flexibility sources³.

Local Flexibility Markets can be also defined like platforms that enable the trading of FS at a local level. These markets allow participants like flexibility service providers (FSPs), to offer their services to DSOs and TSOs when they need power or capacity.

Local Flexibility Markets manage the distribution system efficiently by using decentralized energy resources (DERs) to solve issues like congestion management, minimize power outages, and avoid costly grid expansions. This approach promotes a more cost-effective and secured energy system⁴.

There are different interpretations of LFM, as collected in Table 1 of the article “Decoding design characteristics of LFM for congestion management with a multi-layered taxonomy” by Sergio P. Menci, Orlando Valarezo (Applied Energy, Volume 357, 2024). These definitions, especially those of the Agency for the Cooperation of Energy Regulators (ACER)’s and European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity (ENTSO-E)’s incorporate design aspects such as the target group (e.g., DSOs), while in other cases, include trading actions, flexibility grid needs, aggregation, and platform independence.

According to the cited authors these definitions can limit the scope of the solutions, especially if collected in regulations or frameworks and that is why they offer a broader, more inclusive definition of Local Flexibility Markets as “*information system solutions that enable buyers and sellers to trade flexibility-services to address local needs*”.

³ Sergio Potenciano Menci, Orlando Valarezo, Decoding design characteristics of local flexibility markets for congestion management with a multi-layered taxonomy, Applied Energy, Volume 357, 2024, 122203, ISSN 0306-2619, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2023.122203>. (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306261923015672>)

⁴ [Local Flexibility Markets smartEn Spotlight](#), June 2022

Table 1: Definitions of Local Flexibility Markets

Author	Year	LFM definition
Ramos et al. ⁵	2016	Long- or short-term trading actions for flexibility in a specific geographical location, voltage level, and system operator (DSO and TSO), given by grid conditions or balancing needs, where participants in a relevant market can be aggregated to provide FSs
Olivella-Rosell et al. ⁶	2018	An electricity flexibility-trading platform to trade flexibility in geographically limited areas such as neighbourhoods, communities, towns, and small cities.
Radecke et al. ⁷	2019	Mechanism that i) aims to relieve congestion in the distribution grid, ii) works through impacting the dispatch of generation, load and/or storage assets, with iii) voluntary participation, and iv) remuneration that is determined based on participants' bids
Correa-Florez et al. ⁸	2020	Independent trading space/platform with specific bidding rules
Ziras et al. ⁹	2021	A market-based solution to trade flexibility locally between flexibility providers and DSOs.
Dronne et al. ¹⁰	2021	A local flexibility market is typically used to provide services for the flexibility needs inherent to the Distribution Network Operator (DNO).
Faregard et al. ¹¹	2021	Enablers of explicit DSF, to be used for several purposes such as managing grid congestions
Singh et al. ¹²	2022	Trading mechanism for electrical flexibility in geographically constrained regions like communities, neighborhoods, and towns. The LFM provides a competitive trading platform that allows flexibility purchasers, such as DSOs and BRPs, to trade flexibility with flexibility sellers, such as aggregators and prosumers.
ENTSO-E ¹³	2022	Specifically aimed solutions at resolving distribution network constraint
ACER ¹⁴	2022	Markets where service providers offer products for local SO services
Valarezo et al. ¹⁵	2023	A marketplace that enables buyers and sellers to trade FSs to address local needs.

⁵ Realizing the smart grid's potential: Defining local markets for flexibility - ScienceDirect

⁶ Olivella-Rosell P., Bullich-Massagué E., Aragüés-Peñalba M., Sumper A., Ottesen S.Ø., Vidal-Clos J.-A., et al. Optimization problem for meeting DSO requests in LFMs with DERs Appl Energy, 210 (2018), pp. 881-895, 10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.08.136

⁷ Radecke J., Hefele J., Hirth L. Markets for local flexibility in distribution networks: Tech. rep. ZBW – Leibniz Information Centre for Economics, Kiel, Hamburg (2019) URL <http://hdl.handle.net/10419/204559>

⁸ Correa-Florez C.A., Michiorri A., Kariniotakis G. Optimal participation of residential aggregators in energy and local flexibility markets IEEE Trans Smart Grid, 11 (2) (2020), pp. 1644-1656, 10.1109/TSG.2019.2941687

⁹ Ziras C., Heinrich C., Bindner H.W. Why baselines are not suited for local flexibility markets, Renew Sustain Energy Rev, 135 (2021), Article 110357, 10.1016/j.rser.2020.110357

¹⁰ Dronne T., Roques F., Saguan M. Local flexibility markets for distribution network congestion-management in center-western Europe: Which design for which needs? Energies, 14 (14) (2021), 10.3390/en14144113

¹¹ Fåregård S., Miletic M. A Swedish Perspective on aggregators and LFMs: considerations and barriers for aggregators and sthlmflex together with their potential to manage grid congestions in Stockholm [Master's thesis] KTH - Kungliga Tekniska högskolan (2021)

¹² Singh R., Vijay R., Mathuria P., Bhakar R. Local flexibility markets in the context of reactive power provision by DERs 2022 4th international conference on energy, power and environment (2022), pp. 1-6, 10.1109/ICEPE55035.2022.9798333

¹³ Charbonnier V., Dikaiakos C., Foresti M., Appleman N., Cooper M., Hussein A., et al. Review of flexibility platforms: Tech. rep. ENTSO-E and Frontier Economics Ltd (2021)

¹⁴ European Union Agency for the Cooperation of Energy Regulators (ACER) Framework guideline on demand response (2022)

¹⁵ Valarezo O., Chaves-Ávila J., Gómez T. Exploring the interaction between electricity distribution network reconfiguration and local flexibility markets Curr Sustain/Renew Energy Rep (2023), 10.1007/s40518-023-00221-6

This definition is not specific to any particular market design, implementation, or service, and stimulates innovation and allows adaptation to various contexts, requirements and designs.

A Local Flexibility Market provides an opportunity for consumers to play a significant role in the operation of the electric grid by reducing or shifting their electricity usage in response to time-based rates or other forms of financial incentives.

Most of the current flexibility platforms have to be automated and dynamic forms of system services to fully unlock the flexibility potential allowing data exchange and coordination among stakeholders, who are mainly operators of transmission and distribution systems and aggregators and others, in countries where they operate.

The DE-RISK project looks at the Local Flexibility Markets from the point of view of an electricity trading platform trading flexibility at DSO level.

Benefits and fairness through the whole value chain can also be ensured by applying new business models such as aggregation, virtual power plants and other distributed energy resource platforms.

A homogenized definition of Local Flexibility Markets should summarise their core purpose, key stakeholders, operational mechanisms, and benefits in a way that is universally applicable across different regions and market structures. A definition complying with the mentioned requirement above, states the following:

Local Flexibility Markets are decentralized trading platforms that facilitate the exchange of flexible energy resources at a local level to balance supply and demand, enhance grid stability, and optimize network operations. They enable distributed energy resources (DERs) such as demand response, battery storage, and renewable generation to offer FS to grid operators, utilities, or aggregators in response to real-time or near-real-time network constraints.

LFMs promote efficiency, resilience, and sustainability in the energy system by integrating local flexibility into market-based mechanisms, reducing the need for costly grid reinforcements and enhancing the integration of RES.

4. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FACILITATING DEPLOYMENT OF LFMS AND EXPLOITATION OF FLEXIBILITY IN 9 EU COUNTRIES AND TÜRKİYE

Short overview of the EU regulation on LFMs

The EU has established a comprehensive legislative framework to promote the development of LFMs among its member states comprising the following key directives and regulations:

- **Electricity Directive (EU) 2019/944¹⁶**

Objective: To establish common rules for the internal electricity market, aiming to enhance competition, consumer rights, and the integration of RES. Its key provisions include:

Market Access: Facilitates the participation of new market entrants, including those offering FS.

Consumer Empowerment: Empowers consumers to participate actively in the energy market, including through demand response and self-generation.

- **Renewable Energy Directive (EU) 2018/2001¹⁷:**

Objective: To promote the use of energy from renewable sources, setting binding targets for all member states. Its key provisions include:

National Targets: Mandates that member states achieve specific renewable energy targets, contributing to the overall EU goal.

Support Schemes: Encourages the development of support mechanisms for renewable energy projects, including those enhancing grid flexibility.

- **Energy Efficiency Directive (EU) 2012/27/EU¹⁸:**

Objective: To establish measures to promote energy efficiency within the EU, aiming for a 20% improvement by 2020 and further enhancements thereafter. The key provisions are:

Energy Savings: Requires member states to set indicative national energy efficiency targets.

Demand Response: Encourages the implementation of demand response programs, enabling consumers to adjust their energy usage in response to market signals.

¹⁶ [EUR-Lex - 02019L0944-20220623 - EN - EUR-Lex](#)

¹⁷ [EUR-Lex - 02018L2001-20231120 - EN - EUR-Lex](#)

¹⁸ [EUR-Lex - 02012L0027-20180709 - EN - EUR-Lex](#)

- **Third Energy Package¹⁹:**

Objective: Aims to further open up and integrate the gas and electricity markets within the EU.

Key Provisions:

Unbundling: Requires the separation of companies' generation and sale operations from their transmission networks to prevent conflicts of interest.

Regulatory Authorities: Establishes national regulatory authorities and the Agency for the Cooperation of Energy Regulators (ACER) to oversee and coordinate the internal energy market.

The recently updated EU legislative framework further promotes the development of LFM among its member states to enhance the integration of RES, ensure grid stability, and empower consumers. These legislative instruments are:

- **Directive (EU) 2024/1711²⁰:**

Objective: To amend previous directives to improve the EU's electricity market design, focusing on consumer protection, flexible connection agreements, and energy sharing. Key provisions:

Flexible Connection Agreements: Mandates that regulatory authority develop frameworks for transmission and distribution system operators to offer flexible connection agreements in areas with limited grid capacity.

Energy Sharing Rights: Grants households, small and medium-sized enterprises, and public bodies the right to participate in energy sharing as active customers within the same bidding zone or a defined geographical area.

Supplier of Last Resort: Requires member states to establish a regime ensuring continuity of supply, particularly for household customers, in cases where their current supplier ceases operation.

- **Regulation (EU) 2024/1747²¹:**

Objective: To amend existing regulations to enhance the EU's internal electricity market, focusing on market transparency, flexibility, and consumer empowerment. Key provisions:

Non-Fossil Flexibility Support Schemes: Allows member states to implement support schemes for non-fossil flexibility resources, such as demand response and energy storage, to achieve national flexibility objectives.

¹⁹ Directive - 2009/72 - EN - EUR-Lex

²⁰ Directive - EU - 2024/1711 - EN - EUR-Lex

²¹ Regulation - EU - 2024/1747 - EN - EUR-Lex

Dedicated Measurement Devices: Permits the use of data from dedicated measurement devices for the observability and settlement of demand response and FS, especially in areas lacking smart metering systems.

Peak-Shaving Products: Introduces mechanisms to reduce electricity demand during peak periods, enhancing grid stability and preventing price spikes.

These updated legislative instruments, some of them effective as of July 2024, aim to create a more resilient, flexible and consumer-centric energy market within the EU, facilitating the development of LFM and supporting the transition to a sustainable energy system.

In addition, some legislative measures also contribute to the promotion of the LFM across EU member states, as follows:

- Electricity Market Design Reform (2024):
 - *Flexible Connection Agreements:* The EU encourages the use of flexible, non-firm connection agreements, which facilitate the rapid integration of renewable energy and storage solutions. These agreements allow new producers to connect to the grid in areas with limited capacity, operating under conditions that may include curtailment during peak times until necessary infrastructure upgrades are completed²².
 - *Non-Fossil Flexibility Objectives:* Member States are required to assess their flexibility needs biennially and set indicative national targets for non-fossil flexibility resources, such as demand response and energy storage. This approach aims to ensure a balanced and resilient energy system that can adapt to fluctuations in supply and demand²³.
- Contracts for Difference (CfDs):
 - The EU mandates that new investments in specific renewable energy generation facilities utilize two-way Contracts for Difference or equivalent schemes. This mechanism provides price stability for investors and ensures that consumers benefit from lower costs when market prices exceed the agreed-upon strike price²⁴.
- Capacity Mechanisms and Flexibility Support:
 - To address potential shortfalls in energy supply and promote the participation of non-fossil flexibility solutions, the EU has reformed capacity mechanisms. These reforms include setting stringent CO₂ emission limits for participating resources

²² Reform of the European electricity market: a new organization without revolution - Concurrences

²³ Regulation - EU - 2024/1747 - EN - EUR-Lex

²⁴ Regulation - EU - 2024/1747 - EN - EUR-Lex

and encouraging Member States to design support schemes that favour demand response and energy storage solutions²⁵.

- Consumer Empowerment and Energy Sharing:

- The EU emphasizes consumer rights by ensuring access to various electricity supply contracts, including fixed-term, fixed-price options and dynamic pricing models. Additionally, legislative provisions support energy sharing among households, small and medium-sized enterprises, and public bodies, enabling collective participation in renewable energy generation and consumption²⁶

These legislative frameworks collectively foster the development of LFM and enhance the overall resilience of the energy system.

²⁵ Regulation - EU - 2024/1747 - EN - EUR-Lex

²⁶ Directive - EU - 2024/1711 - EN - EUR-Lex

4.1. Bulgaria

Bulgaria has been actively advancing its renewable energy sector, aligning with EU directives and setting ambitious national targets.

The share of renewable energy in Bulgaria's Gross Final Energy Consumption has seen a notable increase, reaching 22.6% in 2023, up from 19.04% in 2022. The sectoral shares of renewable energy also show an increase by 9.4 % in electricity produced from RES to 29.4%, followed by renewable energy for heating and cooling by 3.2%, reaching a share of 35%²⁷. This growth is attributed to significant investments in solar energy, with the country adding approximately 1.2 GW of solar capacity in 2023 and an additional 938 MW in 2024. By the end of 2024, projects totalling 4.1 GW were awaiting connection to the national grid²⁸.

However, wind energy development has remained stagnant since 2012, with no new wind farms commissioned, primarily due to administrative challenges and local opposition.

In recent years, a number of legislative changes have been introduced to liberalise the Bulgarian electricity market. Electricity providers benefit from various market advantages due to the range of products they can offer in the liberalised market, as well as competitive pricing and flexibility. The amendments to the Energy Act have significantly changed the operating conditions for those involved in the country's electricity market, including the Public Electricity Provider. The scope of the regulated market has considerably decreased, while the relative share of the free market has risen. All transactions for the purchase and sale of electricity are conducted via platforms in order to enhance trade transparency.

In accordance with the Commission's Third Liberalisation Package, Bulgaria has made progress towards completely liberalizing the electricity market. Due to legal modifications implemented since early 2018, all electricity generated for the free market is exclusively traded on the commercial platforms of the IBEX. Amendments to the Energy Act, which were approved on November 17, 2023, specify:

- (1) The complete liberalization of the wholesale electricity market is set to occur by June 30, 2024, while residential customers will remain in a regulated market until the end of 2025.
- (2) New participants in the electricity market, such as citizen energy communities, proactive consumers, and aggregators, are subject to regulation. Additionally, it includes strategies to safeguard energy service consumers by allowing them to enter into fixed-term and fixed-

²⁷ НСИ отчете ръст на дела на възобновяемата енергия в потреблението през 2023 г. - Енергетика - manager.bg

²⁸ <https://serbia-energy.eu/bulgaria-sees-growth-in-renewable-energy-capacity-despite-challenges-and-delays>

price agreements, as well as dynamic electricity pricing contracts for those who have a smart meter installed.

(3) Definitions and criteria have been established to define ‘households in energy poverty’ and ‘vulnerable electricity customers’ for the purpose of liberalising the electricity market and implementing measures to support households facing energy poverty, including preferential treatment when implementing programmes to enhance the energy efficiency of residential buildings.

In 2018, an intraday market was launched, which is the link between long-term negotiation, the short-term day-ahead market and the real time balancing market. Its implementation has strengthened the overall framework of the Bulgarian market, similar to that found in most European markets, enabling participants to adjust their contractual positions according to the forecast of production or consumption, as close as possible to the actual time of trade.

The challenges that Bulgaria's renewable energy expansion faces include administrative hurdles, grid infrastructure limitations, and the need for increased energy storage solutions. The Electricity System Operator has highlighted the necessity for developing reserve capacities, such as battery storage and pumped hydroelectric energy storage, to manage the intermittent nature of RES effectively²⁹.

In summary, while Bulgaria has made significant strides in developing its renewable energy sector and aligning with EU directives, still ongoing efforts are required to overcome existing challenges and achieve its long-term energy and climate objectives.

4.1.1. State-of-the-art of LFMs and FS, Transposition of EU Regulation

The recent changes to the RES Act impact the design of LFMs in Bulgaria. New concepts and players, including aggregators and citizen/renewable energy communities, are being introduced to align the relevant laws with the corresponding EU directives. Contractual agreements, competitive bidding, and market settlements will be modified to align with LFMs in addition to the existing rules governing the electricity market. LFMs are likely to need cutting-edge metering infrastructure, as well as IT systems that can handle the data efficiently. Furthermore, LFMs creation will be encouraged when citizens and households will be part of the free energy market which is expected to happen at the end of 2025.

²⁹ <https://www.bta.bg/en/news/577840-bulgaria-has-more-than-3-000-mw-of-renewable-energy-power-generation-capacities>

The flexible services offer a natural solution for all members of society to become active participants in the energy market, facilitating and promoting the transition to RES and the implementation of new technologies, which allows for effective management and balance of the energy system.

Although the stability and transparency of the organized free electricity market have improved with the incorporation of RES and various business customers, households lack sufficient motivation to participate in the free electricity market due to regulated pricing. There is ambiguity concerning the regulation of new technologies, smart energy networks and services. This hinders the development of flexible tariffs by traders to accurately cover individual consumption. An appropriate regulatory framework must be established to facilitate market flexibility, which includes solving energy sharing issues.

The decrease of the administrative and bureaucratic procedures will further ease the development of closed networks, and will clarify how citizens access the network – whether as producers or consumers of energy, etc. Despite some improvements in the Law on Territorial Development, a user or energy community must go through several different institutions to achieve their goal.

The development of energy markets foresees that all current players will remain active in the sector, but their roles will shift due to the emergence of new players, specifically prosumers, aggregators, and energy management systems for buildings and homes.

The energy communities represent another new market entrant and while they are defined in the Bulgarian legislation, there is a need to establish a more detailed regulatory framework and guidelines to promote their growth in the country.

In October 2023, Bulgaria amended its Energy from Renewable Sources Act to fully transpose the requirements of Directive (EU) 2018/2001. These amendments aim to simplify administrative procedures for renewable energy projects, establish energy communities, and promote the use of biofuels in transportation. Notably, the legislation introduces a three-month deadline for issuing construction permits for renewable energy facilities, regardless of capacity, and mandates the creation of administrative service centres in each municipality to guide and inform stakeholders about renewable energy projects³⁰. Still, further efforts and actions are needed to fully transpose the EU directives and comply with EU legislation.

³⁰ <https://www.bpva.org/en/actual/ministry-of-energy-proposes-for-public-consultation-amendments-to-the-renewable-energy-act>

4.1.2. Smart local flexibility Services - Compliance and Safety

The goals of Bulgaria's energy security are focused on enhancing the flexibility of the national energy system and strengthening network and information security (cybersecurity).

To enhance the capacity of the electricity transmission system in order to harness the significant potential of renewable energy (exceeding 8 GW, including green hydrogen) at both national and regional levels, it is essential to advance the digitalisation and automation of the transmission network. This involves the installation of devices for real-time monitoring, forecasting, modelling, and optimization of transmission capacities (Dynamic Line Rating, DLR), the implementation of flexible variable transmission solutions (FACTS), and facilitating more effective Demand-Side Response (DSR) in collaboration with national distribution system operators.

The balancing model in Bulgaria is transparent and ensures consistent conditions for balancing, irrespective of the production technology, the scale of the facilities, or whether prices are regulated or freely negotiated.

The total installed capacity of RES is quite substantial in comparison to the country's existing capacity, and the existence of two large units at the Kozloduy nuclear power plant, each with a capacity of 1 GW, helps ensure that there is capacity held in cold reserve and available for provision of additional services (primary and secondary regulation).

The liberalization of the electricity market has resulted in a reform of the balancing energy market, accomplishing the primary goals which include: market-driven procurement of balancing capacity; the release of balancing energy prices within 30 minutes following the closure of the intraday market; implementation of a unified balancing price for times when balancing energy is not activated; a 15-minute period for imbalance settlement; and no price limits imposed on balancing electricity.

These goals have been achieved through amendments to the Energy Act and to the associated regulations (such as the Electricity Trading Rules, the Methodology for determining balancing energy prices, and the Instructions for notifying and validating commercial and production schedules in the day-ahead and intraday market segments, among others).

Since 2016, both residential and non-residential low-voltage customers have had the option to change their electricity provider and engage in contracts at prices that are freely negotiated. Nevertheless, currently, a considerable portion of the market operates on regulated prices,

making up approximately 40% of total electricity production. Eliminating regulated prices for all consumers and producer rates will enhance competition among electricity providers.

In accordance with Regulation (EU) 2019/943 and Directive (EU) 2019/944 concerning the internal electricity market, and aiming for the eventual complete liberalization of the electricity market, Bulgaria is working to enhance the involvement of end customers in DR via aggregation. This includes enabling end customers, even those providing DR through the aggregation of all electricity markets alongside generators.

Complete liberalization of the electricity market will create the necessary conditions to enhance the system's flexibility by enabling competitive pricing and boosting the liquidity of the electricity exchange market. Achieving full liberalization of the electricity market is essential for realizing the goal of fully integrating the electricity market into the unified European energy market. Some notable examples about the active advancement in smart local FS, focusing on compliance and safety are:

- EVN Bulgaria's Participation in Balancing Markets

In January 2025, EVN Bulgaria (one of the Bulgarian TSO), in collaboration with CyberGrid³¹, was pre-qualified as an aggregator for balancing markets through its subsidiary, EVN Trading. Utilizing CyberGrid's flexibility management platform, CyberNoc, EVN Bulgaria began trading and monetizing flexibility in the manual Frequency Restoration Reserve (mFRR) energy market. This initiative received approval from Bulgaria's Transmission System Operator (ESO), ensuring compliance with national energy regulations. The project emphasizes safety and efficiency by enabling real-time monitoring and management of energy resources, as demonstrated by the integration of the Albena Resort and EVN Toplofikacia's combined heat and power plant in Plovdiv³².

- FlexiGrid Project's Implementation

The FlexiGrid project, initiated in November 2021, aimed to enhance the energy system flexibility in Bulgaria. The project focused on developing a blockchain-based platform allowing electricity distribution companies to procure grid FS from producers and consumers. In its final phase as of July 2023, the project involved installing smart electricity meters for selected pilot customers of ENERGO-PRO (one of the DSOs in Bulgaria) in the Varna region. These meters monitor production and consumption at 15-minute intervals, ensuring precise data collection and compliance with energy standards. The project's emphasis on real-time data monitoring

³¹ CyberGrid | Flexibility experts since 2010

³² <https://www.cyber-grid.com/knowledge/evn-bulgaria-goes-live-in-balancing-markets-with-cybernoc>

and blockchain technology addresses safety and regulatory considerations, providing solutions for optimizing distribution network operations³³.

- Deployment of Mobile Power Flow Control Technology

In June 2021, Bulgaria's ESO, in partnership with Smart Wires and as part of the EU-funded FLEXITRANSTORE project, installed an innovative mobile power flow control system in the North-eastern region that hosts 750 MW of wind energy generation. The technology enhances the grid's capacity to accommodate renewable energy and improves cross-border electricity flows between Bulgaria and Romania. The mobile nature of the solution allows for flexible redeployment, ensuring compliance with evolving energy demands and regulatory frameworks³⁴.

- Positive Energy Blocks Initiative in Smolyan

The Energy Agency of Plovdiv (EAP) is leading efforts to establish Positive Energy Blocks (PEBs) in Smolyan, Bulgaria, as part of the "Positive City Exchange" project. PEBs are urban areas that produce more energy than they consume. The initiative involves integrating advanced energy technologies, such as AI-based energy management and smart e-charging, into municipal sports and educational buildings. These efforts aim to increase self-sufficient energy production, promote prosuming, and ensure safety and compliance with energy regulations³⁵.

These examples highlight Bulgaria's proactive approach to implementing smart energy local FS, with a strong emphasis on compliance, safety, and efficiency.

³³ FlexiGrid - FlexiGrid

³⁴ <https://www.prnewswire.com/>

³⁵ https://managenergy.ec.europa.eu/managenergy-discover/news/energy-agency-plovdiv-uses-positive-energy-blocks-smart-energy-transition-2023-05-03_en

4.1.3. Business Models and Financing Mechanisms to Boost Stakeholder Motivation

Business models

LFMs in Bulgaria are still in their early stages, but as energy transition accelerates, various business models emerge. These models revolve around decentralized energy resources (DERs) like distributed solar, battery storage, DR, and electric vehicles. Here are some viable business models for Bulgaria's LFMs:

- **Aggregator Model:**

Aggregators play a pivotal role by consolidating the flexibility capacities of multiple DERs (producers and users - residential, commercial, and industrial energy users), enabling them to sell it to DSOs or balance responsible parties (BRPs) thus participating collectively in the market. This model facilitates the inclusion of smaller resources that individually may not meet market thresholds, thereby enhancing overall market liquidity and providing grid services such as congestion management and balancing. The challenges the model meets come from the need for digital infrastructure for real-time DR. An example of this business model is the Electrohold trade³⁶ which is a private aggregator of energy assets.

- **Utility-Led Flexibility Market:**

DSO or a vertically integrated utility creates a LFM platform where prosumers and flexibility providers trade services. Revenues are ensured by the participation fees from the market participants, cost savings from reducing grid congestion and avoiding infrastructure upgrades. (i.e. FlexiGrid project³⁷)

- **Peer-to-Peer (P2P) Energy Trading:**

P2P trading represents a decentralized market where consumers and prosumers can trade energy and FS directly using blockchain or digital platforms (FlexiGrid project). Revenue comes from transaction fees on energy and flexibility trades, subscription fees for platform access and value-added services (AI-based optimization, forecasting, etc.). Challenges are the regulatory uncertainty for P2P markets in Bulgaria and the lack of advanced metering and smart contracts.

- **Demand Response as a Service (DRaaS):**

Companies provide DR solutions, enabling businesses and households to reduce or shift consumption during peak periods in exchange for incentives. Revenue is generated from subscription-based models for businesses, revenue sharing from flexibility transactions and

³⁶ [Електрохолд Трейд](#)

³⁷ [Energo-Pro :: Проектът FlexiGrid навлезе в своята финална фаза](#)

incentives from grid operators and retailers. Challenges: Consumer engagement and awareness has to be increased. There is a need for investment in real-time automation technologies.

- **Industrial Flexibility Services:**

Large industrial consumers optimize energy use and sell excess flexibility to grid operators, reducing costs and generating additional revenue. The revenue comes from payments from DSOs for local grid support, wholesale market participation and savings from optimized energy consumption. Challenges: investments in energy management systems are needed; Industrial processes may not always allow flexibility.

- **Energy Communities:**

Local energy communities generate, store, and trade energy within a closed-loop system, offering FS to the grid. Revenue comes from membership fees and local energy trading and payments for grid FS. Challenges: Regulatory support for community energy models and government incentives for CEC/RECs and strong local participation and investment needed. At present some pilot projects have been implemented, initiated by some municipalities (Gabrovo, Burgas, Sofia) and supported by European projects.

Bulgaria's energy market regulations are evolving, but flexibility markets still need a structured legal framework. In regard to the technology Infrastructure smart meters, data platforms, and automation are critical for market success. LFM should integrate with the Bulgarian Electricity System Operator (ESO) and European balancing markets.

Financing mechanisms to motivate stakeholder participation

Developing LFM in Bulgaria requires strategic financing mechanisms to motivate stakeholder participation. Some of these approaches include:

Bulgaria is presently implementing a focused strategy for energy efficiency measures in buildings and in the business sector as well as for the use of renewable energy. Over the years, various support programs have been established to renovate the building stock of the country and to promote the production and consumption of energy from renewable sources.

- *Energy Efficiency and Renewable Sources Fund (EERSF):* Established under the Energy Efficiency Act, the EERSF operates as an independent legal entity separate from governmental institutions to offer technical assistance to Bulgarian enterprises, municipalities, and private individuals in developing energy efficiency investment projects. The fund provides financing, co-financing, or acts as a guarantor for these projects, facilitating investments in energy efficiency and renewable energy³⁸.

³⁸ <https://www.bgeef.com/en/about-us/>

- *Programme "Development of the Regions" 2021-2027*³⁹ (co-financed by the ERDF and the national budget) finances measures aimed at renewal and modernisation of roads, public infrastructure, energy efficiency and sustainable urban mobility, support for green urban environment, etc. A significant part is dedicated to promoting renewable energy and improving energy efficiency, contributing to Bulgaria's commitment to increasing the share of RES in its energy mix.
- *National Recovery and Resilience Plan*: The activities under the "Low Carbon Economy" component include support for new capacities for electricity production from RES and electricity storage; support for RE for households; for energy-efficient street lighting systems; for the development and utilization of geothermal energy and production of green hydrogen⁴⁰.
- *The National Program for Energy Efficiency of Multi-Family Residential Buildings*⁴¹ supports the implementation of energy efficiency measures including RES in Multi-Family Residential Buildings.
- *The EEA and Norway Grants 2021-2028* support projects in Bulgaria that aim to promote European green transition, social inclusion and resilience, democracy, rule of law and human rights.
- *National Decarbonisation Fund*: As part of its long-term renovation strategy and national Recovery and Resilience Plan, Bulgaria is establishing a National Decarbonisation Fund. This financial scheme aims to support investments in energy efficiency and renewable energy in buildings, including residential, industrial, commercial, and public structures. The fund is designed to leverage private financing and provide technical assistance to accelerate the decarbonisation of Bulgaria's building stock.
- *Leveraging Public and Private Investments*: Bulgaria's Integrated Energy and Climate plan outlines strategies to attract investments in energy efficiency and renewable energy. By creating favourable regulatory frameworks and offering financial incentives, the plan aims to mobilize both public funds and private capital towards sustainable energy projects, enhancing the flexibility and resilience of the local energy market⁴².
- *Utilizing Sustainable Energy Financing Facilities (SEFFs)*: SEFFs have been effective in Bulgaria, providing dedicated credit lines for energy efficiency and renewable energy projects. The facilities offer technical assistance and financing to businesses and homeowners, reducing the financial barriers to implementing energy solutions that contribute to market flexibility⁴³.

³⁹ General information on the RDP - Program "Development of the Regions" 2021-2027

⁴⁰ Дейности по Националния план за възстановяване и устойчивост

⁴¹ Energy Efficiency of Multi-Family Residential Buildings National Programme - Energy efficiency

⁴² energy.ec.europa.eu

⁴³ European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD)

- *Implementing Energy Efficiency Obligation Schemes (ESCO)*: Developing schemes that obligate energy companies to achieve energy savings can lead to investments in flexibility measures. Such mechanisms can include opportunities for participation in funds and markets dedicated to fulfilling these obligations, thereby stimulating stakeholder engagement in energy efficiency initiatives.

By implementing these financing mechanisms, Bulgaria can effectively motivate stakeholders to participate in the development of LFM, contributing to a more sustainable and resilient energy system. These financial mechanisms collectively aim to enhance stakeholder motivation and participation in the development of renewable energy projects across Bulgaria, contributing to the country's sustainable energy transition.

4.1.4. Awareness & Actions to Ensure High Customer Participation in the LFMs

The current legislation establishes the framework for the growth of self-consumers and renewable energy communities (REC), increasing interest and encouraging local residents to engage in the production and consumption of clean energy.

Dedicated administrative service centres have been set up for each municipality to provide guidance and information about the implementation of investment intentions for renewable energy production, including the modernisation of existing energy facilities and for the production of energy from renewable sources.

Enhancing customer participation in Bulgaria's LFMs requires a comprehensive approach that addresses regulatory frameworks, technological infrastructure, and consumer engagement.

Bulgaria has liberalized its power market for commercial and administrative consumers, permitting aggregation and demand-side flexibility but there is no a licensing scheme for aggregators and ongoing reforms in the balancing energy market. To foster higher customer participation, it is essential to establish clear regulations that facilitate aggregator operations and streamline market entry for various stakeholders.

Investing in advanced technological infrastructure, such as smart metering systems and energy storage solutions can provide both local and system services, benefiting utilities and independent power producers. Deploying such technologies enhance grid flexibility and reliability, making participation more attractive to consumers.

Empowering consumers through the establishment of energy communities will significantly boost participation and enable collective investment in RES and active involvement in energy markets. Implementing supportive policies and providing incentives for the formation of such

communities will lead to increased consumer engagement and a more decentralized energy system.

Addressing all these areas and providing specific, tailor made consultancy services and information and training through energy offices and one stop platforms, Bulgaria will create an environment that encourages active customer participation in LFM, leading to a more sustainable and efficient energy system.

4.1.5. Strategic Planning Documents

Bulgaria's strategic planning for energy is primarily outlined in its Integrated National Energy and Climate Plan (INECP) for 2021-2030. This comprehensive document details the country's objectives and measures across five key dimensions: decarbonisation, energy efficiency, energy security, internal energy market, and research, innovation, and competitiveness. The NECP aims to achieve a sustainable and flexible energy system, aligning with the European Green Deal and the European Climate Act. It emphasizes increasing the share of RES in electricity production, transport, and heating and cooling sectors {See Table 2}. Specific measures include diversifying energy resources, enhancing the national energy system's flexibility, and improving interconnectivity and cybersecurity.

In response to evolving EU policies, Bulgaria updated its INECP in December 2023, proposing a target of 33% renewable energy in its energy mix by 2030. However, this falls short of the 44% target required by the 2018 EU Renewable Energy Directive. Consequently, the European Commission has urged Bulgaria to intensify its efforts to meet the EU-wide goal of 42.5% renewable energy by 2030 (See Figure 1).

Additionally, the REPowerEU plan focuses on energy savings, diversifying energy supplies, and accelerating the rollout of renewable energy. It proposes increasing the EU's 2030 target for renewable energy to 45% and emphasizes the rapid deployment of solar and wind energy projects.

In summary, the **updated Bulgarian Integrated Plan in the Field of Energy and Climate /INECP**⁴⁴ is in line with the high targets set by the European Green Deal, the Fit for 55 package and the REPowerEU Plan. Bulgaria has launched a legislative initiative to change the national legal framework to help achieve the objectives set out in the INECPs.

Slow progress in achieving the energy efficiency targets for the building sector has a negative impact on productivity and competitiveness and for that reason requires focused policies and

⁴⁴ INECP, Integrated Plan in the Field of Energy and Climate of the Republic of Bulgaria Updated 2024

measures. Significant energy savings can be achieved through targeted investments in low-emission energy infrastructure, by increasing renewable electricity and improving energy efficiency that are essential elements of the goal pursued to build a climate-neutral energy system in Bulgaria.

The energy sector's future development is building on the efficient use of alternative energy resources, the development of the energy market and smart systems, the direct involvement of citizens and society in the energy transition, and the active participation of consumers in the electricity market.

Some of the main objectives set out in the INECPs include: to simulate the low-carbon development of the economy; to develop competitive and secure energy; to enhance energy efficiency and provide access to affordable energy for every consumer.

National energy priorities encompass:

- increasing energy security and diversifying the supply of energy resources and developing an integrated and competitive energy market;
- accelerating the uptake of renewable energy production and consumption, promoting renewable self-consumption, developing RECs and developing related energy infrastructure for the transmission, distribution and storage of RE, grid development;
- increasing energy efficiency by developing and applying new technologies to achieve modern and sustainable energy;
- safeguarding consumers by ensuring fair, transparent and non-discriminatory conditions for accessing energy services.

National priority is the development of the energy sector, in particular the electricity sector, with a focus on national and regional energy security and as well as the liberalisation of energy markets, with commitment to manage possible social risks and negative impacts on vulnerable social groups.

Having in mind the future growth of energy demand and supply, Bulgaria fosters the sustainable development of renewable electricity generation on market bases and supports an increase in the share of renewable energy in gross final energy consumption. The national target for the share of RES in gross final energy consumption by 2030 is set to 34.1%.

The electricity sector aims for 42.2 % share of energy from RES in gross final consumption of electricity by 2030. This share is expected to occur by boosting electricity consumption from newly built RES capacities, predominantly wind and solar, after 2020, by as much as 4,778 MW.

To reach the goals in the electricity sector, it is crucial to encourage investment in enhancing the nation's electricity transmission and distribution systems. This will facilitate the technical connection and integration of electricity generated from RES, all while adhering to the electricity system's security standards. The implementation of energy storage systems will facilitate the installation of new capacities and tackle issues related to grid congestion, balance, and market distortion.

A key element in the full liberalisation process is the safeguarding of energy poor and vulnerable customers as Bulgaria is phasing out regulated electricity prices by the end of 2025. Other policies and measures aimed at developing the internal energy market in line with the EU objectives are DR, promoting the creation of RECs and stimulating a more active role for consumers.

Table 2: Bulgaria's 2030 targets (INECP, updated 2024)

Renewable Energy Sources	
National target for the share of RES in gross final energy consumption by 2030	34.1 %
Share of electricity from renewable sources in gross final consumption of electricity	42.2 %
Share of heating and cooling from RES in gross final consumption of heating and cooling	45.5 %
Share of energy from RES in final energy consumption in the transport sector	29 %
Energy Efficiency	
Reduction of primary energy consumption compared to Reference Scenario 2020	11.6 %

Bulgaria is currently pursuing a targeted strategy to advance its renewable energy sector. A set of regulatory, administrative and financial measures have been put in place to promote the production and consumption of energy from renewable sources.

Clear deadlines have been introduced with regard to the connection of RES plants for production of electricity and measures to speed up connection procedures for the RES electricity generation sites.

The present legislation creates the conditions for the development of self-consumers and RECs, raising interest and activating the participation of local populations to produce and consume clean energy. This is expected to lead to increased investment activity, a positive uptake of renewable energy, greater consumer choice and greater involvement of citizens in the energy transition.

Figure 1: Share of energy from renewable sources by 2030 (INECP, updated 2024)

4.1.6. Policy Guidelines for Facilitating Deployment of LFM and Exploitation of Flexibility

To align with the EU's climate objectives and ensure energy security, Bulgaria should consider the following guidelines and recommendations for its energy long-term frameworks (LTFs) and enhance of energy flexibility up to 2030:

- **Regulatory Framework to Enhance LFM**

Clear regulations have to be established to facilitate the operation of LFM, enabling DERs to participate effectively. All relevant parties, including DSOs, TSOs, and energy service companies, etc. should be involved in the regulatory development process to ensure comprehensive and practical guidelines.

Legal frameworks and pilot programs will encourage the adoption of innovative energy solutions. An appropriate regulatory framework must be established to facilitate market flexibility, which includes solving energy sharing issues.

The administrative and bureaucratic processes have to be reduced to facilitate the establishment of closed networks and clarify how citizens engage with the network—whether as producers or consumers of energy, as users or energy communities must still navigate various institutions to reach their objectives. Still further efforts and actions are needed to fully transpose the EU directives and comply with EU legislation.

- **Energy Sources Diversification**

In line with the NECP the share of energy from RES in gross final energy consumption has to be increased to at least 34.1% by 2030, focusing on solar, wind, and hydroelectric power. Large solar parks and small distributed power generation systems with PV capacity to around 2,645

MW are planned to be installed by 2030. At least 2 GW of new wind power installations, particularly in areas with favourable wind conditions have to be developed. Hydropower already plays an important role in Bulgaria's energy mix, that is why the focus has to be on the modernization and optimization of existing hydroelectric power plants.

- ***Battery Storage Systems Utilisation***

The deployment of battery storage to manage the variability of RES, ensuring a stable and reliable power supply needs to be promoted. The potential of pumped hydro storage projects, such as utilizing existing reservoirs like Dospat and Batak, to provide large-scale energy storage solutions should be explored.

- ***Demand Side Flexibility Enhancement***

Complete liberalization of the electricity market will create the necessary conditions to enhance the system's flexibility by enabling competitive pricing and boosting the liquidity of the electricity exchange market. Smart electrical meters have to be installed. The electricity grid has to be further upgraded with smart technologies to enable real-time monitoring and management of energy consumption. Programs that encourage consumers to adjust their energy usage during peak periods, contributing to grid stability and efficiency have to be initiated and developed.

- ***Energy Infrastructure Modernisation***

Investments in the modernization of the national grid to accommodate the increasing share of renewables, ensuring efficient transmission and distribution have to continue. Cross-border energy connections have to be strengthened, such as the Gas Interconnector Greece–Bulgaria, to diversify energy sources and enhance system flexibility.

- ***Energy Efficiency Measures***

Programs to improve insulation and EE in residential and public buildings, addressing energy poverty and reducing overall consumption have to be further implemented and industries to adopt energy-efficient technologies and processes to lower energy intensity to be encouraged.

- ***Phasing Out Coal Reliance***

A clear roadmap to reduce coal-based energy production has to be followed, aiming for a complete phase-out by 2038 or earlier, in line with EU directives. Investments in economic diversification and retraining programs in coal-dependent areas should be accomplished to mitigate social and economic impacts.

- ***Innovation and Research Support***

The development of pilot projects that test new technologies and business models for FS have to be further encouraged. Partnerships with research institutions to explore innovative solutions and best practices in flexibility continued.

- ***Public Engagement***

Citizens have to be educated and involved in energy transition plans to build public support and ensure equitable policy implementation. Self-consumption and development of energy communities in the country have to be promoted based on developed models.

These goals are part of the broader European Union strategy to achieve climate neutrality by 2050 and are in line with Bulgaria's commitments under the Paris Agreement. Achieving these goals will require significant investments in infrastructure, technology and training. Bulgaria should enhance its energy flexibility, ensuring a resilient and efficient energy system aligned with European Union climate objectives.

4.2. Greece

Greece's renewable energy sector is experiencing rapid development in recent years. The share of renewables in the country's electricity mix has grown in the last 5 years, reaching over 50 % in 2023. The country aims to double its renewable energy capacity by 2030, which is expected to grow from 14 GW in 2022 to 28 GW in 2030.

The high investment interest in developing new RES for the period 2023-2030 ensures the achievement of the new higher targets set, but also highlights significant needs in supporting, expanding and upgrading Greece's electricity transmission and distribution network in order to integrate the projects into the system reliably and safely.

Near-future reforms in Greece are focused on cost reduction and electrification driven by modern technologies: further development of e-mobility, energy-efficient buildings as well as smart grids implementation.

An important milestone in the integration of Greece with the European market followed by internal market restructuring is the introduction of Demand Response.

From 2025 to 2030 inclusive, the average annual consumer price is expected to decrease, in particular due to increased RES penetration combined with storage facilities and a focus on energy efficiency, in parallel with the gradual reduction in the prices of energy products as a result of the easing of the energy crisis.

The objectives for the electricity market, complementing the guidelines of the EU, are to ensure proper functioning and competitiveness for the benefit of final customers.

The role of consumers is now upgraded by enabling them to provide energy from small-scale RES plants and FS through DR schemes or smart charging of electric vehicles in the grid.

4.2.1. State-of-the-art of LFM's and FS, Transposition of EU Regulation

Greece has an overall successful implementation and satisfactory performance of the functioning electricity market, with important results being the reduction of prices in the balancing market and the increase of the intraday market liquidity.

In November 2020, Greece adopted the target model for its balancing market, introducing mechanisms such as the balancing capacity market, balancing energy market, and imbalance settlements.

Greece has opened their ancillary services markets to demand-side flexibility (DSF), as well as FCR, aFRR and mFRR markets from July 2022. They were opened fully with both demand-side flexibility and aggregation allowed, 1 MW min bid size, no BRP agreement required and an asymmetrical product design⁴⁵.

Companies like Sympower have emerged as key players, pooling energy flexibility from various businesses and offering it in balancing markets. In October 2022, Sympower secured 37 MW of capacity from industrial partners, marking a milestone as the first independent aggregator in Greece's balancing markets⁴⁶.

Initiatives like the Greek Simulator⁴⁷ focus on testing new market tools and mechanisms. These simulations aim to incorporate novel flexibility-related services into electricity markets, expanding the existing regulatory framework to include distribution networks.

To overcome barriers such as high minimum capacity requirements and limited market accessibility for DERs, Greece has undertaken reforms aimed to promote the integration of FS into the energy market.

The transposition of IEMD 2019/943, IEMD 2019/944 and RED II 2018/2001 directives have been implemented in the Greek legislation in laws 4986/2022, 5037/2023 and 4951/2022.

In order to reduce barriers to licensing and grid connections for RES two major updates to legislation are implemented in Law 4685/2020 and Law 4951/2022 aiming to reduce the duration of the licensing process from an average of 5 years (with some projects taking much longer) to 24 months, to facilitate the granting of licences to 12 GW of renewable energy projects by 2030. The goal of Law 4951 is to decrease grid congestion, while the TSO and DSO have to make significant investments to expand grid infrastructure and reduce the waiting time to connect renewables generation.

The National Climate Law, adopted in May 2022, sets targets to reduce total greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by 55% by 2030, and to reach net zero emissions by 2050. It defines key emissions reduction measures, including the phase-out of lignite-fired generation by 2028.

In Greece there are more than 1,600 energy communities registered that operate renewable energy systems with an installed capacity of more than 1 GW mainly dominated by companies.

⁴⁵ smartEn – 2022 Market Monitor - For Demand Side Flexibility (2023)

⁴⁶ <https://sympower.net/news/sympower-goes-live-in-greeces-balancing-markets>

⁴⁷ Flexibility market – Market Simulator in Greece | FEVER

In 2024 the legal framework was adapted to facilitate the establishment of energy communities by cooperatives, citizens' groups and municipalities. In December 2023, the Greek government made 42 million EUR available with the support of the EU Structural and Investment Fund to support locally operated energy communities that operate via net metering or virtual net metering. The projects must use RES to meet the electricity needs of municipal buildings such as hospitals, schools and sports halls and the electricity generated can also be used for households in energy poverty. Funding is provided for 80 % of the costs of energy community projects with a minimum installed capacity of 0.3 MW⁴⁸.

4.2.2. Smart Local Flexibility Services - Compliance and Safety

In Greece, the integration of smart local FS is advancing through collaborative efforts between industry stakeholders and regulatory bodies, focusing on compliance and safety. These services aim to enhance grid stability and efficiency by enabling demand-side flexibility and active system management.

The Greek energy market has undergone significant reforms to accommodate FS. The Independent Power Transmission Operator (IPTO) oversees the integration of FS, ensuring that providers comply with established protocols and prequalification processes. This includes rigorous testing and validation to confirm that flexibility service providers (FSPs) can deliver the required services reliably and safely⁴⁹.

Ensuring the safety and reliability of FS involves the deployment of advanced technological solutions and tools that enable system operators to predict and mitigate potential issues such as grid congestion or voltage irregularities, thereby maintaining operational safety. Additionally, real-time monitoring and automated control systems are implemented to promptly address any deviations, ensuring that FS do not compromise grid stability.

Independent aggregators like Sympower that participate on the Greek energy market collaborate with the Greek Transmission System Operator (TSO) to tailor FS to local requirements. Sympower's platform integrates various energy assets, providing real-time monitoring and optimization to ensure compliance with regulatory standards and operational safety. By October 2024, Sympower expanded its portfolio to 300 MW of daily DR capacity in Greece, partnering with local businesses to enhance grid resilience and support the energy transition⁵⁰.

⁴⁸ EU project - Integrating energy communities into sector coupling

⁴⁹ <https://www.mdpi.com/2076-3417/13/20/11248>

⁵⁰ <https://www.energetika.net/eu/novice/trading/sympower-expands-greek-flexibility-capacity-to-300-mw>

Pilot projects play a crucial role in testing and validating FS within real-world settings. The iFLEX project, for example, focuses on aggregating household consumption flexibility to address imbalances between supply and demand. By integrating intelligent assistants into existing mobile applications, households can participate in DR events, contributing to grid stability while receiving incentives. These initiatives not only enhance the safety and reliability of the energy system but also engage consumers in the energy transition process⁵¹.

The technological upgrade and digitalisation of energy networks, which is the basis for maximising not only the operation but also the flexibility of the energy system is an important issue. There is a need to increase the share of household consumers equipped with smart meters in Greece⁵² that will increase their involvement in the FS market.

In summary, the deployment of smart local FS in Greece is underpinned by a robust regulatory framework, advanced technological solutions, active industry participation, and community-focused pilot projects. These elements collectively ensure that the integration of FS adheres to compliance standards and maintains the safety and reliability of the national grid.

4.2.3. Business Models and Financing Mechanisms to Boost Stakeholder Motivation

The reorganisation of the Greek electricity market and its alignment with the corresponding European electricity market along the lines of the “Target Model” was completed in the period 2020-2022. From 1st November 2020, the Greek electricity market became operational along the lines of the European Target Model, i.e. the single electricity market model applicable in all EU countries. The Greek energy market has fully complied with the three markets that comprise the Target Model, in particular: the Day-Ahead Market, operated by the Greek Energy Exchange (ERA), the Intra-Day Market, which also is operated by the ERA and the Balancing Market, operated by the Independent Power Transmission Operator (ADMIE), and in addition, the Forward Market, which manages the ERA.

In order to increase the economic benefit of final customers, there is a need to further modernise the electricity transmission system and distribution network through their digitalisation, in order to enable the real time participation of consumption in the electricity market as well as to enable dynamic energy packages from suppliers to also take part in the market.

⁵¹ <https://www.iflex-project.eu/responding-to-requests-for-shifting-electricity-use>

⁵² Share of household consumers equipped with a smart meter

For the transition to green energy, the financing of investment expenditure in the final energy consumption sectors (e.g. expenditure for the purchase of advanced technology vehicles) has to be considered. Access to finance of low- and middle-income households has to be facilitated in the coming years. Programmes (such as "Exoikonomo 2021"⁵³) including incentives to support poor and vulnerable households will need to be further developed in the future.

Policy Priority 2 (PP2) of the National Energy and Climate Plan for 2030 describes in detail the support schemes for granting of operating aid to RES plants and for promotion of storage systems (see PP2 in p.4.2.5).

In addition, Policy Priority 3 (PP3) presents self-consumption schemes; programmes for households and farmers and a subsidy programme for businesses (see PP3 in p.4.2.5).

4.2.4. Awareness & Actions to Ensure High Customer Participation in the LFM

The increasing penetration of DERs into the electricity system requires greater customer engagement in providing new FS. The main behavioural barriers and existing gaps related to customer engagement in the emerging flexibility markets can be defined as: lack of awareness, lack of skills to process information, and inactivity.

To ensure high customer participation, it is crucial to educate energy consumers, businesses, and local communities about the benefits and workings of LFM.

Raising Awareness about LFM. Actions to be implemented:

- *Public Information Campaigns:* The Greek government and energy regulators can initiate educational campaigns via TV, radio, and social media.
- *Workshops and Webinars:* Online and in-person events with local municipalities, businesses, and energy cooperatives should be organized.
- *Demonstration Projects:* Real-world case studies should be highlighted where Greek consumers have benefited from flexibility markets.

Example: The HEDNO (ΔΕΔΔΗΕ)⁵⁴ pilot projects aim to test flexibility services at the distribution level, providing valuable insights for future market integration.

Incentives & Financial Benefits for Participation. Customers must see direct benefits to participate in these markets. Actions to be done:

⁵³ SAVE 2021 : Home
⁵⁴ Strategic Projects | HEDNO

- *Dynamic Pricing & Time-of-Use Tariffs:* Consumers can be rewarded for shifting electricity use to off-peak times.
- *Financial Incentives & Grants:* Subsidies for households and businesses installing battery storage and smart grid technologies.
- *Revenue Opportunities:* Aggregators or energy communities can trade excess flexibility and share profits with participants.

Example: Save & Autonomy (“Εξοικονομώ – Αυτονομώ”) program⁵⁵ provides financial support for smart energy upgrades, indirectly encouraging flexibility participation.

Leveraging Energy Communities. Greece has a strong framework for Energy Communities, which can act as aggregators and facilitators in local flexibility markets. Actions to happen:

- Encourage Energy Communities to participate in flexibility markets by pooling resources and offering local grid services.
- Support Energy Communities with training and regulatory consultancy to enable them to act as market players.
- Simplify registration and participation processes for individuals joining Energy Communities.

Example: The Sifnos Energy Community⁵⁶ promotes renewable energy and could integrate local flexibility services.

Technology and Digital Infrastructure. Customers need access to the right technology in order to engage. Actions to be taken:

- Smart Meter Rollout Acceleration will ensure real-time tracking of energy usage.
- AI & IoT-based Demand Response Systems will enable automatic load adjustments.
- User-Friendly Platforms and Applications allow customers to track participation and earnings.

Example: The HEDNO⁵⁷ Smart Meter Pilot in Melitaia and Lesvos aims to enhance consumer awareness of energy usage.

Regulatory Support & Simplification. A clear, supportive regulatory environment will foster participation. Needed actions:

- The sign-up process for households and businesses has to be simplified.

⁵⁵ 'Saving - Autonomy' programme for residential buildings' energy upgrade - Eurofound EU PolicyWatch

⁵⁶ PRESENTATION – Ενεργειακή Κοινότητα Σίφνου Ε.Κοιν.Π.Ε.

⁵⁷ Strategic Projects | HEDNO

- Transparent pricing mechanisms for flexibility services ensured.
- A stable legal framework should be established that protects consumer rights.

Example: The Greece-Northern Macedonia cross-border flexibility cooperation is an example of regulatory-driven energy innovation.

By combining awareness campaigns, financial incentives, energy community participation, technological upgrades, and regulatory support, Greece can drive high customer participation in LFM. Greek-specific pilot programs and initiatives, such as HEDNO's smart grid projects and energy communities, can serve as models for success.

4.2.5. Strategic Planning Documents

The development of the **National Energy and Climate Plan for 2030**, launched in 2019, combined with the Greek energy privatisation plan and the significant rise of RES in its electricity generation underpins Greece's strong role as an important participant in the European energy market. The revised plan in 2023⁵⁸ sets ambitious goals, aiming for a 58.6% decrease in greenhouse gas emissions by 2030 and obtaining 79% of electricity requirements from RES over the coming ten years. Greece's plan sets the target for energy efficiency at 5% by 2030, rising considerably to 14% by 2035. Greenhouse gas emissions are expected to decrease by 54% by 2030 (See Table 3).

The National Energy and Climate Plan for 2030 of Greece can play the role of a detailed roadmap towards climate neutrality by 2050, with important targets outlined for 2030.

In addition, the targets in the new plan provide for: PVs to be set at 13.4 GW and offshore wind farms capacity to be eventually 1.9 GW; for electricity storage it is estimated that by 2030 a total capacity portfolio of 5.3 GW will be in operation, while the installed capacity of batteries will be set at 3.1 GW. The total installed capacity of gas-fired power plants is expected to increase from 7 to 7.7 GW by the end of the decade. This means that one more plant will be built by 2030, by which time all lignite plants must be retired.

⁵⁸ [Revised National Energy and Climate Plan lays out energy roadmap for Greece - Lexology](#)

Table 3: Summary of revised NECP objectives for 2030

Renewable Energy Sources	
National target for the share of energy from renewable sources in gross final energy consumption by 2030	44 %
Share of electricity from renewable sources in gross final consumption of electricity	79 %
Share of heating and cooling from RES in gross final consumption of heating and cooling	46 %
Share of energy from renewable sources in final energy consumption in the transport sector	29 %
Energy Efficiency	
Reduction of primary energy consumption compared to Reference Scenario 2020	5 %

Source: *Revised National Energy and Climate Plan lays out energy roadmap for Greece - Lexology*

In order to achieve the active participation of consumption in the energy market through DR, the installation of smart metres by 2030 is planned to happen. Since 2021, 13.000 smart meters have been deployed at medium voltage level and 70.000 at low voltage level, mainly for high electricity demand meters. In 2022, 100.000 smart meters were installed. It is estimated to increase to 500.000 in 2023 and above 800.000 per year from 2024 to 2030.

Regarding the electricity prices, the estimate in the plan suggests that prices will decline over time. The higher cost of electricity was a result of the new technology installations in Greece along with significant investments in the electricity infrastructure to accommodate RES and to maintain gas-fired power plants utilized as back-up units. Due to the decreasing cost of renewables the overall cost of electricity generation is expected to lower in the future.

NECP provisions

Achieving the target of 44 % set for RES as a share of total gross energy consumption for 2030 requires the development of regulatory and techno-economic policies and measures with a specific timetable. The policy measures for the promotion of RES in the period 2023-2030 aim to cover eight different policy priorities (PP1-PP8) as follows:

[PP1: Reforming a licensing framework and updating the special spatial space for RES – Acceleration, digitalisation and efficiency of licensing](#)

The aim is to further shorten permitting times for the installation of an RES plant, step up investment and strengthen the climate of confidence, thus attracting more investment to the future. Simplified licensing procedures and shortening the response times of the services, the defined preconditions for implementing the various licensing stages set for investors, and the completion and full operation of the RES information system are carried out for the digitisation of licensing procedures, the subsequent licensing of a RES plant, the interoperability of the

individual systems and the existence of a point of contact where the investor can turn to all licensing issues.

[PP2: Ensuring that RES and Storage Investments are implemented – Extension of Schemes Active Aid – Promotion of bilateral contracts](#)

In the period 2023-2030, RES will play a leading role in the energy mix, while in the domestic electricity sector already in 2025 their share is estimated to be above 58%.

In the period 2023-2030, the existence of a support scheme for the granting of operating aid to RES plants will continue either through competitive bidding procedures or outside the process for RES plant technologies which do not require a tender procedure. A corresponding support scheme will apply to RES plants with a storage system.

The framework for the participation of RES projects directly in the electricity markets and the conclusion of bilateral contracts has to be further enhanced, so that without receiving operating support, these plants can participate in the energy market to recover part of the investment.

To guarantee a consistent revenue stream and secure bank financing, they may enter into bilateral contracts with suppliers, consumers, and Cumulative Representation Bodies. Bilateral contracts will also be available via a digital form with an administrator tasked with managing and settling the transactions. The aim is to create the necessary liquidity in the market, ensuring mutual benefits for participants and competitive prices.

Measures promoting storage systems of short duration e.g. cumulative storage systems will be implemented. In order to achieve the NECP objective of installing 3.1 GW of electricity storage stations, the aim is to extend the specific support scheme for capacity beyond 1 000 MW, and policies will also be adopted to promote RES plants with integrated storage.

[PP3: Promoting dispersed RES systems, Hybrid island systems and empowering local communities and consumers](#)

Self-consumption schemes have to be implemented in accordance with the new institutional framework established by Law 5037/2023⁵⁹ and the incorporation of RED II. This can be achieved both by ensuring the availability of electrical space for the condition of RES plants for self-consumption and by financing part of the installation to make this feasible and sustainable.

There is a special provision and a specific electric space of 10 MW per substation for self-consumption plants of up to 10.8 kW reserved to accommodate the needs of households,

⁵⁹ New Energy law 5037/2023 Economou & Economou law office

farmers and SMEs, while the remaining available substations and the network are allocated 20% to auto power plants and 80 % to other RES power plants.

In addition, for households and farmers, programmes for installing photovoltaic at the building roofs and in the fields have been launched with resources from the Recovery and Resilience Fund (RRF) and the installation of battery PV plants to cover their own needs through the application of energy compensation. For businesses, a subsidy programme, with a total budget of EUR 160 million from the RRF will be available for the installation of PV plants with a battery exclusively for self-consumption.

The promotion of dispersed production and self-consumption has further to be enhanced through a specific framework for the installation of PV plants in buildings, simplified procedures for connecting them and collective self-consumption, while also exploiting available electric space in the urban fabric. The actions will be strengthened through a special self-consumption register established by the Network Operator and the promotion of 'energy coaching' to shape active consumers and optimise energy habits.

RECs and CECs play an active role in the implementation of policies to promote RES in final consumption. EUR 100 million from the RRF and other available financial instruments will be used to strengthen the role of local communities and consumers. Specific actions and grant investment aid provide effective support for the development, construction and operation of RES plants to reduce the electricity costs, as well as to cover all electricity consumption of energy vulnerable households. A technical assistance and advisory mechanism will support the communities, identify and eliminate obstacles to their development and simplify and update the institutional framework governing them.

[PP4: Ensuring the sustainability and liquidity of the mechanism for granting operational splitting to RES power plants and storage plants](#)

Since 1 January 2016, RES power plants have joined the electricity market and have been included in a support scheme in the form of operating aid. This aid scheme will continue to support overall RES technologies for electricity generation as well as storage plants, while special provision will continue to be made for small installed capacity installations where operating aid for the type of fixed price will be applied. In this context, a specific mechanism and follow-up procedure is in place to adjust the reference value of the relevant RES technology for projects not yet in operation, in line with developments in financing and operation costs of these plants. The development of environmental markets utilizing Guarantees of Origin for RES electricity is planned for the upcoming period to serve as a complementary market mechanism.

PP5: Development and strengthening of energy networks and optimal integration and operation of RES plants – Energy storage

New regulatory models for the distribution of charges for new network and system development projects have been designed and implemented to facilitate such projects to connect small producers. Substations built by producers (mainly for wind power stations) could now be used to serve the distribution lines of the network, as in this case it would allow more RES plants to be connected to the grid, and the regulatory framework will have to be modernised. The development of new financing models for the rapid deployment of the specific infrastructure will be launched, while management complexity and time delays due to external factors have to be reduced through effective planning and transparent consultation procedures.

A comprehensive legislative and regulatory framework is also under way to limit the injection into the grids of electricity produced by RES stops, with a view to making better use of the grids and maximising the difficulty of absorbing energy from RES plants in areas with limited absorption capacity.

In order to limit cuts in renewable production to the economic minimum level, while ensuring uninterrupted supply to consumers, increased flexibility in the system is needed and therefore the importance of sources of flexibility, such as storage, is further increased. The development of storage systems behind the meter will add electrical space to the grid as it offers the possibility to limit the injected energy during maximum generation hours, thus offering the possibility to absorb RES electricity.

A benefit for system operators is the optimisation of network stability through the provision of ancillary services (e.g. control, frequency response and power quality), while at the same time the ability of the network to accommodate new RES units through management services will increase. New participation in additional energy markets, such as the balancing market and the Month Cross Capacity Adequacy Compensation Mechanism⁶⁰, are being opened, which implies increased profitability for the investment and a reduction in need to strengthen it.

PP6: Ensuring minimum RES participation in meeting energy needs in the building sector – adaptations to the building regulation – promotion of energy sharing

The potential for RES penetration in buildings remains high, leading to the adoption of specific policy measures for its efficient use. A key tool will be the implementation of a regulatory framework for the obligation to share RES in meeting the energy needs of the building sector.

⁶⁰ Report-I-CRM-final.pdf

Targeted solutions and regulations to promote the collective self-consumption of 'green' energy in residential complexes and share it among tenants are measures of first importance, as housing complexes are home to almost 60 % of the Greek population.

The above provisions of the regulatory framework will be incorporated into the revised Energy Performance of Buildings Regulation, and particular emphasis will be placed on the exemplary role that public buildings used by the public sector must take on by setting minimum RES participation thresholds, taking into account the criteria of economic viability and energy benefit. Removing barriers to installation of RES and storage systems in buildings through targeted adaptations of the Buildings Regulation will take place. Policy measures for the implementation and promotion of self-consumption schemes and other measures concerning public and private buildings in the field of energy efficiency will be developed.

[PP7: Promote the use of RES systems to cover heating and cooling needs](#)

The promotion of efficient heating and cooling systems is a key policy priority. 17% of residential buildings are expected to meet the positive needs with air-to-water heat pumps in 2030. The increased penetration of heat pumps in the case of tertiary sector buildings is expected to be close to 69% and 90% in 2030 and 2050 respectively. In addition, support will be given to the promotion of RES systems, such as thermal solar systems, contributing both to the improvement of energy efficiency and to the further penetration of RES for heating and cooling. In the same time, programmes for the installation of PV storage systems for self-generation to produce electricity from RES will be activated to meet thermal and cooling needs through water-grade pumps and reduce energy costs for consumers. The promotion of efficient heating and cooling systems will increase the share of RES in heating and cooling, which is estimated to be 46% and 100% in 2030 and 2050 respectively.

[PP8: Promotion of new technologies and coupling of energy sectors with a focus on making maximum use of domestic renewable energy potential](#)

Maximising the domestic potential of RES and promoting new spin-offs is a key concern of policy efforts leading up to 2030 to achieve the targets. In order to increase the economic benefit of final customers, it is important to further modernise the electricity transmission system and distribution network through their digitalisation, so as to enable the participation of consumption in the electricity market in real time and to enable dynamic energy packages from suppliers to participate in the electricity market.

In order to achieve the active participation of consumption in the energy market through DR, it is necessary to install "off-the-counter" meters. In the coming years in parallel to the development of smart meters, it is expected to promote dynamic electricity prices on the part

of suppliers, with variable tariffs adjusted to electricity market prices over the days. These tariffs will encourage consumers to adjust their consumption profile by reducing it during periods of high electricity prices and increasing the profile of high RES generation.

4.2.6. Policy Guidelines for Facilitating Deployment of LFM and Exploitation of Flexibility

LFMs enable DER—such as distributed generation, DR, and storage systems—to provide FS, ensuring grid stability and efficient renewable integration. Greece plans to significantly expand its RES capacity, enhance energy storage solutions, and modernize its energy infrastructure. To achieve this, the ambitious targets to transform its energy landscape by 2030, aiming for 82% of its electricity generation from RES, the following actions have to be taken into consideration:

- **Regulatory and Policy Framework**

Further follow the transposition of the EU directives. Efforts were made to reduce the average licensing time for RES projects from 5 years to 14 months, encouraging faster deployment⁶¹. The government conducts auctions for RES projects, promoting cost-effective renewable energy integration⁶². The Offshore Wind Law from 2022 establishes a framework for developing offshore wind farms, aiming for 2 GW by 2030. Dynamic network usage tariffs (DNUT) are introduced that reflect the real-time state of the network, encouraging participants to offer flexibility in locations and times most beneficial for grid operation. Development of standardized protocols and interfaces can further facilitate seamless integration of various DERs into the LFM.

- **Renewable Energy Expansion**

The updated NECP outlines specific capacity goals for various RES technologies by 2030: More than 28 GW cumulative renewables capacity is aimed by 2030: an increase of PVs to 14.1 GW from the current 5 GW; 2.7 GW offshore wind with a focus on floating offshore wind farms due to the deep waters surrounding Greece, 7.1 GW onshore wind, 4.0 GW hydro power and remaining 800 MW to come from other renewables.

- **Energy Storage and Grid Modernization**

To support the integration of RES, Greece is investing in energy storage solutions: 5.6 GW in battery energy storage systems (BESS) and 2.5 GW in pumped hydro storage by 2030. The

⁶¹ <https://balkangreenenergynews.com/greece-passes-renewables-law-targeting-15-gw-in-new-capacity-by-2030>

⁶² <https://cms.law/en/int/expert-guides/cms-expert-guide-to-renewable-energy/greece>

country has to invest in smart grid technologies and demand-side management to balance supply and demand effectively.

Additionally, Greece has to enhance its electricity grid to accommodate increased RES input and improve interconnections with neighbouring countries, thus positioning itself as a regional energy hub.

- **Market Design and Structure**

A continuous trading framework can be adopted that allows real-time matching of flexibility supply and demand. This approach enhances market liquidity and responsiveness, which is crucial during the initial stages of LFM development. It has to be ensured that market operations consider the physical limitations of the distribution network. Implementing AC network sensitivities can help in assessing the impact of flexibility transactions on grid stability⁶³.

- **Technological Infrastructure**

Finalise deployment of smart meters, and robust communication networks to provide real-time data, essential for the accurate dispatch and settlement of FS. Energy storage solutions can be incorporated, such as Li-ion batteries and pumped hydro storage, to manage variability in renewable energy production and enhance system reliability⁶⁴.

- **Stakeholder Engagement and Education**

Capacity Building training programs have to be offered for grid operators, energy producers, and consumers to understand and effectively participate in LFMs. The active involvement of consumers has to be encouraged by promoting DR programs and incentives for flexibility provision. There is a need to educate and involve local communities in RES projects to ensure public support and address potential concerns.

- **Pilot and Demonstration Projects**

Pilots about LFMs can be initiated in some regions to test market designs, assess performance, and identify potential challenges. Based on pilot outcomes, scale up successful models to a national level, ensuring that lessons learned enrich implementation strategies.

In conclusion⁶⁵ Greek wholesale markets are currently open to a large number of participants including RES producers, aggregators of RES, demand response aggregators, self-supplying consumers and consumers representing dispatchable loads. Greece is among the European

⁶³ <https://arxiv.org/abs/2207.05363>

⁶⁴ <https://arxiv.org/abs/2209.10787>

⁶⁵ [the_smarten_map_2024_DIGITAL-updated.pdf](#)

countries that have established a framework enabling independent aggregators to participate in wholesale markets, but energy storage is still unable to access the wholesale market due to the lack of a regulatory framework. Reforms are underway, and HEnEX, the Greek wholesale market operator, is currently working on a framework to enable storage participation in electricity markets expected to be finalized in 2025. HEnEX also offers both Day Ahead and Intra Day products based on one-hour granularity. Trades on the continuous Intra Day market can occur up to 60 minutes before delivery. The large granularity and long lead time can be considered constraints for DERs participation. The introduction of dynamic tariffs has to be available for Greek households. Starting in January 2025, some electricity suppliers are required to offer these contracts. The limited deployment of smart meters is a challenge for customers interested in subscribing to these offers.

By adhering to the guidelines and implementing the outlined reforms, Greece can successfully develop LFM that support the integration of RES, enhance grid resilience, and contribute to the country's 2030 energy and climate objectives.

4.3. Ireland

Ireland depends on imported energy, primarily gas and oil, to satisfy its energy requirements. The government's objective is to facilitate Ireland's transition, within EU and globally, to an economy that is low in carbon, resilient to climate change, and environmentally sustainable.

By 2030, the government aims to meet the following targets:

- Up to 80% renewable electricity;
- 30% reduction in CO₂ emissions;
- 32.5% improvement in energy efficiency.

To reach these objectives there is a need to create a balance between developing low carbon and RES, ensuring a safe, secure and reliable supply of electricity, and maintaining a competitive and well-regulated energy market.

This transition has to be achieved through increased energy efficiency and RES use. The government has implemented measures and support systems to assist individuals, communities, businesses, and the public sector in reaching this goal in order to make energy more affordable and to decrease energy poverty.

Ireland has made significant strides in integrating renewable energy into its power grid, with renewables accounting for 40.7% of the electricity supply in 2023, up from 38.6% in 2022. Wind energy is contributing 33.7% to the electricity mix in 2023. Solar PV systems, though still emerging, supplied 1.9% of the nation's electricity in the same year⁶⁶.

The Irish government has set ambitious targets to further enhance renewable energy adoption. The Climate Action Plan 2024 aims for 80% of electricity to come from RES by 2030, including at least 5 GW from offshore wind, 9 GW from onshore wind, and 8 GW from solar capacity⁶⁷. This initiative aligns with Ireland's commitment to achieving net-zero carbon emissions by 2050⁶⁸.

Despite these advancements, challenges persist. In 2023, 82.6% of Ireland's energy supply was still derived from fossil fuels, indicating a significant dependency that needs addressing⁶⁹.

⁶⁶ <https://www.seai.ie/data-and-insights/seai-statistics/key-publications/renewable-energy-in-ireland>

⁶⁷ <https://www.idaireland.com/latest-news/insights/renewable-energy-opportunity-for-ireland>

⁶⁸ <https://www.iea.org/countries/ireland>

⁶⁹ <https://www.seai.ie/data-and-insights/seai-statistics/key-publications/renewable-energy-in-ireland>

Additionally, the rapid expansion of data centres, which consumed 21% of the nation's electricity in 2023, has raised concerns about energy demand and its impact on climate targets⁷⁰.

To meet its renewable energy goals, Ireland must accelerate infrastructure development, streamline planning processes, and attract investments in renewable projects. Efforts are underway to enhance grid capacity and integrate more renewable sources, positioning Ireland as a leader in sustainable energy within Europe.

4.3.1. State-of-the-art of LFM and FS, Transposition of EU Regulation

The targets for renewable energy set out in the first Renewable Energy Directive (RED) in Ireland were met by 2020, while RED II set new targets and criteria to be met by Ireland in 2030 and the interim. RED III, which came into force in November 2023, sets a binding renewable energy target for the EU of at least 42.5% by 2030. Ireland's objective is to contribute to this target by achieving a 43% share of renewable energy in total energy consumption by 2030.

Ireland's National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP) for 2021-2030⁷¹ consolidates policies, actions, and initiatives concerning energy and climate outlined in different government strategies, such as the Climate Action Plan⁷², the National Development Plan⁷³, and Project Ireland 2040⁷⁴, into one comprehensive document that demonstrates the country's current approaches to achieving its primary European goals.

In 2018, the Irish Government approved Renewable Electricity Support Scheme (RESS)⁷⁵ with the ambition to support energy communities, which emerged as a key function of the recast RED within the EU Clean Energy Package. The RESS terms and conditions include the Renewable Energy Communities definition. It was the first policy to directly support community-owned generation projects. The Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland (SEAI) has been assigned to be the implementation body providing a range of supports including advice, guidance, financial help and mentoring to RECs, as well as support to maximise the local benefit from renewable energy projects through realising a stake in a commercial project, or maximising the community benefit.

⁷⁰ [Ireland embraced data centers that the AI boom needs. Now they're consuming too much of its energy | AP News](#)

⁷¹ [gov.ie - National Energy and Climate Plan \(NECP\) 2021-2030](#)

⁷² <https://www.gov.ie/en/publication/67104-climate-action-plan/>

⁷³ <https://www.gov.ie/en/publication/774e2-national-development-plan-2021-2030/>

⁷⁴ <https://www.gov.ie/en/campaigns/09022006-project-ireland-2040/>

⁷⁵ [gov.ie - The White Paper: Ireland's Transition to a Low Carbon Energy Future 2015-2030](#)

Ireland's national objective is to deepen the integration of Ireland's wholesale electricity market, and its regulation, building on ongoing plans, programmes, and actions in this regard.

In July 2022, Ireland notified the European Commission of the full legal transposition of the Internal Market Electricity Directive 2019/944 into Irish law. These measures have strengthened consumer protection measures and the flexibility and transparency of the retail market.

In 2023 the European Commission started reforming the Electricity Market Design (EMD) with the aim of better protecting consumers from price volatility, supporting their access to secure energy from clean sources, and making the market more resilient. Transposition of EMD and implementation of the Regulation on wholesale energy market integrity and transparency (REMIT)⁷⁶ in Ireland commenced in early 2024.

4.3.2. Smart Local Flexibility Services - Compliance and Safety

Ireland is highly dependent on imported gas that makes up almost half of the electricity generation and will be required for many years to supply flexibility as renewable generation grows. To build resilience and independence in the future, Ireland focuses on developing renewables and associated infrastructure for energy systems ranging from storage to alternative supply. Ireland's future energy will be secure by developing an electricity-led system, maximising renewable energy potential, flexibility and being integrated into Europe's energy systems.

The impact of the wide range of policies and measures aimed at increasing energy efficiency can contribute considerably to ensuring security of the energy network. These policies, together with the measures on improving the flexibility of the system, will strengthen Ireland's capacity to deal with the consequences of the planned closure of coal and peat plants.

Further plans include growth of renewable generation, demand-side flexibility, new gas-fired generation as back-up, ensuring interconnection and storage facilities to secure electricity supplies.

The increase of the renewable generation will be achieved by support that will be given to at least 500 MW of local community based renewable projects and increased levels of new micro-generation and small-scale generation.

⁷⁶ Regulation - 1227/2011 - EN - REMIT - EUR-Lex

The development of the FS will contribute to the consumers' participation in the energy system and will ensure the benefit from self-generation and new technologies, including smart meters available for every home by the end of 2025.

Though there are no financial incentives for DSF to participate in the Irish wholesale markets, beyond the obligations placed on them by the Irish Capacity Market, the benefits of the ToU tariffs' benefits are notable. Energy consumers can subscribe to ToU tariffs. The regulated SmartPay Time of Use Tariff (SST) divides the day into three distinct time-bands: Peak (5 pm to 7 pm), Day (8 am to 5 pm and 7 pm to 11 pm), and Night (11 pm to 8 am). These time-bands allow consumers to adjust their energy consumption patterns in response to different pricing levels throughout the day, potentially leading to cost savings and more efficient energy use.

Access to wholesale prices through a dynamic electricity contract is not possible due to the lack of current offers by electricity suppliers. While hourly dynamic contracts based on spot prices are allowed in Ireland, no supplier made this offer available to households and businesses. In 2023, 69% of Irish households had a smart meter installed; the rollout of smart meters will create the technical ability to subscribe to a dynamic contract when available offers exist.

Ireland put in place an ambitious and comprehensive set of policies and targets to reach net zero by 2050 and 80% of renewable electricity generation by 2030, but their implementation needs to accelerate. Natural gas will remain an important part of the energy mix at least until the mid-2030s, especially to meet peak electricity demand, but offshore renewable energy will become the cornerstone of Ireland's energy transition beyond 2030.

Given Ireland's current exclusive reliance on energy imports from the United Kingdom, energy security is a major concern to the government while transitioning to a renewables-based energy system and advancing the electrification of the heating and transport sectors to meet the ambitious climate targets to 2030 and beyond⁷⁷.

4.3.3. Business Models and Financing Mechanisms to Boost Stakeholder Motivation

A new market design started functioning in 2018 including the establishment of Day-Ahead, Intra-Day and Balancing Markets, with an ex-ante clearing price, and a new obligation on participants to take responsibility for imbalances. This market design has the objectives of facilitating greater market integration through the application of integrated energy market rules and enhancing competitive outcomes to benefit consumers. It also has the objective of ensuring

⁷⁷ <https://www.iea.org/countries/ireland>

compliance with the network codes and guidelines developed under EC Regulations within the Third Energy Package and with the principles of wholesale market design laid out in the recast electricity market regulation.

LFMs in Ireland are evolving to integrate DERs such as renewable generation, energy storage, and DR into the electricity grid to enhance grid stability, defer infrastructure investments, and support the nation's decarbonisation goals.

Though Ireland is in the early stages of developing local flexibility markets, various business models are being considered to effectively integrate DER, enhance grid stability, and support the country's decarbonisation objectives. They are:

- *Aggregator Model*: Aggregators play a pivotal role by consolidating multiple DERs to offer significant FS to system operators managing the coordination of various small-scale resources, and enabling effective participation in flexibility markets. This model enhances the integration of RES and provides system operators with reliable flexibility options⁷⁸.
- *Peer-to-Peer (P2P) Trading*: Allows prosumers to trade surplus energy directly with other consumers within a local community. P2P trading fosters local energy autonomy, optimizes the use of locally generated renewable energy, and can lead to cost savings for participants. In Ireland, several P2P trading platforms cater to various needs, such as small business loans, short-term consumer debt, and more⁷⁹. “EnerPort” is an Irish government- and industry-funded collaborative project where blockchain technology is being used to develop a peer-to-peer (P2P) energy trade model to support energy trade between microgrids⁸⁰.
- *Community Self-Consumption*: In this approach, a community collectively manages and consumes the energy produced by shared renewable resources, such as community-owned solar panels or wind turbines. This model promotes local renewable energy utilization and can provide economic benefits to community members⁸¹.
- *Transactive Energy Models*⁸²: Involve automated, price-based interactions between energy producers and consumers, enabling real-time balancing of supply and demand. Transactive energy frameworks facilitate efficient energy distribution and can enhance grid resilience by dynamically responding to changing conditions.

⁷⁸ esb-networks-national-network-local-connections-programme-phased-flexibility-market-development-plan.pdf

⁷⁹ Peer-to-Peer (P2P) Trading in Ireland - Top 2 Platforms 2024

⁸⁰ EnerPort: Irish Blockchain project for peer-to-peer energy trading | Energy Informatics | Full Text

⁸¹ Collective self-consumption for energy communities in Ireland: a blockchain based application | IET Conference Publication | IEEE Xplore

⁸² Emerging business models in local energy markets: A systematic review of peer-to-peer, community self-consumption, and transactive energy models

Ireland does not yet have an established market for local FS on its electricity distribution system. The "Phased Flexibility Market Development Plan" by ESB Networks outlines initial proposals for developing such markets, aiming to introduce flexibility products and services to enhance the efficiency and reliability of the distribution system.

Companies like GridBeyond⁸³ are actively contributing to this space by providing energy optimization services and are specialized in the optimization and operation of DERs, offering services such as virtual power plants and energy demand management, which are integral to the development of LFM.

The Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland (SEAI) provides support to businesses and homeowners who want to invest in renewable energy in the form of grants, training, and advice on renewable energy technologies⁸⁴.

The Renewable Energy Support Scheme (RESS)⁸⁵ is a governmental initiative that offers financial incentives for renewable energy initiatives in Ireland. This program is designed to promote the advancement of renewable electricity projects in the country, which encompasses wind, solar, and biomass energy sources.

The Small-Scale Renewable Electricity Support Scheme (SRESS)⁸⁶ is an essential component for achieving the objectives of the Irish solar strategy and is a part of the Government's extensive support framework for Renewable Self-Consumers. This scheme provides assistance for renewable electricity installations to various groups, including communities, small and medium enterprises (SMEs), and farmers.

4.3.4. Awareness & Actions to Ensure High Customer Participation in the LFMs

Ireland is actively promoting customer participation in LFMs to enhance grid efficiency and support the integration of RES. Key initiatives include:

- *National Network, Local Connections Programme (NN, LCP)*⁸⁷: SB Networks has launched this programme to develop FS that allow customers to participate in market-based solutions. The program is rolling out operational technologies to broaden customer participation, including residential demand-side response at scale. This phased approach involves piloting market solutions, refining them based on learnings, and scaling up to include a wider range of participants and technologies.

⁸³ Artificial intelligence for the energy transition

⁸⁴ SEAI Grants: Home Improvement, Business, EV & More | SEAI

⁸⁵ gov.ie - Renewable Electricity Support Scheme (RESS)

⁸⁶ Small-Scale Renewable Electricity Support Scheme (SRESS)

⁸⁷ National Network, Local Connections Programme

- *Flexibility Multi-Year Plan 2024–2028*⁸⁸: The Commission for Regulation of Utilities (CRU) has outlined a comprehensive plan to increase demand flexibility. The plan includes: i) Launching products to incentivize location-specific medium-duration flexibility through multiyear contracts; ii) Introducing standard flexibility readiness technology requirements for new electric transport installations; iii) Creating routes to market for energy communities to participate in LFMs; iv) Implementing flexible connections for storage and demand customers. These measures aim to build customer participation and awareness through extensive research, education, and recruitment initiatives.
- *National Energy Demand Strategy*⁸⁹: The CRU (Commission for Regulation of Utilities) has developed a strategy to ensure that electricity and gas demand meet Ireland's carbon emission targets. The strategy emphasizes delivering demand flexibility and response initiatives, with a goal of achieving 15–20% flexibility by 2025 and 20–30% by 2030. This involves coordinated efforts across various sectors, including domestic, commercial, and large energy users, to facilitate active participation in the energy market.
- *Collaboration with Flexibility Platforms*: Ireland is engaging with platforms like Piclo Flex⁹⁰ to facilitate the end-to-end process from flexibility procurement to operation and settlement. Such collaborations aim to simplify access to flexibility markets for service providers, thereby encouraging broader participation.

Through these initiatives, Ireland is fostering an environment that encourages high customer participation in LFMs, contributing to a more resilient and sustainable energy system.

The energy transition will not succeed without the backing of the Irish consumers by their participation in the energy market to make personal investments, by change in behaviour, and support of construction projects in their localities. Consumers have to trust that these actions will not only benefit the environment, but also will create local jobs and support local businesses. Understanding consumers' attitudes and motivations is crucial to developing the public support required to accelerate the energy transition.

It is essential to have clear communication and meaningful actions to build trust among Irish citizens. Achieving net zero in Ireland requires a collaborative effort from people, businesses, communities, and the government. People in Ireland need to increase awareness and actions like reducing personal energy consumption by adopting energy efficient practices at home,

⁸⁸ https://www.esbnetworks.ie/docs/default-source/publications/flexibility-myp-2024-28_accessible.pdf?sfvrsn=c380b38e_7

⁸⁹ The National Energy Demand Strategy is now complete and includes an implementation plan with a list of recommendations and time-bound actions. | CRU.ie

⁹⁰ Piclo Flex

choosing sustainable transportation options and supporting eco-friendly and sustainable products and companies. SMEs also have to implement sustainable and environmentally friendly practices within their operations and optimise supply chains for sustainability. Communities could engage in local sustainability initiatives and projects, raise awareness about climate change and sustainable living within the community and advocate for sustainable urban planning and development. By addressing these considerations and taking proactive steps, each stakeholder group can contribute to Ireland's achievement of energy transition.

4.3.5. Strategic Planning Documents

The Ireland's National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP) for 2021-2030 brings together the policies, targets, tools and associated material relating to the climate and energy obligations under the EU Regulations and Directives from across government bodies and departments into one document outlining the ambition of the country to move towards the creation of a carbon-neutral society.

The NECP highlights shortcomings and aspects where Ireland can enhance its efforts, which ought to be incorporated into revised policies and actions in future Climate Action Plans.

At the end of 2023 Ireland's total installed solar-PV capacity was 0.72 GW and by the end of 2030 Ireland has set itself a target of 8 GW of installed solar-PV capacity (See Figure 2). Achieving this target will require adding an average of 1.04 GW installed capacity every year for the next few years.

Figure 2: Ireland's installed solar-PV capacity to the end of 2023 in GW and its Climate Action Plan target for 2030.

The deployment rates of renewable energy and grid infrastructure requires urgent action across all actors to align with the national targets illustrated in Table 4.

Table 4: Key targets in electricity from renewables in Ireland

National Target	2025	2030
Renewable Electricity Share	50%	80%
Onshore wind	6 GW	9GW
Solar	Up to 5GW	8GW
Offshore wind	-	At least 5 GW
New Flexible Gas Plant	-	At least 2 GW
Demand Side Flexibility	15-20%	20-30%

Source: Climate Action Plan 2024

Transformational policies, actions and measures, and societal change are required to increase the deployment of renewable energy generation, strengthen the electricity grid, and meet the demand and flexibility needs required for the challenges in achieving the key goals as follows:

- Boosting renewable energy production to meet 80% of demand by 2030 by rapidly expanding onshore wind and solar power, developing offshore renewable sources, and enhancing grid infrastructure.
- Encouraging micro and small-scale generation along with community initiatives by means of actions like providing grants and allowing small-scale producers to engage in energy markets.
- Enhancing the adaptability of the electricity system by boosting system services and expanding storage capacity.
- Creating instruments and strategies that enhance demand-side FS by utilizing smart metering, such as market incentives and intelligent tariffs, eliminating regulatory obstacles, and prioritizing flexibility-compatible standards for smart technology.
- Provision of a minimum of 2 GW of new flexible gas-powered generation.

In 2023 the Irish Government published a strategy⁹¹ to promote the sustainable development of Ireland’s geothermal resources to decarbonise the heating and cooling of buildings and for industrial uses and power generation. The optimal deployment of geothermal energy will increase the flexibility of the national energy system through the moderation of demand for electricity, and through geological energy storage.

⁹¹ gov.ie - Policy Statement on Geothermal Energy for a Circular Economy

4.3.6. Policy Guidelines for Facilitating Deployment of LFM and Exploitation of Flexibility

Ireland is currently revising its rules on energy payments, with the new measures decided by the end of 2024. While this revision aims to remove the primary barrier to the participation of DSF in the wholesale market, further review of the technical and administrative requirements are necessary. It is required to ensure a level playing field between DERs and other assets, promoting fair and equal access to the market for all participants

Implementing LFM in Ireland by 2030 is pivotal for enhancing grid resilience, integrating RES, and achieving decarbonisation goals. The following guidelines and recommendations can facilitate this implementation:

- **Comprehensive Regulatory Framework aligned with National Energy Strategies**

Establish clear policies that define the roles and responsibilities of participants in LFM, including consumers, producers, and aggregators.

Ensure that LFM initiatives are consistent with Ireland's National Energy Demand Strategy and the Climate Action Plan, contributing to overarching goals of sustainability and energy security. Follow and monitor the objectives outlined in the NECP.

- **Promotion of FS and Market Design and Mechanisms:**

Create market structures that incentivize FS, ensuring fair compensation for participants who adjust their demand or supply in response to grid needs. Collaborate with grid operators to align LFM development with grid infrastructure plans, facilitating the seamless integration of flexible resources.

Develop mechanisms for procuring FS from various providers, including DR and distributed generation, to enhance grid reliability and efficiency. Promote access to wholesale prices through dynamic electricity contracts for citizens and businesses. Offer long-term contracts to flexibility service providers to encourage investment and provide financial stability.

- **Technological Innovation**

Invest in advanced grid technologies, such as smart meters and real-time monitoring systems, to facilitate efficient communication and operation within LFM. Complete the rollout of smart meters in the country. Promote the development and integration of energy storage systems to manage variability in renewable energy production and enhance grid stability.

- **Stakeholder Engagement**

Empower local communities to participate in LFMs by providing education and incentives, enabling them to contribute to and benefit from the energy transition.

Establish collaboration platforms - forums for dialogue among regulators, grid operators, technology providers, and consumers to align objectives and address challenges collaboratively.

- **Pilot Projects and Scalability Plans**

Launch pilot LFMs in selected regions to test market designs, technologies, and regulatory approaches, using the insights gained to refine and scale up successful models.

Develop plans to expand successful pilot projects nationally, ensuring that lessons learned inform broader implementation efforts.

By following these guidelines, Ireland can effectively contribute to the implementation of LFMs by 2030, fostering a resilient, efficient, and sustainable energy system.

4.3.7. Findings as a Result of the Pilot Project Implementation in Ireland

The Irish pilot at Áras de Brún highlights key regulatory and structural issues that affect the potential for local flexibility markets (LFMs) in Ireland. While the pilot focuses on improving heating efficiency through IoT-enabled controls to the room level and providing near real-time user engagement, it reflects challenges that may limit future participation in flexibility markets for similar public buildings.

Public-sector buildings are often managed by central estate teams rather than individual occupants. This means that energy savings are treated as operational cost reductions rather than incentives for performance improvement. Without clear financial benefits or flexibility obligations, there is little motivation for facility managers to engage in demand-side response. Existing regulatory frameworks do not mandate public-sector entities to participate in LFMs or provide demand-side flexibility (CRU, 2025a)⁹².

Procurement rules in the public sector are complex and slow, making it difficult for facility managers to engage with flexibility providers or aggregators. Current rules require formal tendering for most service contracts, which increases costs and delays decisions. Introducing

⁹² Commission for Regulation of Utilities (CRU). (2025a). "Large Energy Users connection policy Proposed Decision"- (CRU/202504, 18 February 2025). Dublin: CRU.

simpler contracting options, such as pre-approved agreements with aggregators, could help public buildings engage more easily with flexibility markets.

Electricity tariffs for large users in Ireland currently provide little incentive to shift load or reduce peak demand. Most large consumers pay fixed or averaged rates, which do not reflect the real-time value of demand reduction. Introducing dynamic pricing or critical peak pricing for large consumers could enhance the financial viability of participating in LFM. Additionally, compensation mechanisms for demand-side response, such as direct payments or reduced network charges, could make flexibility more attractive to public-sector actors (CRU, 2025b)⁹³.

Aggregating flexibility from multiple public buildings could also improve participation. Grouping the university with nearby public buildings, such as hospitals and schools, could create a larger and more reliable flexibility resource (CRU, 2025c). Regulatory support for aggregation and peer-to-peer flexibility trading would make it easier for public buildings to participate.

Technology also plays a role. The use of IoT-based controls and real-time monitoring systems in the pilot shows that digital infrastructure can support more responsive energy management. Mandating or incentivising the deployment of smart controls and sub-metering in large public buildings could enhance responsiveness and data visibility, improving the ability to participate in LFM (CRU, 2025c)⁹⁴.

In summary, the Irish pilot shows that public-sector buildings could become valuable contributors to flexibility markets with the right regulatory changes. Improving procurement rules, adjusting tariffs (CRU, 2025b), supporting aggregation, and investing in smart controls would help unlock this potential.

⁹³ Commission for Regulation of Utilities (CRU). (2025a). "Large Energy Users connection policy – Proposed Decision" - (CRU/202504, 18 February 2025). Dublin: CRU.

⁹⁴ Commission for Regulation of Utilities (CRU). (2025c). "Electricity Connection Policy – Generation & System Services: Charging and Rebating Methodology" (Consultation Paper) (CRU/202538, 14 March 2025). Dublin: CRU.

4.4. Portugal

Portugal's energy transition is driven by strong government policies, favourable natural conditions, and a commitment to EU climate goals. The country has already made significant strides in increasing the share of renewables in its energy mix and it has set ambitious targets for the coming decade.

Portugal was among the first countries in the world to set a target for carbon neutrality by 2050, with its ambitious National Energy and Climate Plan 2030 setting out its trajectory to achieve 80% of its electricity from renewables by 2030.

In 2024 renewable production hit a record 36.7 TWh, the highest in the national grid's history, reflecting an ongoing shift from fossil fuels. The total electricity consumption was 51.4 TWh, marking a 1.3% increase from 2023. Portugal reached a significant achievement with renewable energy accounting for 71% of the electricity consumption thanks to robust growth in renewable installations and favourable weather conditions. The breakdown includes about 28% from hydroelectric power, 27% from wind power, and around 10% from solar energy; biomass contributed 6% to the national electricity mix for 2024. Non-renewable energy, primarily from natural gas, dropped to 5.1 TWh, and accounted for just 10% of total consumption. Natural gas consumption in Portugal fell 17% in 2024, totalling 40.5 TWh—the lowest since 2003⁹⁵.

Portugal's energy transition is progressing swiftly, positioning the country as a leader in renewable energy. The next challenge is to sustain the growth of renewables while maintaining grid stability, ensuring a sustainable energy future.

4.4.1. State-of-the-art of LFM and FS, Transposition of EU Regulation

The EU's regulatory framework, particularly the Clean Energy for All Europeans package, the Electricity Regulation (EU 944/2019), and the Governance Regulation (EU 2018/1999), has been central to shaping the evolution of flexibility markets across Europe, including Portugal. The gradual integration of RES in the electricity production has led to structural changes in the electricity market. In particular through Decree-Law 215-A⁹⁶ and 215-B⁹⁷ of October 8, 2012 which have enabled RES electricity producers to directly sell their electricity on the open market. Legislative Decree 76/2019 supplemented the previous regulations by requiring future producers to obtain a network capacity reserve title prior to any authorization to produce.

⁹⁵ <https://www.portal-energia.com/energias-renovaveis-abastecem-portugal/>

⁹⁶ <https://dre.pt/dre/detalhe/decreto-lei/215-a-2012-588860>

⁹⁷ <https://dre.pt/dre/detalhe/decreto-lei/215-b-2012-588861>

The transposition of the European directives IEMD and RED II into Portuguese legislation was done in 2022 through the Decree-Law 15/2022⁹⁸ January 14, and has made it possible to better define market players and their actions in order to develop the electricity market as close as possible to the European model and also in order to optimize FS.

Here are some of the main national laws in the sector:

- *Parliamentary Resolution 23/2006* approves the Agreement between the Portuguese Republic and the Kingdom of Spain for the constitution of an Iberian Electricity Market (MIBEL)⁹⁹
- *Decree-Law 141/2010* defined the National Energy Strategy until 2020 by setting RES targets and partially transposed EU Directive 2009/28/EC
- *Decree-Law 74/2013* promotes effective competition in the wholesale market, protects the interests of consumers
- *National Plan for Energy and Climate 2021-2030 (PNEC)* sets new objectives for renewable energies and electricity production decarbonisation
- *Decree-Law 15/2022* transposes the EU Directives 2018/2001 (on energy production from RES) and the EU Directive 2019/944 (common rules for the internal electricity market)

Regarding specific provisions for renewable energy, there is a separate legal framework in Portugal. The legal framework for renewable energy includes the Renewable Energy Auctions Regulations, which govern the bidding process for the allocation of capacity to renewable energy projects.

Upcoming changes in laws and regulations relevant to renewable energy in Portugal may include changes to the licensing procedures to simplify the current regime.

Market Structure and integration

The electricity sector was nationalized after the 1974 revolution and began to be liberalized at the end of the 20th century. Even if the electricity law in 1995 divided the market in several segments, they were still non-competitive. The market has gradually opened up, primarily to industries with high electricity consumption. It was in 2006 that the electricity market started to be open to new stakeholders according to the European Directive 96/92/EC and that residential consumers were able to choose their supplier. New market players are able since then to ensure a role in production, distribution or energy supply. Scheduled for 2025, the

⁹⁸ <https://dre.pt/dre/detalhe/decreto-lei/15-2022-177634016>

⁹⁹ [Iberian Electricity Market](#)

abolition of the regulation of energy supply tariffs for end customers will conclude the market's liberalization.¹⁰⁰

Missions relating to the transmission and distribution systems are now carried out by private companies under a concession system. The Portuguese TSO is Redes Energéticas Nacionais (REN) and the main DSO is the historical operator of the electricity network E-REDES but several concessions also exist for low voltage lines at a municipal level. Those concessionaires are in charge of managing the National Electricity System (SEN) and ensuring its security under the supervision of the Energy Services Regulatory Authority (ERSE).

The Portuguese part of the Iberian electricity market is the OMIP¹⁰¹ and manages the ancillary markets by offering standardized agreements. Services system markets have been created in accordance with European regulation. They allow the TSO to have direct access to FS but also to enter into bilateral contracts with certain market players for specific flexibility needs. Access to the markets is guaranteed to all market players with a market agent qualification.¹⁰²

Any entity willing to access the Portuguese wholesale market needs to register as a “market agent” with the TSO, REN. This rule applies to all electricity markets and every market actor can register, including suppliers, independent aggregators, industrial consumers and energy communities.

In 2023, Portugal undertook reforms to improve self-consumption access to the wholesale market through an independent aggregator, but the current framework does not cover the technical requirements ensuring the participation of DR in wholesale markets (e.g. baselining, settlement, compensation of suppliers). A major element stands on the obligation of all units integrated in an aggregator portfolio to belong to the same BRP. Moreover, technical requirements governing the aggregation of low voltage customers are acting as a barrier. The technical requirements (e.g. prequalification, requalification, baseline methodology and settlement) need to be updated to create a level of playing field between DR and other technologies. By early 2025, the Portuguese regulator announced the launch of pilot projects aiming at identifying barriers faced by aggregation of small residential/commercial consumers and other DER. A promotional campaign should support regulatory updates to raise awareness among low-voltage consumers about the economic advantages to engage in DR programmes.¹⁰³

¹⁰⁰ <https://www.erse.pt/eletricidade/o-setor/>

¹⁰¹ <https://www.omip.pt/en/about-us-omip>

¹⁰² <https://thelawreviews.co.uk/title/the-energy-regulation-and-markets-review/portugal>

¹⁰³ <https://smarten.eu/>

The integration of LFM with the broader European energy market remains a challenge. There is also a need for harmonization of rules and technical standards at both national and European levels to ensure the smooth functioning of cross-border flexibility markets.

Technological infrastructure and advancements

The implementation of advanced digital infrastructure, including smart meters, sensors, and communication networks, is still in progress. These technologies are essential for the accurate measurement, communication, and transaction of local FS.

The process of smart metering installation started in 2016 by Portuguese DSO E-REDES, was finalized in 2024 with 6.6 million installed smart meters, at all points of connection to the grid, with an investment of EUR 330 million.¹⁰⁴

In addition to all its functionalities, the smart grid now supports 323 energy communities, around 6,500 electric vehicle charging points, 234k individual self-consumption customers and 1,350 collective self-consumption customers, with 6.4 million real bill readings without estimates.

4.4.2. Smart Local Flexibility Services - Compliance and Safety

Portugal has made significant progress in setting up local flexibility mechanisms, which are still evolving. Key features of these developments include:

- *Local FS via the TSO-DSO Interaction:* The collaboration between the TSO and DSOs is crucial for enabling local FS. The DSO is tasked with managing local grid congestion, and the TSO ensures system reliability at the national level. In Portugal, this coordination is facilitated by the energy market operator, *REN* (Redes Energéticas Nacionais).
- *Dynamic and Real-Time Market Design:* Portuguese regulations are moving towards a more dynamic market design, where FS are procured through both day-ahead and real-time markets. This allows for the real-time balancing of supply and demand and enhances the integration of intermittent RES.
- *Integration of Distributed Energy Resources:* There has been a growing focus on integrating small-scale producers, such as households with solar panels or battery storage systems, into the electricity grid. Through the transposition of EU rules, Portugal has encouraged the participation of these actors in flexibility markets.

¹⁰⁴ <https://www.e-redes.pt/en/news/2024/12/11/smart-meters-pillar-energy-transition>

Ensuring compliance with EU and national regulations, as well as safeguarding safety, is critical to the successful operation of local FS. Portugal is building a flexible and secure energy system through careful regulatory oversight, the adoption of technical standards, robust cybersecurity practices, and consumer protection.

As these services evolve, maintaining a balance between innovation, compliance, and safety will be essential to achieving the country's energy transition goals.

Compliance

Regarding the accordance of the Portuguese national legislation with the EU directives, it promotes the integration of FS, including:

- Access to LFM for all energy resources, ensuring participation by aggregators, prosumers, and storage systems.
- Non-discriminatory market design that facilitates the participation of smaller, decentralized assets (e.g., residential solar panels or electric vehicle chargers).
- Smart grid integration that ensures FS can be used to balance local supply and demand in real-time, and provide ancillary services such as frequency regulation and voltage control.

Portugal has incorporated these EU regulations into national law, primarily through:

- The Portuguese Electricity Sector Law (Lei nº 58/2019), which reflects the EU's electricity market rules and enables FS within Portugal's energy market.
- ERSE (Energy Services Regulatory Authority), the Portuguese regulatory body, oversees the implementation of LFM and ensures they comply with both national and EU standards. It developed specific grid codes and market rules for integrating local FS in the energy system.
- TSO and DSO Coordination: The collaboration between Portugal's Transmission System Operator (REN) and the DSOs is essential for facilitating FS.

Compliance also involves ensuring market transparency:

- Participants in LFM must have access to relevant information, such as grid conditions and pricing, to make informed decisions.
- Flexibility providers, whether small-scale producers or residential consumers, must comply with market access rules to ensure fair competition. This includes transparency in transaction reporting and ensuring all market participants are treated equitably.

Safety

Ensuring the safety of these systems is essential to protect the grid, consumers, and the broader energy infrastructure. It includes electrical safety, grid protection, cybersecurity, consumer protection, real-time monitoring, etc.

Electrical Safety

- Using technologies such as smart inverters and advanced sensors are essential for monitoring and controlling the overloading of the system, the voltage instability and so on, in real-time.
- Portugal's regulatory framework requires that energy devices meet electrical safety standards, such as those outlined in the IEC 60364 and IEC 61508 standards, to ensure safe operation across all connected assets.

Grid Protection

Portugal has adopted *smart grid* technologies to provide real-time monitoring and enable automatic responses to electrical disturbances. These technologies contribute to preventing major disruptions while enabling flexible energy management at the local level.

Cybersecurity

- In Portugal, compliance with the NIS2 Directive (EU Directive on Network and Information Systems Security) is required to ensure robust cybersecurity for critical infrastructure. This includes adopting standards such as ISO/IEC 27001 for information security management systems and IEC 62443 for industrial control systems.
- Grid operators, technology providers, and market participants must adhere to stringent encryption, authentication, and access control measures to safeguard the integrity and security of the data exchanged between devices and market platforms.

Consumer Protection

- The Portuguese Consumer Protection Law ensures that consumers participating in flexibility markets are informed of risks and benefits. This includes ensuring that smart appliances and home systems meet electrical safety standards. Consumers also have access to clear information about terms of participation in flexibility programs, as well as opt-out mechanisms if they feel their safety or privacy is compromised.

Real-Time Monitoring

A real-time monitoring of grid conditions, including voltage, frequency, and power flow, which ensures that the FS can be dispatched without compromising grid stability. Smart meters and advanced sensors integrated into the grid provide granular data to grid operators and market participants, enabling more precise and safe management of local FS.

Portuguese law allows electricity suppliers to offer dynamic electricity contracts to their customers, but there are no commercial offers based on wholesale prices for residential and commercial customers available on the market. Instead, available tariff options include three regulated choices: a flat tariff, a bi-hourly tariff with two periods (off-peak and peak hours), and a tri-hourly tariff with three periods (peak, mid-peak, and off-peak hours). In 2023, 86% of households had a smart meter installed enabling the collecting consumption-data every 15 minutes. The introduction of dynamic tariffs will open a lot of possibilities for the consumers, when the full rollout of smart meters will be accomplished.¹⁰⁵

4.4.3. Business Models and Financing Mechanisms to Boost Stakeholder Motivation

Various business models and financing mechanisms can develop and implement smart FS in Portugal which present significant opportunities for enhancing energy efficiency, integrating renewable energy, and providing innovative solutions for grid stability. Including stakeholders, such as consumers, businesses, technology providers, grid operators, and regulators and ensuring their interests is crucial for the successful deployment of LFM and services.

A well-structured business model is essential to attract investment, ensure sustainability, and align the motivations of various stakeholders. Below are some proposals for business models that are suitable for deployment of smart local FS in Portugal:

- *Aggregator-Based Model* where independent aggregators collect flexibility from multiple small and medium-sized energy resources (e.g., solar panels, batteries, electric vehicles, demand-side response) and bundle them to sell as a single unit to grid operators or flexibility markets. Consumers, on the other hand, receive compensation for offering their flexibility, such as reducing energy demand or providing stored energy. Companies like EDP, Iberdrola, could act as aggregators and thus be a good example for the others. Independent aggregators managing generation assets are legally entitled to access Portuguese wholesale markets; ill-defined technical requirements such as baselining, settlement, and supplier compensation act as barriers to market entry.

¹⁰⁵ <https://smarten.eu/>

- *Consumer-Powered Business Model (Prosumers)* based on the high production of solar energy and its storage. Consumers can monetize their excess energy or provide grid-balancing services like demand-side response or energy storage via smart devices. Good examples are programs like “Soluções de Flexibilidade de Energia” (SFE) by REN (Portugal’s TSO) which are designed to integrate consumer flexibility into the grid.
- *Energy-as-a-Service (EaaS) Model* is a subscription-based business model in which customers pay for energy services (e.g., FS, grid balancing, energy management) rather than for the energy itself. It can include bundled services such as DR, energy storage management, and optimization of renewable energy use.
- *Peer-to-Peer (P2P) Energy Trading* Consumers or small producers (e.g., homeowners with solar panels) can sell or trade excess energy with each other directly, using blockchain or other decentralized platforms. This enables local energy markets where consumers can actively participate in balancing supply and demand. Pilot projects or companies like Powerledger or SolarCoin can facilitate peer-to-peer trading of solar energy in local communities in Portugal.

Some of the financial mechanisms that could boost the motivation for participation in the LFM in Portugal are:

- *Government Grants* - Portugal's Programa de Apoio à Modernização da Rede Elétrica (program to support the modernization of the electrical grid) and Fundo de Modernização da Energia (energy modernization fund) support investments in energy infrastructure, including flexibility.
- *Green bonds* - can be issued to finance local flexibility projects that focus on reducing carbon emissions, enhancing renewable energy integration, or improving energy efficiency. Investors in these bonds can benefit from stable returns while supporting sustainable development. Banco Português de Investimento (BPI) and Caixa Geral de Depósitos (CGD) have supported financing for renewable energy and green projects, and could play a role in expanding investment into FS.
- *Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs)* - The European Investment Bank (EIB) and Portuguese public institutions, like Agência para a Energia (ADENE), could support partnerships to finance the development of flexibility markets and services in Portugal.
- *Crowdfunding and Community Financing* - The growing popularity of crowdfunding platforms in Portugal, such as Seedrs or PPL (a Portuguese crowdfunding platform), could be used to finance community-based renewable energy and flexibility projects. The “Solar for All” initiative is a good example for local engagement of stakeholders.

4.4.4. Awareness and Actions to Ensure High Customer Participation in the LFM

The roles of the participants in this market will change and develop along with the services and the newcomers as new types of producers and customers.

The raising of awareness is aiming to ensure high customer participation in the LFM in Portugal and it includes activities such as education of the market participants, collaboration with local authorities and communities and development of platforms and apps.

- **Education through:**

Workshops and Seminars: Organize events to explain the concept of LFM, their benefits, and operational mechanisms.

Targeted Communication Campaigns: Develop informational campaigns through local media, social platforms, and direct communication to explain the importance of customer involvement.

User-Friendly Educational Materials: Provide easy-to-understand guides, infographics, and videos explaining the characteristics of the flexibility market, the role of DSOs and TSO, economic benefits, etc.

- **Collaborations with Local Authorities and Communities**

Engage municipalities and community organizations to act as intermediaries and to lead awareness efforts.

- **Leverage Digital Platforms**

Use apps and portals where customers can learn about local energy consumption, pricing, and opportunities for active participation.

Facilitate access to simulation tools to show potential earnings from providing FS.

Different actions can be undertaken to stimulate the participation in the LFM in Portugal as follows:

- *Financial Incentives* including compensations, subsidies or tax incentives for equipment enabling participation.
- *User-Centric Technology Solutions* such as smart grid technologies and enable real-time participation for customers through digital tools.
- *Simplified Market Access* by ensuring an easy onboarding process for participants, with minimum technical and regulatory barriers.
- *Innovative Demand Response Programs* including dynamic pricing models (time-of-use tariffs, real-time pricing) to incentivize behaviour shifts.
- *Focus on Specific Customer Segments* and their concrete needs and interests.
- *Regulatory and Policy Support* to mandate transparency and fairness in market operations. Reduce complexity in compliance for smaller players.
- *Pilot Programs and Demonstrations* showing the benefits of active participation also including case study models from abroad.
- *Feedback Mechanisms* through different channels for participants to share experiences and suggestions for improvement.

4.4.5. Strategic Planning Documents

Portugal has been actively developing strategic initiatives to establish local FS and markets, aiming to enhance grid resilience and support the integration of RES.

Portugal's National Energy and Climate Plan 2024-2030 (PNECP)

It is the country's main energy and climate policy instrument in the short to medium term whose original draft was delivered in 2019. It purports to outline how the country intends to address decarbonisation, energy efficiency, energy security, renewable energy adoption, the internal energy market, including FS and research, innovation and competitiveness.

The revision of the Plan was prepared in 2024 and the focus has been on setting even more ambitious goals concerning the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, as well as on redefining targets for specific RES and technologies.

The Portuguese government committed in 2016 to ensure its emissions neutrality by the end of 2050, setting out a clear vision for the deep decarbonisation of the national economy, as a contribution to the Paris Agreement and in line with ongoing international efforts. To achieve

this goal, the Carbon Neutrality Roadmap 2050 (RNC2050), which was the long-term low greenhouse gas emission development strategy, pointed out that an emission reduction level of 55 % compared to 2005 should be achieved by 2030.

Taking into account the scenario envisaged for the evolution of the power generation sector in Portugal, renewable energy can be expected to contribute 80 % of electricity production by 2026. 90 % of the electricity produced in the Portuguese electricity generation system is expected to be renewable in 2030, with a focus on wind with around 36 % and solar with around 39 %, which will be the technologies with the highest growth in the next decade (See Figure 3).

Source: Portugal's National Energy and Climate Plan 2030, p.44

Figure 3: Estimated evolution of electricity production by technology in Portugal towards 2030, based on planned policies and measures – WAM Scenario (MWh)

The National Energy and Climate Plan for 2030 of Portugal can play the role of a detailed roadmap towards climate neutrality by 2050, with important targets outlined for 2030 (See Table 5).

Recovery and Resilience Plan

The Portuguese Recovery and Resilience Plan (RRP) is a national program, to be executed until 2026, which aims through reforms and investments to resume sustained economic growth, ensuring the recovery from the pandemic crisis and a resilient future for our country. It is structured in three dimensions, Resilience, Climate Transition and Digital Transition.¹⁰⁶

¹⁰⁶ <https://www.dgeg.gov.pt/en/transversal-areas/international-affairs/energy-policy/national-recovery-and-resilience-plan-rrp>

The energy area is included in the "Climate Transition" dimension, which focuses on advancing sustainability by transforming mobility, decarbonizing industries, enhancing energy efficiency, and promoting the bioeconomy. It prioritizes the shift to clean and renewable energy, fosters a circular economy, and aims to redefine mobility. Through research, innovation, and adoption of efficient energy technologies, it seeks to optimize resource use and strengthen renewable energy-based economic sectors. Allocating 18% of the RRP's overall funding, it encompasses six key components—Sea, Industrial Decarbonisation, Sustainable Bioeconomy, Energy Efficiency in Buildings, Hydrogen and Renewables, and Sustainable Mobility—delivering eight reforms and 17 strategic investments to reduce carbon emissions and expand renewable energy integration.

Table 5: Summary of revised PNEC objectives for 2030 in Portugal

Renewable Energy Sources	
Renewable electricity generation	90 %
National target for the share of energy from renewable sources in gross final energy consumption by 2030	49 %
Share of electricity from renewable sources in gross final consumption of electricity	93 %
Share of heating and cooling from RES in gross final consumption of heating and cooling	47 %
Share of energy from renewable sources in final energy consumption in the transport sector	23 %
Energy Efficiency	
Reduction of primary energy consumption compared to Reference Scenario 2020	2 %

The "Hydrogen and Renewables" dimension aims to promote the energy transition by providing support to renewable energies, with a major focus on hydrogen production and other gases of renewable origin. The National Strategy for Hydrogen (EN-H2) foresees as investments, EUR 185 M for hydrogen and renewable gases, EUR 69 M for the potentiation of renewable electricity in the Madeira Archipelago and EUR 116 M for the energy transition in the Azores.

National Strategy for Hydrogen

This strategy supports national and EU decarbonisation goals by fostering the gradual adoption of hydrogen as a sustainable energy pillar. It promotes incentives and stability for the energy sector, integrating hydrogen into a broader transition to a decarbonized economy. The plan focuses on enhancing hydrogen supply and consumption across various sectors, laying the groundwork for a robust hydrogen economy in Portugal.¹⁰⁷

The long-term objective, by 2050, is to decarbonize the entire natural gas and power plant network and significantly reduce emissions in the transport and industrial sectors.

¹⁰⁷ <https://www.dgeg.gov.pt/en/transversal-areas/international-affairs/energy-policy/national-strategy-for-hydrogen>

The strategy also sets other goals that reveal its ambition until 2030, such as installed H₂ production capacity, number of H₂ vehicles (passengers and goods), creation of 50 to 100 hydrogen filling stations, 2 GW to 2.5 GW of installed capacity in electrolysis.

The Government is promoting an industrial policy around hydrogen and renewable gases, based on the definition of a set of public policies that guide, coordinate and mobilize public and private investment in projects in the areas of production, storage, transport and consumption of renewable gases in Portugal.

4.4.6. Policy Guidelines for Facilitating Deployment of LFM^s and Exploitation of Flexibility

Portugal is actively advancing its energy FS and LFM development to meet ambitious renewable energy and decarbonisation targets by 2030. The nation's strategic approach encompasses regulatory reforms, pilot projects, and substantial investments in smart grid technologies.

- **Regulatory Framework and National Plans**

In alignment with the EU's Clean Energy Package, Portugal has implemented Decree Law 15/2022, which restructures the National Electrical System (NES). This legislation emphasizes several key priorities:

- Simplification of Administrative Procedures: Streamlining prior control activities for NES operations to reduce bureaucratic hurdles.
- Network Planning Optimization: Maximizing the Public Service Electricity Network's capacity to integrate RES efficiently.
- Introduction of Competitive Mechanisms: Implementing competitive processes for licensing NES activities to ensure transparency and equity.
- Consumer Empowerment: Encouraging consumers to participate actively in energy production, storage, and FS.
- Legal Framework for Innovation: Establishing regulations for emerging technologies such as re-equipment, hybrid systems, and energy storage solutions.

These reforms are integral to Portugal's NECP 2030, which aims for 85% of electricity consumption to be from RES by 2030. The plan also targets the installation of 20.4 GW of solar capacity and 12.4 GW of wind capacity, including 2 GW offshore¹⁰⁸.

¹⁰⁸ <https://renewablesnow.com/news/portugal-targets-85-percent-renewables-in-electricity-mix-by-2030-827597>

- **Pilot Projects and Market Initiatives**

To implement these policies, Portugal has launched several pilot projects focusing on LFM:

- E-REDES and Piclo Collaboration: E-REDES, Portugal's primary DSO, in partnership with Piclo, have initiated the country's first LFM. This platform enables FSPs to participate in upcoming service opportunities, facilitating the integration of DER and enhancing grid decarbonisation efforts¹⁰⁹.
- FIRMe Pilot Project: E-REDES has also introduced the FIRMe project, aiming to create a LFM within distribution grids. The inaugural auction attracted 21 service providers, offering a total of 36 MW across various assets, including consumer installations, production units, and storage facilities. This initiative underscores the potential of FS to optimize grid management and integrate RES effectively¹¹⁰.

- **Investments in Smart Grids and Energy Storage**

Recognizing the critical role of infrastructure in supporting FS, Portugal is investing heavily in smart grids and energy storage:

- Grid Flexibility and Storage Incentive: The Portuguese government has established an incentive system to support the installation of at least 500 MW of energy storage capacity by December 31, 2025. This initiative aims to enhance grid flexibility and manage the anticipated increase in renewable energy production and consumption¹¹¹.
- Smart Grid Development: E-REDES is advancing the deployment of smart grids to accommodate new technologies and improve grid resilience. Efforts include transitioning to LED public lighting and implementing remote management systems, with a goal of achieving 100% LED coverage by 2027¹¹².

- **Stakeholder Engagement and Future Outlook**

The successful development of FS in Portugal hinges on active collaboration among various stakeholders, including regulatory authorities, grid operators, technology providers, and consumers. Initiatives like the DE-RISK project aim to support the market uptake of RES by fostering the adoption of LFMs and minimizing implementation risks through innovative customer engagement strategies.

¹⁰⁹ <https://www.piclo.energy/press-releases/e-redes-and-piclo-lead-the-way-towards-portugals-first-local-flexibility-market>

¹¹⁰ <https://www.e-redes.pt/en/news/2023/07/25/e-redes-launches-first-auction-local-flexibility-market-distribution-grids>

¹¹¹ <https://www.cuatrecasas.com/en/portugal/art/grid-flexibility-and-storage-incentive-for-companies>

¹¹² <https://csze.cz/en/projects-to-develop-flexibility-in-europe>

As Portugal progresses toward its 2030 energy objectives, the continuous evolution of regulatory frameworks, technological advancements, and stakeholder cooperation will be pivotal in realizing a resilient and sustainable energy system.

4.5. Spain

Spain is the 8th most attractive renewable energy investor in the world according to the 61 edition of the Renewable Energy Country Attractiveness Index (RECAI), prepared by Ernest - Young. It is also, after Germany, the 2th EU country that has concentrated the most investment in financing for new construction of assets for renewable energy projects in the period 2017-2021, according to Bloomberg Climate scope 2022, and the 7th globally.

The country is the 5th largest wind capacity worldwide for 2021 and is an electricity exporter, with a value of about 11,187 GWh.

Since 2010, REE¹¹³ has been the sole TSO and owner of the whole transmission network. As such, REE guarantees the continuity and security of supply and adheres to the principles of transparency, objectiveness and independence. It was set up in 1985 pursuant to Law 49/1984 of 26 December 1984, and the company is regulated by the Electricity Act and Royal Decree 1955/2000 of 1 December 2000, which regulates the transmission, distribution, retail and supply activities and authorization procedures for electricity facilities.¹¹⁴

In recent years, Spain has improved its system flexibility by integrating more variable renewables, including: allowing renewable energy and co-generation facilities to participate in balancing services; technical and regulatory work at the national and European level for the development of pan-European imbalance netting services (REE began participation in the Integrated Gasification Combined Cycle [IGCC] imbalance netting platform in September 2020), and regulation to allow demand-side response to participate in balancing markets.¹¹⁵

There are 333 distribution companies on the territory of Spain and five of them are dominant. These five companies, each with more than 100 000 consumers connected to their grids, are part of the main electricity companies in the country and carry out their activities in compliance with the unbundling requirements that are established in the electricity sector regulatory framework and in European law. The other companies are small ones, linked to the historical development of the local networks. As of 30 September 2019, the five traditional suppliers

¹¹³ <https://www.ree.es/en>

¹¹⁴ Electricity law and regulation in Spain- <https://cms.law/en/int/expert-guides/cms-expert-guide-to-electricity/spain>

¹¹⁵ Spain 2021 Energy Policy Review <https://iea.blob.core.windows.net/assets/bf2b75f3-224f-45bd-9dc2-83eb86388636/Spain2021.pdf>

supplied 84.9% of total supply points in the free market (three years before they supplied 90.4%).¹¹⁶

There is no centralized planning process for the distribution grid, although the government imposes a spending cap on distribution network plans, which are defined over periods of three years.

4.5.1. State-of-the-art of LFM and FS, Transposition of EU Regulation

The state-of-the-art in Spain includes developments in *regulatory frameworks, market structures, and technological advancements* aimed at optimizing local flexibility to enhance grid stability and maximize the use of RES such as solar panels, wind turbines, batteries for storage, electrical vehicles, and demand-side response.

Regulatory Framework

The reform of the electricity market started in 2013 with the Law 24/2013 of December, 26th 2013 (Electricity Act) to ensure its financial sustainability. Further legislations such as the Specific Remuneration Regime passed during the last decade to reform the electricity market and follow the EU Directives. The creation of a common electricity market with Portugal in 2006 (MIBEL) was a precursor of the European policy towards the goal of a more integrated European market. Without an integrated common market, Spain's network also has interconnection with France, Andorra and Morocco.¹¹⁷

The backbone of Spanish legislation that transposed also the EU directives (including Directive (EU) 2019/944 on common rules for the internal market for electricity (DIR), Regulation (EU) 2019/943 on the internal market for electricity (REG), Directive (EU) 2018/2001 on the promotion of the use of energy from RES (RED) and Regulation (EU) 2022/2577 laying down a framework to accelerate the deployment of renewable energy (ACC)) are as follow:

- Law 54/1997 on the liberalization of Spain's electricity market
- Parliamentary Resolution 23/2006 which approves the constitution of the Iberian Electricity Market (MIBEL)
- Integrate National Energy and Climate Plan (2021-2030 (INECP) which sets objectives for de-carbonization and RES development
- Climate Change and Energy Transition Act (CCET Act)
- Spain's Recovery, Transformation and Resilience Plan (RTRP) provides financing for the development of RES and the electricity network evolution

¹¹⁶ Spain Electricity Security Policy <https://www.iea.org/articles/spain-electricity-security-policy>

¹¹⁷ D3.2: Regulatory Impact Analyses for LFM - DE-RISK project.

- Law 24/2013– Electricity Act which organize and regulate the electricity Market and its participants
- Royal Decree 244/2019 which regulate auto-consumption
- Royal Decree-Law 23/2020 which regulate access to the electricity network & promote energy efficiency
- Royal Decree 446/2023 - update the methodology for estimating the dynamic electricity price that vary hourly

A new Royal Decree approving the General Regulation on Supply and Contracting and establishing the conditions for the commercialisation, aggregation and consumer protection of electrical energy is in an incipient phase of processing at the end of 2024. It aims to respond to the different challenges and energy policy objectives set out in the national and European regulations approved in recent years. The goal is to overcome the already obsolete regulations in force on the commercialisation and supply of electricity to make it more sustainable and efficient and with the clear objective of decarbonising the economy by 2050. This decree addresses the regulatory framework for aggregators and independent aggregators, a proposed interim aggregation model, and the rights and obligations of independent aggregators. The final framework is not expected to be implemented until 2025.

Access to wholesale markets in Spain is currently limited to suppliers and large energy consumers, with the main barrier for explicit DSF being the regulatory framework. Once aggregators are allowed access to wholesale markets, more tailored rules will need to be implemented enabling aggregation and portfolio management, establishing not overly restrictive technology requirements, and ensuring accurate and simple baseline requirements.

Residential and small commercial consumers can benefit from wholesale prices through a well-developed dynamic tariff (PVPC) where the TSO publishes on a daily basis the hourly wholesale prices for the next day, making it available for those consumers. This tariff includes a time-of-use component with three different time slots. Subscription to the PVPC and other dynamic electricity contracts is supported by the completed rollout of smart meters. By 2023, 99% of Spanish households had a smart meter installed, enabling the recording of consumption data every 60 minutes. According to the Ministry of Energy, 8.5 million consumers use dynamic tariffs at the beginning of 2024, which amounts to one third of all residential consumers.¹¹⁸

Market Structure

In Spain, the electricity market is organized as the wholesale sale on one hand and the retail market on the other hand. The wholesale market is managed by REE and is divided into the day-

¹¹⁸ <https://smarten.eu/>

ahead, the intraday and the balancing markets (Art.23, Law 24/2013). The last one is used by the TSO to manage real-time imbalances between supply and demand. Participation in the balancing markets is allowed for different market participants such as electricity producers (generation), aggregators and storage facilities. The procurement of balance services (aFRR, mFRR, RR) by the TSO is remunerated by recovering balancing costs.¹¹⁹

To participate in the electricity markets, market players must be registered with the Spanish regulatory authority: the National Commission on Markets and Competition (CNMC). The CNMC is responsible for ensuring the electricity market's competitiveness and its efficiency by monitoring and regulating market entry and exit, price setting.

Technological advancements

Spain's legislation has already triggered beneficial developments, for example in the roll-out of smart meters and contracts with dynamic tariffs.

Spain is one of the international frontrunners when it comes to the use of smart meters and the operation of a smart grid. In its electricity retail market monitoring report, The Comisión Nacional de los Mercados y la Competencia stated that:

- 99% coverage of smart meters was achieved in Spanish households by December 2019.
- As a result, an increasing number of consumers are entering into contracts with dynamic price tariffs, reaching almost 14 million consumers at the same time.

4.5.2. Smart Local Flexibility Services - Compliance and Safety

Compliance

The regulatory framework of the Spanish electricity system has undergone a profound transformation in recent years as a result of the need to adapt to the challenges from the energy transition and in compliance with Spain's ambitious objectives of decarbonisation. This transformation has also been reinforced by the gradual adaptation of national regulations to the European regulatory framework and, more recently, due to the energy crisis caused by Russia's invasion of Ukraine. The main energy law in Spain is Law 24/2013 (Ley del sector eléctrico), enacted in 2013 and updated in 2023. This legislation includes numerous definitions and regulates various aspects of the electricity market, such as generation, transmission, distribution, and commercialization, but also emphasizes the market's security, efficiency and transparency. It also delegates the economic and technical management of the electricity

¹¹⁹ D3.2: Regulatory Impact Analyses for LFM - DE-RISK project.

system to the state administration and assigns the responsibility of grid management to the operator Red Eléctrica de España (REE).¹²⁰

The Royal Decree 1183/2020 regulates FS, DR, and the participation of end-users in the electricity market. This decree outlines the conditions and requirements for FS, ensuring they operate within a structured legal framework.

The extensive use of data (e.g., energy consumption data, smart meter readings), in Spain is in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and it is of great importance for the protection of consumers' privacy.

Safety

Smart local FS in Spain refer to advanced energy systems designed to improve the efficiency, sustainability, and flexibility of electricity grids by integrating various technologies, such as smart meters, DR, energy storage, and RES. These services help manage the grid's supply and demand, ensure the stability of the electricity network, and enable the efficient use of energy resources.

To face the fluctuation of RES production and the need of flexibility, the Spanish government leans towards the development of energy storage with an objective of 6 GW additional storage capacities (3.5 GW from pumped storage and 2.5 GW from batteries) according to the PNIEC. Article 49 (Law 24/2013) states that consumers and owners of storage facilities (either directly or through aggregation) may participate in the services included in the generation or demand-side flexibility market. REE and the DSOs are allowed to operate storage facilities from 2021 as long as they are integrated as a network component.

Demand management and electricity storage are cited as the two major components of Spain's policy in this area, in accordance with the PNIEC 2021-2030. This legislation opens up the possibility of incentives for the provision of FS (Art.1 (1)) and particularly within local markets (according to Annex I).

Smart local FS involve the use of digital technologies, making them vulnerable to cyberattacks. The Spanish government, as part of its national cybersecurity strategy, has established frameworks to ensure that energy systems are protected from cyber threats. The National Cybersecurity Institute (INCIBE) is responsible for ensuring the protection of critical infrastructure, including the energy sector.

¹²⁰ Analysis of the implementation of EU provisions for the clean energy transition in selected Member States
www.ecologic.eu/sites/default/files/publication/2024/50153-Implementation-EU-Provisions-for-the-Clean-Energy-Transition-Final-Report.pdf

Smart meters used in FS must meet strict safety standards. These include ensuring that the meters are tamper-proof, accurate, and do not pose risks to consumer safety, such as electrical hazards.

4.5.3. Business Models and Financing Mechanisms to Boost Stakeholder Motivation

Boosting stakeholder motivation in Spain's LFM requires a combination of innovative business models and financing mechanisms that align the interests of various market participants, including energy consumers, energy producers, grid operators, technology providers, and investors. By developing business models that offer clear incentives and financing mechanisms that lower barriers to entry, the Spanish LFMs can grow and contribute to a more efficient, sustainable, and resilient energy system.

Here are some key business models and financing mechanisms that could help stimulate stakeholder participation and engagement in Spain's LFMs:

Business models

- Demand Response Programs for residential and commercial consumers who are incentivized to reduce or shift their electricity demand during peak periods or when grid instability occurs. This can be achieved through automated systems or manual participation.
- Virtual Power Plants (VPPs) that aggregate DERs, such as solar panels, wind turbines, battery storage, and flexible demand, to operate as a single entity in the energy market. VPPs can offer both energy generation and storage services while providing grid balancing and ancillary services.
- Energy-as-a-Service is a subscription-based business model in which customers pay for energy services (e.g., FS, grid balancing, energy management) rather than for the energy itself. It can include bundled services such as DR, energy storage management, and optimization of renewable energy use.
- Peer-to-Peer (P2P) Energy Trading - Consumers or small producers (e.g., homeowners with solar panels) can sell or trade excess energy with each other directly, using blockchain or other decentralized platforms. This enables local energy markets where consumers can actively participate in balancing supply and demand. Endesa has developed a pilot project that uses blockchain to enable customers to track the origin of the renewable electricity they consume.

- Flexibility-as-a-Service - Companies provide flexibility solutions to consumers and businesses, such as smart energy management systems, battery storage, and grid balancing. These services help both the energy user and the grid optimize energy consumption and production in real-time.

Financing mechanisms

The Spanish government offers various *incentives* for adopting EE technologies and renewable energy generation systems. These can include grants, tax incentives, *or subsidies* for individuals and businesses investing in local flexibility solutions.

- *The Energy-Efficiency National Fund* may receive contributions from other sources such as the ERDF Community Structural Funds, the State's general assumptions or any other resources intended to finance actions aimed at implementing energy saving and efficiency measures. The fund energises financial institutions as actors to mobilise inventions in energy efficiency and renewable energies, given that the energy transition must take place with all public and private actors and all regional and local authorities.
- *Public-private partnerships* can enable large-scale projects involving local FS. The public sector can provide initial capital, regulatory frameworks, and policy support, while private companies bring technological expertise and commercial funding. Collaborations between government entities and private companies can drive innovation and investment in LFMs. For example, Spain's leveraging of industrial clusters to lead Europe's energy transition demonstrates the effectiveness of such partnerships. By boosting demand signals, streamlining financing mechanisms, and channeling Emission Trading System (ETS) revenues into cleantech innovation, Spain is positioning itself at the forefront of the energy transition.
- *Green bonds* can be issued to finance local flexibility projects that focus on reducing carbon emissions, enhancing renewable energy integration, or improving energy efficiency. Investors in these bonds can benefit from stable returns while supporting sustainable development.
- Energy storage systems are crucial for FS, and *innovative financing mechanisms* can lower the barrier to entry for consumers or small businesses to install storage technologies. This could include financing options like leasing, Power Purchase Agreements (PPAs), or Energy-as-a-Service models for storage.
- *Crowdfunding and Community Financing* - Community-based financing mechanisms can be used to fund local energy flexibility projects. Crowdfunding platforms allow individuals to invest in energy projects in their community, sharing in the benefits or returns generated from those projects.

4.5.4. Awareness and Actions to Ensure High Customer Participation in the LFM

The raising of awareness is very important for the development of the LFM in Spain. The roles of the participants in this market will change and develop along with the services and the newcomers as new types of producers and customers.

A good example is the storage deployment in Spain that will add to provide opportunities for job creation, fair transition, economic recovery, and the creation of new business models across the value chain. These technologies are in place in sectors such as electric mobility, building or industry, and promote the development of new business models such as independent aggregators or renewable energy communities, which drive the active role of consumers.

The Spanish supply market is only partially liberalized, with the majority of customers still purchasing electricity at regulated prices (i.e. on the LRT). In terms of demand, most energy is contracted on the free market at a fixed price (77%) and the rest (23%) pays the daily market price. So these 23% are the ones that are affected by the price fluctuations on the day-ahead market. Of this 23% of demand met on the day-ahead market, just under half is accounted for by household customers on the regulated tariff (PVPC). Although this amount seems small, it has a large social impact, as about 10 million household consumers use this tariff. The rest of the demand is accounted for by industrial customers who freely choose to be supplied from the pool.¹²¹

These peculiarities of the market define the inactivity of a significant part of the actors and thus lead to delay in customer engagement.

To ensure high customer participation in Spain's LFM, it is essential to create awareness about the benefits, opportunities, and mechanisms available, as well as to provide the right incentives, education, and support for customers.

The Spanish Ministry for Ecological Transition and Demographic Challenges recognizes self-consumption as one of the cornerstones that needs to be strengthened in the coming years. Although self-consumption has risen steadily in recent years, further support is needed to encourage consumers to actively participate in the electricity market in its many dimensions. Therefore, the Ministry of Energy has put in place measures to strengthen self-consumption in

¹²¹ The Spanish Gas and Electricity Sector: Regulation, Markets and Environmental Policies, Giulio Federico, Feb, 2011, IESE Business School - <https://www.iese.edu/media/research/pdfs/OP-0187-E.pdf>

Spain as part of its roadmap to self-consumption (also see Art. 21 RED). These measures include, among other things:

- a support program for self-consumption (Measure 1),
- raising awareness and disseminating information about self-consumption (Measure 6),
- ensuring transparency of access and connection costs for electricity (Measure 23), and
- providing impulses for self-consumption using storage facilities (Measure 29).¹²²

Developing local flexibility programs, using smart home applications, meters and systems, create time-of-use pricing models, learning about the benefits of FS, such as cost savings, grid stability, and environmental impact reduction - all of these are a small part of the methods for increasing the customer participation in the LFM.

4.5.5. Strategic Planning Documents

Specific roadmaps and strategies are adopted in the Strategic Energy and Climate Framework of Spain. The development of these documents has allowed for certain areas a particular level of detail, precision and creation of visibility and certainty that were incorporated into the updated NECP in 2023. INECP, the Energy Storage Strategy and the Self-consumption roadmap will be presented for the purposes of this report.

Integrated National Energy and Climate Plan (2021-2030)

The energy sector's policy and the flexibility market and services are set by the INCEP 2021-2030 which allows the country to respect its European commitments regarding the decarbonization of the sector and the development of renewable energies (includes several measures to facilitate their integration, including measures on demand management, storage and flexibility, and on the adaptation of electrical networks for the integration of renewables.). Spain targets a 42% share of renewables in final energy consumption and a 23% reduction in GHG emissions in 2030. It aims at carbon neutrality in 2050. The country expects to raise wind and solar capacity to 38 GW and 21 GW, respectively, in 2030.¹²³

The INCEP is revised in 2023 and sets some higher goals, aiming for a 25% decrease in greenhouse gas emissions by 2030 and obtaining 81% of electricity requirements from RES over the coming ten years. Spain's plan sets the target for energy efficiency at 48% by 2030. This increase is accompanied by strengthened measures to promote flexibility, storage and demand management (See Table 6).

¹²² Just Transition Strategy - https://www.miteco.gob.es/content/dam/miteco/es/ministerio/planes-estrategias/transicion-justa/Just%20Transition%20Strategy_ENG.pdf

¹²³ Draft of the Integrated National Energy and Climate Plan (2021-2030) - https://energy.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2019-06/ec_courtesy_translation_es_necp_0.pdf

Table 6: Summary of Spain’s revised NECP objectives for 2030

Renewable Energy Sources	
Renewable electricity generation	74%
National target for the share of energy from renewable sources in gross final energy consumption by 2030	42 %
Share of electricity from renewable sources in gross final consumption of electricity	81 %
Share of heating and cooling from RES in gross final consumption of heating and cooling	35 %
Share of energy from renewable sources in final energy consumption in the transport sector	25 %
Energy Efficiency	
Reduction of primary energy consumption compared to Reference Scenario 2020	2.5 %

The Energy Storage Strategy provided for 20 GW of energy storage by 2030. With the 2023-2030 NECP, these forecasts are exceeded, rising to 22 GW in 2030.

The National Energy and Climate Plan for 2030 of Spain can play the role of a detailed roadmap towards climate neutrality by 2050, with important targets outlined for 2030 (See Table 7).

Table 7: Spain Roadmap to 2030

Year	Key Actions
2024-2025	Regulatory sandbox launch, first pilot projects, local flexibility definitions.
2026-2027	Standardized contracts, expansion of smart metering, AI-enabled grid management.
2028-2029	National rollout of LFMs, V2G market activation, blockchain transactions in P2P markets.
2030	Fully operational LFMs integrated into Spain’s electricity market, allowing real-time flexibility trade.

Greenhouse gas emissions are expected to decrease by 35% by 2030.

Final energy efficiency has improved by 44 % by 2030 compared to the 2007 baseline scenario, while in the 2021-2030 NECP it stood at 41.7 %.

A specific target for the deployment of self-consumption is set at 19 GW installed in 2030.

Electrification of the economy is increasing over the decade as one of the key drivers of decarbonisation, increasing to 34 % in 2030. In particular, with regard to electric vehicles, projections are increasing to a fleet of 5.5 million electric vehicles in 2030 (10 % higher than the previously set target), while significant deployment of heat pumps is expected.

The Energy Storage Strategy

As a part of its roadmap towards realizing a 100% renewable electricity system by 2050, the Spanish government announced its support for the development of technology for energy storage for renewables, to increase the system's flexibility and the stability of the network. It allocated EUR 150 million in 2024 to catalyse energy storage projects linked to renewable installations, an initiative that demonstrates a strong commitment to fostering sector growth through financial incentives.¹²⁴

The Strategy is part of the set of actions planned to meet the objectives established in the National Integrated Energy and Climate Plan 2021-2030 and the Long-Term Decarbonisation Strategy and envisages having a total energy storage capacity of 22.5 GW in 2030 and 30 GW by 2050, when the current capacity stands at 8.3 GW.¹²⁵

Installed capacity in stationary batteries in the European energy storage market has grown significantly in recent years from 0.6 GW/hour in 2015 to around 9.4 GW/hour in 2022. In fact, capacity doubled from 2021 to 2022. Last year around 30% of the market was residential storage, compared to 2% in commercial and industrial storage, and around 70% of installations corresponding to meters.

With an expanding market, Spain, Germany, Ireland and Greece account for the majority of projects, both new projects under construction and operating projects. The report highlights six of the 128 Spanish projects in Teruel, Zaragoza, Valencia, Girona, Granada and Seville, which total over 7,500 MW of power.¹²⁶

Spain is the leader in molten salt energy storage at solar power plants, with a capacity of around 6.8 GW.

The attractiveness of storage technologies will predictably rise in the future due to lower costs, technological improvements that will give a longer useful life for equipment and greater flexibility in a market in need of RES.

The Self-consumption (Auto-consum) Roadmap

The Roadmap is included in Reform C7 R2 “National Self-consumption Strategy” of Component 7 “Deployment and integration of renewable energies” of the Recovery, Transformation and Resilience Planning Policy Lever 3. “Fair and Inclusive Energy Transition” corresponding to the Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge.

¹²⁴Spain and Germany, joint leaders in energy storage in Europe - <https://www.investinspain.org/en/news/2023/spain-germany>

¹²⁵ Energy Storage in Spain: a key element for the energy transition - <https://www.iberdrolaespana.com/sustainability/energy-storage>

¹²⁶ Spain and Germany, joint leaders in energy storage in Europe - <https://www.investinspain.org/en/news/2023/spain-germany>

Its main motivation is to identify the challenges and opportunities and establish measures to fulfil the development potential of the sector and it sets the following objectives:

- Establish the penetration potential of self-consumption by type of consumer.
- Establish lines of action to promote renewable self-consumption, placing citizens at the centre of the energy system, and activate its use as a key tool in the fight against energy poverty.
- Develop instruments to promote their shared use.
- Facilitate the implementation of applications in areas such as the industrial or service sector in a context of economic reactivation, as well as in the public sector.
- Develop self-consumption as a lever for the rapid generation of activity and employment, both directly and through the effect on the different local value chains and savings in energy costs for consumers and industry.¹²⁷

The development of the potential of self-consumption of PV energy till 2030 is as it is shown in the Table 8 below:

Table 8: The potential of self-consumption of PV energy till 2030 in Spain¹²⁸

En conclusión, el Potencial de autoconsumo fotovoltaico a 2030 se recoge en la siguiente tabla (Tabla 1):

Tabla 1: Resumen global de los Potenciales (Técnico, Económico y Real) a 2030 en el Escenario Base.

Tipo de consumidor (cifras en GW)	Escenario Base (2030)		
	Potencial Técnico*	Potencial Económico	Potencial Real
Comercial	48,1 (C+F)	8,88	5,77
Residencial Plurifamiliar	37,6 (C+F)	4,19	1,85
Residencial Unifamiliar	49,4 (C+F)	0,18	0,08
Industrial	33,7 (C+F)	1,74	1,13
Total, Nacional	168,7 (C+F)	14,99	8,83

(C): Cubiertas; (F) Fachadas
(*) Según parque de edificios

Fuente: Elaboración propia

¹²⁷ Self-Consumption Roadmap - <https://www.idae.es/en/technologies/renewable-energies/self-consumption-office/self-consumption-roadmap>

¹²⁸ Study on the photovoltaic potential for self-consumption in Spain
https://www.idae.es/sites/default/files/documentos/idae/tecnologias/energias_renovables/OFICINA-de-AUTOCONSUMO/InformeFV_Con%20Baterias_prueba%20FINAL.pdf

4.5.6. Policy Guidelines for Facilitating Deployment of LFM^s and Exploitation of Flexibility

Spain is actively advancing its energy transition with a focus on enhancing the FS and developing LFM^s by 2030. The National Integrated Energy and Climate Plan (PNIEC) 2023-2030 outlines several key strategies and actions to achieve these objectives:

- *Expansion of Renewable Energy and Storage*

The PNIEC aims to increase RES to constitute 81% of the electricity mix by 2030. This includes installing 76 GW of PV capacity, with 19 GW dedicated to self-consumption, and 62 GW of wind energy, including 3 GW of offshore wind. To support this, 22.5 GW of energy storage systems are planned, facilitating better integration of RES and enhancing grid flexibility¹²⁹.

- *Regulatory Reforms for Flexibility and Demand Response*

Spain is developing a regulatory framework to promote demand-side management and FS. This includes the integration of independent aggregators and the facilitation of consumer participation in energy markets. The reforms aim to create a more dynamic energy system capable of efficiently absorbing higher levels of renewable generation¹³⁰.

- *Promotion of New Business Models*

The government encourages innovative business models such as energy storage solutions, hybridization of generation technologies, and the formation of RECs. These initiatives are designed to foster decentralized energy generation and active consumer involvement, contributing to local flexibility and resilience¹³¹.

- *Implementation of Local Flexibility Markets*

Projects like BeFlexible are underway to enhance cooperation between DSOs and TSOs. These projects aim to validate and demonstrate cross-sectoral services and interoperable platforms for smart grid operations, facilitating the participation of various energy stakeholders in LFM^s¹³².

To ensure the successful deployment of LFM^s in Spain, comprehensive recommendations can be defined to be implemented across policy, market, technology, and stakeholder engagement.

¹²⁹ <https://www.mondaq.com/energy-and-natural-resources/1534672/update-of-the-national-integrated-energy-and-climate-plan-2023-2030>

¹³⁰ eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX%3A52024PC0592

¹³¹ <https://www.mariscal-abogados.com/promotion-of-new-business-models-in-the-energy-sector-in-spain>

¹³² <https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/featured-projects/beflexible-future-proofing-europes-electricity-grids-flexible-and-sustainable-energy-supply>

- **Regulatory and Policy Framework**

Clear Market Rules: Define roles, responsibilities, and compensation mechanisms for flexibility providers (DSOs, aggregators, prosumers). Legally recognize independent aggregators that bundle residential, commercial, and industrial flexibility.

Incentives for Flexibility Services: Create financial incentives for demand-side response (DSR), battery storage, and distributed generation participation. For example: Introduce tax breaks or subsidies for residential and industrial consumers that provide grid flexibility; Implement dynamic network tariffs, encouraging consumers to shift energy consumption based on grid demand; Allow LFMs to stack revenue streams (e.g., capacity payments, congestion relief, frequency control).

Create a Regulatory Sandbox for LFMs: Launch regional pilot programs in high-renewable penetration areas (e.g., Andalusia, Catalonia, Basque Country). Allow flexibility providers to test real-time bidding, aggregation models, and dynamic pricing structures.

DSO-TSO Coordination: Improve communication between DSOs and TSO (REE) to optimize flexibility procurement.

Harmonization with EU Frameworks: Align with EU Electricity Regulation (2019/943) and Clean Energy Package provisions on LFMs.

- **Market Design & Participation**

Local Price Signals: Implement location-based pricing for grid services, reflecting congestion and voltage support needs. Implement nodal pricing or zonal price signals to reflect local grid constraints. Allow DSOs to pay consumers for local marginal flexibility, rewarding those in congestion-prone areas.

Open Market Platforms: Develop digital platforms to facilitate real-time bidding for FS, accessible to aggregators, prosumers, and storage owners. For example: Establish local flexibility marketplaces at the distribution level, coordinated with national electricity markets; DSOs should procure flexibility via real-time bidding platforms (e.g., hourly auctions). Develop standardized communication protocols between aggregators and DSOs/TSOs.

Hybrid Market Models: Allow both bilateral contracts (for long-term flexibility procurement) and spot market transactions for real-time grid balancing. Allow peer-to-peer (P2P) trading of energy and flexibility within communities.

Different Procurement Mechanisms: Use a hybrid approach combining: Long-term contracts for predictable, reliable flexibility; Spot market auctions for real-time grid balancing; Pay-as-bid models for high-demand periods

- **Technological Enablement**

Deploy Smart Grid Infrastructure - 100% smart meter coverage by 2027 to enable real-time DR. Invest in real-time distribution network monitoring (sensor-based grid management).

Implement AI-driven forecasting tools for DSOs to predict congestion needs and anticipate demand peaks. Use blockchain technology to secure P2P flexibility transactions.

Expand Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) integration by creating V2G incentives, allowing EV owners to sell flexibility to the grid. Develop charging station management software that supports LFM participation. Pilot fleet-based V2G services for commercial EV operators (e.g., bus depots, delivery vans).

- **Consumer & Stakeholder Engagement**

Prosumers & Communities: Encourage participation of energy communities, industries, and households in LFMs through dynamic tariffs and peer-to-peer trading. Offer financial incentives for self-consumption collectives participating in LFMs. Allow energy communities to bid solar-battery flexibility into distribution-level markets. Provide blockchain-based energy wallets for REC/CEC members to track transactions.

Education & Awareness: Inform stakeholders about flexibility markets, their benefits, and participation mechanisms. Launch DSO-led education programs on how households can participate in LFMs. Implement user-friendly mobile apps for consumers to track and adjust energy usage dynamically. Partner with universities and research centres to train energy flexibility professionals.

- **Pilot Projects and Scaling**

Regulatory Sandbox Projects: Launch test projects in urban and rural areas to assess the impact of LFMs on the grid. Barcelona Smart Grid Flexibility Pilot to Test blockchain-based P2P energy trading. Seville Industrial Demand Response Program using AI to manage factory demand shifts. Madrid V2G Demonstration Zone to deploy 100 EV chargers participating in LFMs.

Public-Private Partnerships: Engage utilities, technology firms, and local governments in developing scalable solutions. Partner with Iberdrola, Endesa, and Naturgy to fund large-scale flexibility trials. Involve smart city initiatives to integrate urban energy storage solutions. Collaborate with local governments to develop regulatory blueprints.

By following these recommendations, Spain can build scalable and efficient LFM that enhance grid stability, reduce energy costs, and accelerate the transition to a decentralized, renewable-powered system.

4.5.7. Findings as a Result of the Pilots Implementation in Spain

Joven Futura pilot in Murcia

The pilot in Murcia consists of 15 apartments in residential buildings with a shared self-consumption system composed of two 10 kW installations, with a total consumption capacity of 138 kWp across these homes. The average annual consumption is around 3.000 kWh per household. As a result of the successful crowdlending campaign, an additional single-family home with individual solar self-consumption was added to the group. This solar installation, along with the monitoring and control devices, was financed through the mentioned campaign by local investors.

The development of the pilot began with user recruitment from among households in the target neighbourhood (Joven Futura) that showed interest in energy flexibility. This required a significant educational effort for two main reasons. First, the average citizen in Spain is not very familiar with how the electricity system works, due to a lack of adequate public outreach. Second, as stated in this report, 77% of Spanish households are on fixed-rate tariffs, where they are not affected by hourly price variations, making implicit demand response economically meaningless—although explicit demand response still makes sense.

Therefore, the first step was to switch users to and keep them on tariffs indexed to the electricity market price. This was made possible by allowing users to view updated hourly prices for the current day and the next day through the MIW app, enabling them to organize their consumption accordingly. This marks the beginning of the citizen's journey to participate in local flexibility markets.

Problems in the pilot trend arise when market prices rise or fall sharply within a short period. The DE-RISK project started just as Spain was beginning to emerge from the 2022 price crisis, and consumers were looking for fixed-rate tariffs for protection. At that time, only the large energy companies could offer dynamic tariffs, as most of the energy they sell is self-generated, meaning they don't need to hedge 100% of their fixed-rate sales in futures markets—unlike small and medium-sized retailers.

This was the focus of the initial information and training effort. Later, in the winter of 2024–2025, market prices rose again, mainly due to gas-fired power plants entering many auctions

and the high winter gas prices. As this price increase was expected to subside by spring, large companies again offered long-term fixed-rate contracts at prices below the current market, aiming to recover lost profit when market prices returned to normal levels.

As a result, many participants in the pilot (over 50%) wanted to leave MIW, a variable-price retailer, for fixed-price options offered by other providers. This issue was resolved without customer dropouts by offering some clients a significant discount on the indexed price—still keeping them on indexed tariffs and maintaining the economic incentive for demand response. For those who did not accept this option, a discretized tariff with three time periods was created.

These incidents reflect the barriers to local flexibility markets in Spain, which are mainly regulatory, related to public understanding of the energy system, and stem from the lack of a fully liberalized retail market. Traditional retailers—linked to distribution—still hold a large market share (over 80%) in the residential sector, almost entirely through fixed-rate tariffs. This trend intensifies when market prices become volatile, as shown in this CNMC report.¹³³

La Balma pilot in Barcelona

La Balma Energy Community project was executed and legalized without issues, mainly due to the division of the power plant into a two-section project: One for the actual EC (7.84 kWp) and one for the common areas (9.52 kWp), which avoids requiring a complex legal procedure which all self-consumption installations must undergo if they exceed a total 15 kW nominal power. Another of the possible bottlenecks, the DSO acceptance of the sharing coefficients, was conducted without issues in La Balma.

One of the major setbacks to the project, which affected the relationship between La Balma (as EC) and R2M Solution (as energy managers), was the payment for PV generated electricity. Initially set at a fixed value for the duration of the project during the energy crisis, the prices quickly fell below the set price, which in turn opened negotiations and was changed to follow the same cost pattern as their Time-of-Use tariff (indexed to the grid price). This required open communication with their energy retailer, which proceeded without issue.

Deployment of LFM in the pilot of La Balma was met with partial excitement from the side of the participants, with only 9 of the coexistence units (out of 20) agreeing to the installation of extra equipment required for instantaneous consumption analysis.

¹³³ [Update on the state of the retail electricity market. consumer flexibility 2023 \(CNMC, 2023\)](#)

While access to instantaneous consumption provides crucial insights to flexibility models, the lack of control devices in the residences as well as the common consumption points of La Balma (like geothermal heating or washing machine areas) difficulties actions on part of the users, which need to be aware of the consumption recommendations on the web app.

The last hindrance to participation is the current lack of incentives beyond Time-of-Use price differences and photovoltaic energy generation prediction patterns coupled with battery use. While ToU incentives can promote demand shifting, it can also fall short of generating enough benefit to the user for long-term behavioural changes.

The deployment of new Smart Grid Infrastructure with real time measurements is crucial to reduce the need of extra installations, which inconvenience the user and reduce their rate of acceptance.

It is important for the DSO to develop an incentive mechanism based on demand change which further promotes demand shifting beyond ToU schemes, as they currently do not provide enough incentives, or they are extremely dependent on daily price differences.

4.6. Türkiye

Türkiye is experiencing a rapid and radical transition of its energy system with the growing economy and the subsequent energy demand, country-specific economic priorities and the markets that are becoming more competitive. This transition is accompanied by rapidly increasing renewable energy investments, on-site and distributed generation assets and a market model that gives increasing opportunity to the consumers to make their own energy choices.

Türkiye's energy policy has focused on maximizing the use of RES while reducing dependency on imports by enhancing supply security. The strategy for the energy sector by 2030 involves maximizing energy efficiency and renewable potential while taking into account feasibility, market circumstances, and energy security.

Looking ahead, the Turkish government has set ambitious targets for renewable energy. By 2030, their aim is to achieve a 50% share of renewable energy, and 80% by 2053.¹³⁴

Significant advancements in renewable energy have led to a 59% share of renewable energy in the overall installed capacity. The 2030 targets of Türkiye are to increase the installed solar capacity up to 38,000 MW, wind capacity up to 25,000 MW and geothermal capacity up to 4,000 MW.

4.6.1. State-of-the-art of LFM and FS, Transposition of EU Regulation

Türkiye adopted the Paris Agreement in 2015 and signed it on 22 April 2016 launching the country's move towards green development.

Furthermore, as a country going through the European Union accession process, Türkiye closely follows EU policies and has been formulating legislation on climate change and environment in order to align with the relevant *acquis*.

Türkiye's commitment is to reduce its greenhouse gas emissions by 21% by 2030 and to achieve net zero emissions by 2053, aligning key sectors with green development strategies. Various policies and regulations have also targeted improving energy efficiency in both buildings and industry. At present, over 46 energy cooperatives exist in Türkiye. There is a need for further steps in regard to the legal and administrative framework to be suitable for their further development.

¹³⁴ Turkey's energy transition from fossil-based to renewable up to 2030: milestones, challenges and opportunities | Clean Technologies and Environmental Policy

The review of Turkish legislation under RED II and ED 2019 reveals that the adoption of the energy communities' concepts and the requirements are not met, except for cursory regulations on energy cooperatives.

The number of the RECs in Türkiye as of 2020, was 46 and has been growing due to increased environmental awareness and supportive energy policies¹³⁵. The legal and administrative framework for energy cooperatives in Türkiye is still evolving and discussions and research are needed on how to better enable and support these cooperatives. The Turkish government has been working on aligning its policies with the EU's Renewable Energy Directive (RED II) and the Clean Energy for All Europeans package (CEP) aiming to enhance the development and effectiveness of renewable energy cooperatives. At present renewable energy cooperatives face challenges, including financing, technology, and policy barriers. However, they also present significant opportunities for local communities to benefit from RES and contribute to the energy transition.

4.6.2. Smart local flexibility Services - Compliance and Safety

The shift to clean energy, which revolves around energy efficiency, electrification, and RES, is essential for reaching climate objectives as well as ensuring energy supply security and affordable energy access. This is made possible by technological advancements and decreasing costs that come with the transition.

The regulatory framework for smart FS has evolved significantly to enhance grid stability and integrate DER. Until 2023 the legislative infrastructure for demand side participation has been completed, enabling electricity consumers with flexible or shiftable loads to participate as players in ancillary services and balancing power markets. With the regulations made to provide consumers with comparable and more detailed billing information on electricity bills, access to past period consumption information such as daily energy consumption average and the current year and the previous calendar year has been provided.

Additionally, renewable energy objectives necessitate greater flexibility in electricity systems, where maintaining a balance between supply and demand is crucial, and battery energy storage systems can play a significant role in achieving this balance.

Türkiye already has over 14 GW of solar energy capacity with storage in pre-licensing stages, far exceeding the 2030 target of 2.1 GW outlined in the National Energy Plan. The realisation of this

¹³⁵ <https://gcris.ieu.edu.tr/bitstream/20.500.14365/394/1/2969.pdf>

capacity will enhance the flexibility of Türkiye's energy grid and facilitate the integration of even more solar capacity into the system by storing excess generation when needed.¹³⁶

The development of the market infrastructure for demand-side response¹³⁷ has the objective to better manage peak demand through the FS. Since 2018, Türkiye's regulation added a registry system for FS and flexibility services providers need to identify and register the FS that they will sell.

A pivotal development is the introduction of the Electricity Market Aggregator Regulation, published on December 17, 2024, and effective from January 1, 2025. This regulation establishes aggregators as formal participants in the electricity market, defining them as legal entities holding either an aggregator license or a supply license with aggregation activities. Aggregators are authorized to group and manage the generation and/or consumption activities of multiple grid users, facilitating their collective participation in organized wholesale markets, balancing markets, and ancillary services.¹³⁸ To operate as an aggregator, entities must obtain the appropriate license from the Energy Market Regulatory Authority (EMRA). The licensing process requires demonstrating financial adequacy, technical capability, and compliance with specific operational standards. Aggregators are responsible for managing production and consumption schedules, conducting electricity and capacity trading on behalf of their clients, and participating in ancillary services. They must also fulfil all market obligations, including collateral and imbalance responsibilities.¹³⁹

Additionally, Türkiye has implemented regulations to promote the integration of RES and enhance grid flexibility. The Regulation on Unlicensed Electricity Generation in the Electricity Market allows consumers to generate electricity from RES for their own use, with provisions for transferring surplus energy to other facilities under certain conditions. However, collective generation by energy communities is currently limited to entities sharing the same connection point or a common meter, which restricts broader community-based initiatives.¹⁴⁰

Overall, Türkiye's regulatory landscape is progressively adapting to support smart FS, with a focus on integrating aggregators into the electricity market and promoting the use of RES.

Türkiye is actively advancing its energy infrastructure by implementing smart FS, with a strong emphasis on safety and efficiency. These initiatives aim to enhance grid reliability, integrate RES, and ensure consumer protection.

¹³⁶ In-brief: EN - Solar power met two-thirds of the peak demand increase.docx

¹³⁷ IEA – National Energy Efficiency Action Plan 2017-2023 (NEEAP)

¹³⁸ <https://www.mondaq.com/turkey/oil-gas-electricity/1560354/key-changes-to-turkeys-electricity-market-new-aggregator-licenses-explained>

¹³⁹ <https://paksoy.av.tr/en/2024/12/legal-briefing-on-recent-developments-in-the-electricity-market/>

¹⁴⁰ Legal Provisions and Market Conditions for Energy Communities in Austria, Germany, Greece, Italy, Spain, Türkiye: A Comparative Assessment

- Smart Grid Implementation and Safety Measures

The Turkish electricity distribution sector has outlined a comprehensive roadmap to transition to smart grids. A key objective is to replace at least 80% of the country's current electricity meters with smart meters by 2035. This transition is expected to improve consumer satisfaction through more efficient energy usage while reducing electricity losses and outages.¹⁴¹ In Türkiye, the installation of smart meters is not mandatory for residential electricity users, but it is necessary for those whose monthly electricity usage surpasses 2,000 kWh¹⁴². Additionally, the NEEAP outlines a pathway for effectively managing measurement data, suggesting the development of a legislative framework to comply with EU standards and providing data analysis to customers.

Türkiye plans to establish a national grid communication platform; to source smart meters and communication units from national suppliers; to develop a distribution network infrastructure supported by small-scale, distributed, and renewable resources; to increase the number of solar panels to at least one million and to create the necessary infrastructure to integrate them into the power network, and to reduce the rate of loss and illegal electricity use to 8%.

These initiatives underscore Türkiye's commitment to a safer and more efficient energy system.¹⁴³

- Innovative Safety Technologies

To enhance safety, Turkish energy companies are developing innovative solutions. For instance, Enerjisa has introduced the "Do Not Touch Me" system, a smart device designed to warn residents about electrical leaks in poles through sound and light alerts. This system aims to protect individuals, especially children and animals, from electric shocks. It has been piloted on the Anatolian side of Istanbul and is planned for expansion to other regions¹⁴⁴.

- Research and Development Initiatives

Türkiye is also investing in research to integrate local flexibility with national ancillary services markets. A study published in the Turkish Journal of Electrical Power and Energy Systems explores the interactions between national ancillary service markets and local flexibility in Türkiye's evolving power landscape. The research highlights the importance of grid flexibility, especially with the country's shift towards RES, and emphasizes the role of electricity distribution businesses in enhancing grid stability.¹⁴⁵

¹⁴¹ <https://www.mrcgroup-consulting.com/turkeys-smart-grid-road-map.php>

¹⁴² This threshold is set by the EMRA in the Electricity Market License Regulation.

¹⁴³ Turkey Smart Grid 2023

¹⁴⁴ Turkey: Smart system warns of leaks in electric pole

¹⁴⁵ Interaction of Local Flexibility with National Ancillary Services Markets: Paving the Way for Türkiye's Sustainable Grid

In summary, Türkiye's proactive approach in implementing smart FS, coupled with a strong focus on safety, positions the country to achieve a more efficient, reliable, and secure energy future.

4.6.3. Business Models and Financing Mechanisms to Boost Stakeholder Motivation

Electricity markets are operated by the EPIAŞ (Electricity Markets Operating Corporation) and are regulated by Law No 6446, 2013.¹⁴⁶

The electricity market in Türkiye is organised as a wholesale market and a retail market. The wholesale market is structured into the following markets: Day-Ahead market, Intraday market, Balancing Power market and Ancillary Services market¹⁴⁷.

Energy Exchange Istanbul (EXIST) is an energy exchange company, legally incorporated under the Turkish Electricity Market law. The wholesale electricity markets have been operating on it since 2015. It is enforced by the Energy Markets Operation License granted by the Energy Markets Regulatory Authority of Türkiye.¹⁴⁸

Flexibility services such as Primary Frequency Control (PFC) or Secondary Frequency Control (SFC) are part of this electricity market and are not compulsory; PFC and SFC reserves are procured on a voluntary basis.

The Renewable Energy Sources Support Mechanism (YEKDEM)¹⁴⁹ and the By-Law on Renewable Energy Resource Areas (YEKA)¹⁵⁰ have greatly aided the rapid growth of renewable energy investments, particularly in wind and solar energy.

A Presidential announcement regarding the prices and durations for the updated Renewable Energy Resources Support Mechanism (YEKDEM) in Türkiye has been released in 2023, with this, new feed-in-tariffs (FITs) have been implemented for electricity generation from renewable resources, including geothermal. Similar FIT structures have also been provided for solar, hydropower, biomass, facilities with energy storage, and power facilities based on wave or current energy.¹⁵¹

¹⁴⁶ CEE Legal Matters – Türkiye: Liberalisation of the Electricity Market and the Role of Antitrust Interventions

¹⁴⁷ Electricity Market – Sector Report 2021 – Republic of Türkiye Energy Market Regulatory Authority (EMRA)

¹⁴⁸ Europex – EPIAŞ – Energy Exchange Istanbul

¹⁴⁹ New YEKDEM scheme announced for renewables in Türkiye

¹⁵⁰ Republic of Türkiye Ministry of Energy and Natural Resources - Production Activities

¹⁵¹ [New YEKDEM scheme announced for renewables in Türkiye](#)

LFMs in Türkiye are evolving to enhance grid stability, integrate RES, and empower consumers to actively participate in energy management. These markets facilitate the trading of FS, such as DR and distributed generation, at the local level. LFM Key Business Models in Türkiye are well described in the Report¹⁵² of the Energy Transition Centre, as follows:

- **Supply Aggregators / Virtual Power Plants:** These entities combine various DERs like solar panels, wind turbines, and battery storage into a unified system. By centrally managing these resources, VPPs optimize energy production and consumption, providing services such as frequency regulation and voltage control to the grid. This model enhances grid stability and allows small-scale producers to participate in the energy market.
- **Demand Aggregators** manage and aggregate consumer demand flexibility. By adjusting consumption patterns in response to grid needs or price signals, demand aggregators help balance supply and demand, reduce peak loads, and defer infrastructure investments. They often employ advanced technologies like the Internet of Things (IoT) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) for real-time optimization.
- **Peer-to-Peer Energy Trading Platforms:** Leveraging blockchain technology, P2P platforms enable consumers and producers to trade energy directly within local communities. This decentralized approach promotes the use of local renewable energy, reduces transmission losses, and empowers consumers to take an active role in energy markets.
- **Energy-as-a-Service (EaaS) Providers:** EaaS companies offer comprehensive energy solutions, including energy supply, management, and optimization services. Customers pay for the service rather than owning the energy assets, which can include DERs, energy storage, and smart energy management systems. This model provides flexibility and reduces the need for upfront capital investment.
- **Energy Service Companies (ESCOs):** ESCOs implement energy efficiency projects and provide DERs on a turnkey basis. They often use performance-based contracting, where compensation is linked to the energy savings achieved. This model reduces energy costs for clients and promotes the adoption of efficient technologies.

The challenges that accompany the implementation of these business models in Türkiye concern the regulatory frameworks, the technological infrastructure, and the market dynamics.

¹⁵² [Analysis Of Business Models, Technologies, and the Needed Regulatory Scheme For Power System Digitalisation in Turkey - SHURA](#)

Regarding the regulatory environment clear definitions and regulations for new market roles, such as aggregators and prosumers, are essential. Establishing standards for FS and ensuring fair market access are important steps.

As for the technological side, advanced metering infrastructure, real-time data management, and communication systems are necessary to support these models. Investments in smart grid technologies will facilitate effective monitoring and control of DERs.

In relation to participating in the market, it is crucial to promote consumer involvement and establish trust in new energy services. Educational initiatives and transparent communication can help in this regard.

Projects like DE-RISK aims to address these challenges by developing innovative business models and financial mechanisms to support the adoption of LFM in Türkiye. By focusing on consumer engagement, regulatory frameworks, and technological solutions, such initiatives strive to unlock the full potential of local energy flexibility.

In Türkiye, financing mechanisms to boost stakeholder motivation should consider regulatory support, economic incentives, and innovative business models. Here are some key financing mechanisms that can be applied:

Government & Regulatory Support

- **Subsidies & Grants:** Direct financial support from the government for investments in smart grids, storage, and DR technologies.
- **Tax Incentives:** Reductions or exemptions on energy-related taxes for participants in flexibility markets.
- **Capacity Payments:** Financial rewards for stakeholders who ensure flexibility and grid stability, especially for demand-side management (DSM).

Market-Based Revenue Streams

- **Dynamic Pricing & Tariffs:** Time-of-use (ToU) tariffs, real-time pricing, and critical peak pricing models to incentivize flexibility.
- **Aggregators & Virtual Power Plants (VPPs):** Enabling small-scale energy producers and consumers to monetize flexibility by pooling their resources.
- **Contracts for Difference (CfD):** Price guarantees for energy flexibility providers to reduce financial risks.

Private Sector & Investment Models

- Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs): Collaboration between the government and private sector to fund flexibility market infrastructure.
- Green Bonds & Energy Performance Contracts (EPCs): Raising capital for energy efficiency and flexibility projects through sustainable finance instruments.
- Blockchain & Tokenization: Decentralized financing mechanisms through blockchain-based energy trading platforms.

Consumer Participation Incentives

- Peer-to-Peer Trading: Enabling prosumers to sell excess energy directly to consumers via digital platforms.
- Financial Rewards & Rebates: Direct payments or bill discounts for participation in DR programs.
- Community Energy Programs: Local energy cooperatives pooling resources for shared financial benefits.

Some successfully implemented initiatives to enhance stakeholder motivation in LFM through innovative financing mechanisms include:

- DE-RISK Project (See p.1.1)
- Turkish Sustainable Energy Financing Facility (TurSEFF)¹⁵³: Initiated in 2010 by the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD), TurSEFF addresses market shortcomings in sustainable energy by offering loans to private sector companies for EE and RE projects. It also provides technical assistance and expert advice to ensure the successful implementation of sustainable energy investments. This facility has been instrumental in motivating stakeholders by reducing financial barriers and promoting the adoption of energy-efficient technologies.
- Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Financing Facility (REFF)¹⁵⁴: The REFF facility is an ongoing initiative that continues to provide financial support for RE and EE investments. Similar to TurSEFF, it is designed for long-term impact and still functions in Türkiye to help meet sustainability goals. The facility has been active for several years and continues its operations.
- Yenilenebilir Enerji Kaynak Alanları (YEKA)¹⁵⁵ – Renewable Energy Resource Areas: The YEKA program, launched by the Turkish government, aims to boost the country's

¹⁵³ <https://www.ebrd.com/work-with-us/procurement/pn-64597.html>

¹⁵⁴ [chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://www.aiib.org/en/projects/details/2022/_download/Turkiye/AIIB-PIMR_SBF_Turkiye_P000141_TKYB-Renewable-Energy-and-Energy-Efficiency-On-Lending-Facility_No-6_January_2023_Public-Version.pdf](https://www.aiib.org/en/projects/details/2022/_download/Turkiye/AIIB-PIMR_SBF_Turkiye_P000141_TKYB-Renewable-Energy-and-Energy-Efficiency-On-Lending-Facility_No-6_January_2023_Public-Version.pdf)

¹⁵⁵ YEKA Model and Its Practices - Republic of Turkey Ministry of Energy and Natural Resources

installed capacity in RE by allocating large-scale land areas for RE plants. The main focus is on solar, wind, and hydroelectric energy. YEKA aims to install 10,000 MW of RE capacities by 2030, with a significant portion dedicated to wind and solar energy.

- Türkiye SME Energy Efficiency Project (SME-EE), funded by the Global Environment Facility (GEF): It supports SMEs to adopt energy-efficient technologies and practices that will help them reduce energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions. The project aims to enhance the awareness and technical capacity of SMEs regarding energy efficiency, making them more capable of implementing energy-saving solutions. It focuses on promoting the adoption of energy-efficient technologies in SMEs.
- Gümüşköy Geothermal Power Plant represents a pioneering case where the private sector financed exploration in an unproven field in Türkiye that include: private investment of approximately USD 12 million in early-stage exploration and development; public support in the form of a ten-year feed-in tariff from the government ensure financial viability, and debt financing up to USD 34.5 million from a local commercial bank, that facilitated project completion¹⁵⁶.

These initiatives demonstrate Türkiye's commitment to fostering stakeholder motivation in local energy flexibility markets through diverse and innovative financing mechanisms. In addition, Türkiye will invest USD 20 billion in energy efficiency schemes in the public and private sectors by 2030, that will decrease the energy consumption by 16% and contribute to 100 million tons of emission reduction by 2030.

¹⁵⁶ P. Oliver, M. Stadelmann: Public Finance and Private Exploration in Geothermal: Gümüşköy Case Study, Turkey. Climate Policy Initiative, 2015

4.6.4. Awareness & Actions to Ensure High Customer Participation in the LFM

To capitalize on the prospects offered by diverse and accessible RES, it is crucial to involve various stakeholders such as public sector officials, energy sector organizations, private companies, educational institutions, and civil society in efforts to achieve Türkiye's energy transition objectives and strategies. Additionally, having a platform that can promote discussions and serve as a think tank focused on energy policy, research, and technical analysis would be efficient and beneficial.

The documents outlining policies and strategies related to energy transition are subjected to extensive outreach campaigns to assess various viewpoints and to engage with representatives from the public sector, private companies, non-governmental organizations, and academic institutions, as the execution of these policies involves numerous stakeholders. In this framework, workshops and meetings focused on diverse subjects (such as buildings, energy, municipal services, heating and cooling, industry, transportation, energy management, and financing) are conducted, allowing for broad stakeholder participation. During these events, collaborative actions and recommendations can be discussed, and objectives, goals, and actions can be defined while considering Türkiye's developmental priorities, energy strategies, technological capabilities, and socio-cultural advancements.¹⁵⁷

Increasing customer participation in LFM in Türkiye is essential for their success and a well-structured approach combining awareness-building and action steps to enhance engagement has to be applied as follows:

Awareness: Educating and Informing Customers

- Many customers, both residential and industrial, may not be familiar with LFM. Awareness campaigns focused on what LFM are; financial incentives such as lower energy bills, potential incentives from grid operators, participation in DR programs, reliability & sustainability; regulatory support, communicating government policies and potential subsidies that encourage participation.
- Targeted Awareness Channels. To maximize outreach, a mix of online and offline strategies can be used like workshops and seminars for collaborating with utilities, regulators, and industry groups; digital campaigns on social media, targeted emails, and mobile apps from energy providers; traditional media by radio, newspapers, and television campaigns; community engagement – partnering with local municipalities and universities.

¹⁵⁷ [Energy Efficiency 2030 Strategy and 2nd National Energy Efficiency Action Plan 2024-2030](#)

- Customer Segmentation for Effective Messaging for Industrial & Commercial Users to focus on cost savings, energy efficiency, and sustainability goals; Residential Consumers highlighting smart home integration, rewards programs, and ease of participation; Prosumers (Solar/Battery Owners) emphasizing additional revenue streams by selling excess energy or providing grid services.

Actions: Strategies to Increase Participation

- Simplified Onboarding & Participation by User-Friendly Platforms that ensure enrolling in an LFM is as simple as using a mobile app; Automation & Aggregators enabling third-party aggregators to manage participation for customers; Smart Meters & IoT Integration deploy real-time monitoring tools to automate DR actions.
- Financial & Regulatory Incentives like Dynamic Pricing Models implement time-of-use tariffs and real-time pricing to reward flexibility; Subsidies & Grants that are government-backed incentives for installing smart energy management systems; Contractual Flexibility in the form of short-term contracts or trial participation to reduce customer hesitation.
- Collaboration with Key Stakeholders like utilities & DSOs to ensure energy distributors actively promote LFMs and support integration; Technology Providers working with IoT and AI-based energy management companies to simplify participation; Government & Regulators to advocate for clear policies, legal frameworks, and consumer protections.
- Gamification & Engagement Strategies by Loyalty Programs to reward customers with points, discounts, or credits for participation; Leader-boards & Challenges to recognize top participants in energy-saving competitions; Educational Apps & Simulations to help customers visualize their energy savings and rewards.

Monitoring & Continuous Improvement

- Regular Surveys & Feedback Loops – to understand customer pain points and refine engagement strategies.
- Performance Analytics - to use AI-driven insights to optimize participation incentives.
- Policy Adjustments - to work with regulators to adapt policies based on real-world participation trends.

Encouraging high customer participation in LFMs in Türkiye requires raising awareness, simplifying processes, offering financial incentives, and leveraging technology. A collaborative effort involving regulators, energy providers, and technology firms can ensure a well-functioning market that benefits both the grid and consumers.

4.6.5. Strategic Planning Documents

Türkiye National Energy Plan¹⁵⁸ published in 2022 defines the aims of the country to reach in 2035 compared to 2021 the following: to increase its solar energy capacity more than fivefold to reach 52.9 GW; wind capacity to increase nearly threefold to reach 29.6 GW, while hydro capacity to rise to 35.1 GW. Nuclear capacity, which Türkiye considers as renewable in the energy plan, is expected to reach 7.2 GW in 2035.

Figure 4: New Installed Capacity Commissioned in Five-Year Periods in Türkiye

The new capacity that needs to be put into operation in the 2021–2035 periods is 96.9 GW (See Figure 4).

The plan indicates that new capacity amounting to 21.6 GW needs to be put into operation in 2021–2025, 34.3 GW in 2026–2030 and 41.0 GW in 2031–2035. Of this installed capacity increase, 74.3% should come from RES, most notably solar and wind power and it will make up 64.7% of Türkiye's total installed capacity by 2035 (54% in 2021).

The Roadmap for 2035 in renewable energy envisages capacity increase in wind and solar energy from 30 GW at present, to 120 GW, which counts for investments of USD 108 billion¹⁵⁹.

The 1st National Energy Efficiency Action Plan 2017-2023 (NEEAP) put forward concrete steps about how to improve and create a market for energy efficiency. The auctions for RES-zones and the tenders for pre-licensing show that renewable energy-based electricity generation has a strong cost advantage.

¹⁵⁸ Türkiye_National_Energy_Plan.pdf

¹⁵⁹ <https://enerji.gov.tr/news-detail?id=21410>

The Energy Efficiency 2030 Strategy and 2nd National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (2024 - 2030)¹⁶⁰

The Energy Efficiency 2030 Strategy outlines 10 strategic goals and 23 objectives and the 2nd NEEAP aims to achieve these goals, defining 61 actions and 266 activities divided into seven categories: industry and technology, buildings and services, energy, transportation, agriculture, horizontal topics, start-ups, and digitization. For their implementation an energy efficiency investment of USD 20.2 billion will be needed in the period 2024-2030 to achieve a cumulative final energy saving of 37.1 MTOE. With the realisation of this target, which corresponds to a 16% reduction in Türkiye's primary energy consumption in that period, 100 million tons of CO₂ eq. greenhouse gas reduction will be achieved.

Actions to be carried out in the energy sector:

- Establish an effectively functioning heat market within the framework of energy transition goals
- Implementation of efficiency standards for natural gas infrastructure
- Encourage energy efficiency through billing information and tariffs
- Dissemination of smart meters
- Increase energy efficiency in general lighting
- Increase energy efficiency in electricity transmission and distribution activities
- Increase efficiency in electricity generation power plants
- Create market infrastructure for demand side participation and aggregator
- Measures to develop hydrogen technology in compatibility with national energy goals

In order to achieve these targets, Türkiye will direct public financial resources to energy efficiency-oriented investments, improvement programs and incentive practices, taking into account the cost-benefit balance. Non-public financial institutions will also contribute in energy efficiency financing and foreign/international financial resources will be mobilised.

¹⁶⁰ [Energy Efficiency 2030 Strategy and 2nd National Energy Efficiency Action Plan 2024-2030](#)

4.6.6. Policy Guidelines for Facilitating Deployment of LFM and Exploitation of Flexibility

Developing LFM in Türkiye by 2030 requires a comprehensive approach involving regulatory, technological, market, and stakeholder engagement strategies. Key recommendations include:

- **Regulatory & Policy Framework**

Develop a Clear LFM Regulatory Framework: Establish a dedicated legal and regulatory structure for LFM under the Energy Market Regulatory Authority (EPDK). Define clear market rules and roles for participants (DSOs, aggregators, consumers, and generators).

Grid Code Updates: Define technical requirements for DERs, storage, and demand-side response (DSR) to participate in LFM.

Standardized Market Rules: Ensure interoperability between Türkiye's national electricity market and LFM with clear pricing, settlement, and dispute resolution mechanisms.

Incentives & Tariffs: Introduce dynamic pricing models, time-of-use tariffs, and locational incentives to encourage flexibility providers.

- **Market Structure & Mechanisms**

Decentralized Market Platforms: Establish independent or integrated local trading platforms for FS, supported by Türkiye Elektrik İletim A.Ş. (TEİAŞ) and DSOs.

Market Participation Models: Encourage participation from prosumers, renewable generators, energy storage operators, industrial consumers, and aggregators.

Locational Flexibility Pricing: Implement zonal or nodal pricing to reflect local grid constraints and encourage local balancing.

Flexibility Procurement Mechanisms: Introduce long-term contracts, day-ahead flexibility auctions, and real-time flexibility trading.

- **Digitalization & Infrastructure**

Smart Grid Deployment: Accelerate smart meter and advanced distribution management system (ADMS) rollout to enable accurate monitoring and control. Invest in advanced metering infrastructure for real-time DR.

Blockchain and AI for Trading: Use blockchain for secure transactions and AI-based forecasting to optimize flexibility trading. Türkiye can develop AI-powered local grid control systems.

Cybersecurity & Data Privacy: Establish strong cybersecurity measures and data-sharing regulations to protect market participants.

- ***Develop Demand Response Programs***

Encourage commercial and industrial consumers to offer flexibility via load shifting. Provide financial incentives for residential participation in DR. Allow aggregators to pool small-scale flexibility sources. Türkiye can create a national VPP program to engage households and businesses.

- ***Promote DERs and Storage***

Support battery energy storage systems (BESS) for local grid stability. Encourage peer-to-peer (P2P) energy trading for solar prosumers. Implement time-of-use (ToU) pricing to optimize DER utilization. Türkiye can enable local solar and battery owners to trade surplus energy.

- ***Encourage Electric Vehicle (EV) Integration***

Implement Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) technology to use EVs as flexibility assets. Provide incentives for EV charging stations to participate in LFM. Develop smart charging hubs linked to local grids.

- ***Stakeholder Engagement & Capacity Building***

Pilot Projects and Sandboxes: Launch regulatory sandboxes and LFM pilot projects in cities like Istanbul, Ankara, and Izmir with high DER penetration. Partner with universities, DSOs, and startups for testing new flexibility models. Develop hybrid energy communities integrating solar, wind, and EVs.

Capacity Building Programs: Train utilities, regulators, and energy service companies on flexibility market operations.

Public Awareness Campaigns: Educate consumers on demand-side flexibility participation and potential cost savings.

- ***Integration with National Energy Goals***

Support Renewable Integration: LFMs should prioritize balancing solar and wind power fluctuations to support Türkiye's 2053 Net Zero Emissions Target.

Align with Türkiye's Green Hydrogen & Storage Strategy: Encourage hydrogen electrolysis and battery storage participation in LFM.

Grid Congestion Management: Use LFMs to optimize congestion relief, reducing investment needs in traditional grid reinforcements.

By 2030, Türkiye can develop a mature LFM ecosystem through regulatory reform, technology adoption, and strategic pilots. Starting with smart grid investments, demand response programs, and regional trials, Türkiye can unlock the full potential of local energy flexibility.

4.6.7. Findings as a Result of the Pilots Implementation in Türkiye

The pilot implementations carried out in Türkiye have provided significant findings regarding the regulatory, financial, administrative, and technical barriers delaying the development of Energy Communities (ECs) and Local Flexibility Markets (LFMs).

The existing legal framework is not fully aligned with EU directives (RED II, ED 2019), making it difficult to establish and operate energy communities in Türkiye. In particular, the lack of a clear legal definition for energy communities in Türkiye's electricity market regulations limits their ability to operate beyond energy cooperatives.

Additionally, flexibility markets are not explicitly defined in current regulations, preventing demand-side response (DSR), aggregators, and storage operators from effectively participating in the energy market. While the Unlicensed Electricity Generation Regulation supports self-consumption, it significantly restricts collective energy generation among multiple participants, thereby limiting energy-sharing opportunities.

In addition to regulatory constraints, administrative and bureaucratic obstacles pose significant challenges to the development of energy communities and local flexibility markets. In Türkiye, the implementation of energy projects requires approval from multiple institutions, including the Energy Market Regulatory Authority (EMRA), Turkish Electricity Distribution Corporation (TEDAŞ), and Distribution System Operators (DSOs), leading to prolonged permitting processes. Moreover, a lack of transparency in grid connection approvals and uncertainties regarding interconnection requirements cause delays in project implementation. The role of aggregators is not explicitly defined in Türkiye, creating significant uncertainty in demand-side flexibility participation and virtual power plant (VPP) operations.

Furthermore, the absence of a structured collaboration process between DSOs and TSOs creates significant barriers for energy communities seeking grid access, while the lack of data-

sharing mechanisms complicates the management of demand-side flexibility. Additionally, the unclear permitting requirements for energy storage systems hinder investors and pilot participants from adopting battery integration and other technological solutions.

From a financial perspective, the lack of specialized financial support mechanisms for energy communities and LFM projects discourages investors. There are no dedicated incentives, tax reductions, or funds in Türkiye for these initiatives, and high capital investment requirements for smart grid infrastructure, storage systems, and metering technologies further restrict the development of local flexibility markets. Furthermore, the absence of established market incentives for flexibility services (e.g., dynamic pricing, time-of-use tariffs, compensation for grid services) hinders economic sustainability and limits the growth of initiatives in this field.

Another critical barrier in this process is a lack of awareness. Consumers and local stakeholders do not have sufficient knowledge about the benefits of energy communities and flexibility markets. The limited scope of current awareness campaigns reduces interest in such initiatives. The absence of effective engagement strategies to encourage consumer participation in demand-side flexibility initiatives prevents the market from developing adequately. Additionally, many individuals and businesses remain hesitant to participate in energy cooperatives due to a lack of trust and concerns about financial risks.

From a technical perspective, the insufficient deployment of smart meters in Türkiye restricts real-time energy management and the implementation of flexibility trading. This limitation prevents the efficient operation of grid balancing mechanisms, which are crucial for the development of flexibility markets. Additionally, grid congestion in certain regions restricts the integration of a high share of distributed renewable energy, making it more difficult for local energy production projects to expand. Furthermore, interoperability issues between different digital platforms and energy management systems hinder the efficient operation of local flexibility services.

The pilot implementations have identified key barriers preventing the full-scale deployment of Energy Communities and Local Flexibility Markets in Türkiye. To overcome these obstacles, several critical steps must be taken. First, regulatory reforms should be introduced to legally recognize energy communities and flexibility markets. Additionally, simplifying administrative procedures and expediting grid access and investment approvals would accelerate the implementation of projects. To ensure the sustainability of flexibility markets, it is essential to introduce feed-in tariffs, dynamic pricing models, and investment grants as financial support mechanisms. Strengthening cooperation between DSOs, TSOs, and energy communities and enhancing market integration would further establish a more effective system. To encourage consumer participation in flexibility services, expanding awareness-raising educational

programs would contribute to the broader acceptance of local energy projects within society. Finally, investing in smart grid infrastructure and digital energy management platforms would accelerate Türkiye's transition to a more flexible, renewable-based, and consumer-driven energy market.

4.7. France

Renewable energies in France have enjoyed significant growth, mainly because of the development of biofuels, biomass, wind power and solar energy in the last decades. Renewable energies are the third main source of primary energy in France, with a share of 15.4% of the energy mix in 2023. Primary production of renewable energies has almost doubled since 2005, thanks to strong growth in wind power, PVs, heat pumps and biogas. France aims to boost the share of renewable energy to at least 33% of total energy consumption and 40% of electricity production by 2030 compared to 1990 and these targets are set out by law.

The government set out specific near-term targets under the 10-year energy investment plans (programmation pluriannuelle de l'énergie or PPE¹⁶¹) enacted in 2020.

France, like all other EU member states, is heavily reliant on fossil fuels, which accounted for almost half of its primary energy consumption¹⁶² in 2023, with oil accounting for 30 %, natural gas for 13 % and coal playing a minor role. Nuclear energy accounted for about 40 %, renewables for 16 %. Primary production of renewable electricity has increased by 27.4%, due to a significant increase in installed capacity and favourable weather conditions. In 2023, wind and solar installations represented 14.6% of the French electricity mix. Wind power became the third-largest generator, behind nuclear and hydro power but ahead of gas. Wind and solar power thus contribute to balancing electricity supply and demand, including at times of peak consumption¹⁶³. With around 2/3 of France's electricity being produced by nuclear power, the emissions intensity of the country's energy sector is lower than those of some other European countries. There are discussions ongoing in the French government that the country needs to build more than 14 new nuclear plants – compared to the six planned so far.

In September 2023, the government unveiled its ecological planning strategy with a view to reducing the country's emissions based on sufficiency, energy efficiency measures, and the deployment of nuclear and renewable energy. That includes an increase of annual public funding from the national budget to finance the transition, and the pledge to end coal power by 2027.

¹⁶¹ PNACC 3 | Centre de ressources pour l'adaptation au changement climatique

¹⁶² France's energy balance in 2023 - Provisional data | Data and statistical studies

¹⁶³ <https://cms.law/en/int/expert-guides/cms-expert-guide-to-renewable-energy/france>

The roadmaps which constitute France’s future energy and climate strategy – that is its low-carbon national strategy (SNBC)¹⁶⁴, the PPE 2024-2035, the new planning law (LPEC)¹⁶⁵ and the country’s adaptation plan to climate change (PNACC)¹⁶⁶ are to be finalised, the national low-carbon strategy - updated. The EU energy commissioner urged France in February 2024 to “significantly raise its ambition on RES to at least 44 %” regarding gross final energy consumption by 2030 and specify clear targets in its National Climate and Energy Plan (See Figure 5).

Source: DIW Weekly Report

Figure 5: Share of renewable energy in gross final energy consumption in France (in %)

4.7.1. State-of-the-art of LFM and FS, transposition of EU regulation

The development of RES introduced an increasing need for FS in the French electricity market. In 2010, the new organisation of the electricity market (Law NOME 2010/1488) recognised the benefits of load shedding for balancing the transmission network and ensuring its security.¹⁶⁷

After the adoption, in 2019, of the Clean Energy for all Europeans package, signals for better investment and more flexibility have been put in place. The transposition of both European Directives IEMD 2019/944 and RED II 2018/2001 through the Ordinance 2021-236¹⁶⁸ has put

¹⁶⁴ National Low-Carbon Strategy (SNBC) - Climate Change Laws of the World

¹⁶⁵ The Energy and Climate Planning Act (EPCL) | Planning tools

¹⁶⁶ Présentation du plan national d'adaptation au changement climatique

¹⁶⁷ Smartgrids – CRE – Regulatory framework for Demand-side management

¹⁶⁸ Ordinance 2021-236 on Directives (EU) IEMD 2019/944 & RED II 2018/2001 Transposition

consumers at the centre of the electricity market by allowing them to have a more active role in the production of energy as well as have a better control of their consumption and expenses. France has implemented a framework called NEBEF¹⁶⁹ that ensures independent aggregators access to the wholesale markets. This system enables consumers to be compensated for reducing their electricity usage during specific periods, contributing to energy flexibility. To participate in NEBEF, a site of a minimum of 100 kW capacity or an aggregator must obtain certification from RTE, then, can sign contracts with customers to form a demand response group. Customers don't need their electricity supplier's approval to join a DR group and even sites without a smart meter can participate. The aggregator can then submit bids to reduce energy use during peak times on the EPEX Spot power market. At present only bids to reduce demand are accepted as RTE is currently revising its market rules to allow downward bid (i.e. increasing consumption corresponding to load shifting). After that, the aggregator submits a demand reduction schedule to RTE, specifying the overall energy reduction and RTE verifies the energy reduction by analysing data from the boundary meter. RTE is currently experimenting with verification with sub-metering through pilot. Finally, a financial transaction occurs between the aggregator and the electricity supplier in which the aggregator compensates the supplier for the energy not consumed and being transferred to the aggregator.

According to the type of the customer three models can be defined: the customer is either billed for the energy not consumed at the retail price (corrected model) or pays a financial compensation to the supplier, through a regulated price, set by the NRA (regulated model), or the aggregator agrees with the supplier on specific conditions.

To participate in NEBEF, a company must first be recognised as a DR operated by the RTE after completing several administrative steps that prove the operator's qualifications. In addition, the DR operator must either obtain the status of a Balance Responsible Party (BRP) or assign this responsibility to an existing BRP for the volume activated. RTE also requires the operator to provide collateral to cover the compensation owed to electricity suppliers.

French households are, at present, not able to subscribe to dynamic electricity contracts though the rollout of smart meters is almost finalised, no offers are available on the market. While dynamic contracts are permitted for residential customers, there are currently no such offers available in the market; end-users can only access peak/off-peak retail contracts. Commercial entities can only find hourly dynamic electricity contracts options available in the market. Once dynamic contracts are available to residential customers, households will easily be able to subscribe to these tariffs due to the extensive rollout of smart meters. As of 2023, 94% of

¹⁶⁹ [the_smarten_map_2024_DIGITAL-updated.pdf](#)

French households have smart meters installed, allowing for consumption data to be read every 30 minutes.

NEBEF is currently the only framework that allows a significant volume of DR to be activated by independent aggregators on wholesale markets in Europe. France is one of the EU countries with the highest activity of explicit DR in wholesale markets thanks to the implementation of the NEBEF framework and the regulatory framework ensuring DSF access to wholesale markets.

The French multi-annual energy plan (2019, review in 2023) sets a target for the development of DR capacity of 4.5 GW in 2023 and 6.5 GW in 2028. In the «Energy pathways to 2050» report¹⁷⁰ RTE (French TSO) estimates flexibility needs at 15 GW regardless of the energy mix scenario.¹⁷¹

The law No. 2023-175 of 10 March 2023 on accelerating the production of RE (APER Law) brought more clarity in the legal provisions governing electricity grid connection, and allows for better planning of grid connection works and greater flexibility in their construction.

4.7.2. Smart local flexibility services - compliance and safety

Compliance¹⁷²

France complies with non-discriminatory provisions for day-ahead and intraday markets. Free access to end-customer data by eligible parties, based on consumer's consent, is a major enabler of innovative services, and France has already set national rules requiring it.

The country is also compliant with the elimination of double network charges for active customers owning an energy storage facility. ToU tariffs are offered and tariffs based on spot and intraday prices are available. Time-differentiated network tariffs exist and the NRA has approved cost-reflective, transparent network charges considering the need for flexibility.

France has allowed DSOs to procure FS on a pilot basis, and also there are clear rules for the market-based procurement of ancillary services. Still a comprehensive framework foreseeing transparent, non-discriminatory and market-based procurement has to be developed.

As regards the long term, the TSOs in France have already fully considered the potential of using all DER as alternatives to system expansion in their 10-year network development plans. France has also ensured consistency between the long-term network development plans and the

¹⁷⁰ RTE – Energy Pathways to 2050 (2021)

¹⁷¹ D3.2: Regulatory Impact Analysis for Local Flexibility Markets and Services, DE-RISK project

¹⁷² FINAL_smartEn-EMD-implementation-monitoring-report.pdf

submitted National Energy and Climate Plans, following a fruitful cooperation between the relevant authorities and TSOs. It has introduced resource adequacy mechanisms and modified its existing capacity mechanism, to be compliant with EU rules.

France has already defined that the new smart metering systems should be interoperable with both energy management systems and smart grids to ensure full interoperability both behind and in front of the meter and dynamic tariffs covering both the electricity and network components are in place. France has implemented 94% smart meter coverage, managed by Enedis, the primary DSO. The Enedis DataHub provides API and XML web services for residential and commercial electricity data. Enedis has already deployed Linky smart meters, which allow for real-time monitoring and dynamic pricing—critical components for demand response programs and grid flexibility¹⁷³. Building on this, the Enedis DataHub provides API and XML web services to facilitate access to residential and commercial electricity data, enabling more efficient energy management and integration of smart grid solutions.

Safety

France has benefitted from decarbonised electricity based on clean nuclear power but is now expanding its efforts and enforcing its national decarbonisation plan (Ministry of Economy, France) that promotes RES. France has an extensive set of policies promoting systems flexibility and energy efficiency. It demonstrates notable effort on demand side management, digitalisation, and the renovation of buildings.

The development and implementation of the smart FS in the country is supported by a series of actions to ensure compliance with regulations and maintain safety standards. In this regard some key steps have been taken, as follows:

- Investments are being made in the modernization of the electricity grid infrastructure to accommodate advanced smart technologies. This includes upgrading transmission and distribution networks to enable two-way communication and real-time monitoring, both essential for effective smart flexibility solutions. According to RTE, an estimated €100 billion will be required by 2040 to fully modernize the grid.¹⁷⁴
- A *regulatory framework* for smart grids and energy management systems has been established that includes guidelines and standards for the integration of RES, DR mechanisms, and energy storage solutions. The French Energy Regulatory Commission (CRE) plays a crucial role in monitoring these regulations.

¹⁷³ [Théma - Réseaux électriques intelligents.pdf](#)

¹⁷⁴ [Reuters](#)

- Investments in the *electricity grid infrastructure* modernisation take place to accommodate smart technologies that include upgrading transmission and distribution networks to support two-way communication and real-time monitoring, essential for smart FS.
- France has implemented *DR programs* encouraging consumers to adjust their energy consumption patterns based on real-time pricing signals or incentives, thus to help balance supply and demand, reduce peak loads, and enhance grid stability.
- To improve grid flexibility, the promotion of various *energy storage technologies* such as batteries, pumped hydro storage, and thermal storage has taken place, which ensure a more stable and efficient energy system.
- *Interoperability standards* are under development to ensure that different devices and systems within the smart grid can communicate effectively. This includes standardizing protocols for data exchange, cybersecurity measures, and operational procedures with contribution from standardization bodies such as AFNOR (Association française de Normalisation / French Association for Standardization) and CENELEC (European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization).
- France has implemented *DR programs* encouraging consumers to adjust their energy consumption patterns based on real-time pricing signals or incentives, thus to help balance supply and demand, reduce peak loads, and enhance grid stability. One example of such initiatives is *Mon Programme pour Agir* (My Action Program) by ENGIE, launched in 2023. This program rewards customers for managing their energy consumption by allowing them to accumulate points called “KiloActs” for reducing their consumption. These points can be then exchanged for products that promote the energy transition or items that aid in better energy management¹⁷⁵.
- Given the increased reliance on digital technologies in smart grids, the *cybersecurity* has been prioritized to protect critical infrastructure from cyber threats implementing robust security protocols, regular audits, and collaboration with industry stakeholders to address vulnerabilities. In line with this, the European Union Agency for Cyber Security (ENISA) has outlined key security measures for smart grids, emphasizing the need for risk management frameworks, encryption, and access control to ensure the integrity and confidentiality of grid data.

Through these measures, France aims to create a resilient, efficient, and sustainable energy system capable of meeting the growing demands of the future while ensuring compliance with safety and regulatory standards.

¹⁷⁵ [Mon Programme pour Agir récompense les clients qui consomment moins et mieux !](#)

4.7.3. Business models and financing mechanisms to boost stakeholder motivation

In France, several business models have emerged for LFM, aimed at optimizing energy usage, reducing costs, and supporting the integration of RES. Here are some key business models that are being developed and implemented:

Business models

- *Demand Response Aggregation*: Aggregators pool together the flexible capacity of multiple consumers (e.g., households, businesses) to provide DR services to the grid. Consumers agree to adjust their energy consumption based on price signals or incentives provided by the aggregator and in return, they receive compensation for their flexibility. This model reduces peak demand, improves grid stability, and provides additional revenue for consumers. In France there are two aggregation models (one applicable to customers connected to low voltage and other one applicable to medium and high voltage customers. France is the only Member State in Europe, which has opened both the ancillary services markets and wholesale market to DR and independent aggregators. This is made possible because the relationship between aggregators and retailers/BRPs has been regulated in 2013 and a standardised framework is put in place.¹⁷⁶
- *Virtual Power Plants (VPPs)*¹⁷⁷ aggregate DERs such as solar panels, wind turbines, batteries, and controllable loads into a single entity that can be managed and dispatched as if it were a traditional power plant. DER owners connect their assets to a central platform based on market conditions and grid needs. VPPs enhance grid flexibility, enable better integration of renewables, and provide additional income opportunities for asset owners.
- *Peer-to-Peer (P2P) Trading Platforms*¹⁷⁸ allow consumers and producers to trade energy directly with each other without going through a centralized utility. Participants buy and sell energy via a blockchain-based platform, often using smart contracts to automate transactions. It enables localized energy trading, reduces transmission losses, and empowers consumers to become active participants in the energy market.
- *Energy Service Companies (ESCOs)* ¹⁷⁹offer energy efficiency and demand management services to consumers, helping them optimize their energy usage and reduce costs; ESCOs conduct energy audits, implement energy-saving measures, and manage energy

¹⁷⁶ <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/bitstream/JRC101191/Idna27998enn.pdf>

¹⁷⁷ <https://www.cognitivemarketresearch.com/virtual-power-plant-vpp-market-report>

¹⁷⁸ <https://smartlendinghub.com/best-p2p-lending-platforms-in-france/>

¹⁷⁹ Summary of basic data of the French ESCO market | Download Table

procurement on behalf of clients, often operate under performance-based contracts where they guarantee savings.

- *Microgrids* are small-scale, localized energy systems¹⁸⁰ that can operate independently or in parallel with the main grid; they integrate local generation, storage, and load management capabilities to provide reliable and efficient energy services to a specific area. Their benefit is that they increase resilience, reduce dependence on the main grid, and enable better integration of RES.
- *Dynamic Pricing* adjusts electricity prices based on real-time supply and demand conditions. Prices fluctuate based on factors such as time of day, weather conditions, and overall grid load. Consumers can respond by adjusting their energy usage to take advantage of lower prices. The Dynamic Pricing Mechanism encourages energy conservation, reduces peak demand, and aligns consumer behaviour with grid needs. France applies time-of-use network tariffs to more than 80% of households¹⁸¹.
- *Community Energy Projects*¹⁸² involve groups of individuals or organizations coming together to develop and manage shared energy resources by investing in and own renewable energy installations, and share the benefits among members. Thus it promotes community engagement, increases local ownership of energy production, and supports sustainable development.
- *Battery Storage Services*¹⁸³ are used to store excess energy generated during periods of low demand and release it when demand is high. Batteries can be charged when energy prices are low and discharged when prices are high, providing both cost savings and grid stabilization services. They support grid flexibility, reduce curtailment of renewable energy, and provide backup power during outages.

These business models are designed to enhance the flexibility and resilience of the energy system, enabling better integration of RES, improving grid stability, and providing economic benefits to participants. As technology continues to evolve and regulatory frameworks adapt, these models will likely continue to diversify and expand.

Financing mechanisms

To boost stakeholder motivation for FS in France, various financing mechanisms have been developed and implemented. These mechanisms aim to incentivize participation, reduce financial barriers, and promote investment in innovative energy solutions. Here are some key financing mechanisms that are being utilized:

¹⁸⁰ Europe Grid Connected Microgrid Market Size, 2024-2032 Report

¹⁸¹ ACER MMR 2023: Barriers to demand response

¹⁸² Energy communities reach combined capacity of 74 MW in France - Your Source for Clean Energy News & Trends

¹⁸³ France: main energy storage projects' capacity 2024 | Statista

- Feed-in Tariffs (FiTs)¹⁸⁴ provide guaranteed payments to producers of renewable energy for every unit of electricity they feed into the grid. Producers receive a fixed price per kilowatt-hour (kWh) for a specified period, typically over 20 years. This ensures a stable revenue stream and encourages investment in renewable energy projects and provides long-term financial certainty. The feed-in tariffs are gradually replaced with premium fees; it is only maintained for small-capacity renewable plants.
- *Power Purchase Agreements (PPAs)* are contracts between an energy producer and a buyer specifying the terms of electricity purchase over a set period and can be tailored to include FS. The start of corporate PPAs in France was relatively late with the signing of the first PPA in May 2019 due to the uncertainty of long-term contracts. To address this, the French government introduced a guarantee fund in November 2022 to encourage long-term renewable energy PPA signings.¹⁸⁵
- *Grants and Subsidies* are financial support provided by governments or public institutions to support the development of FS allocated to cover part or all of the initial investment costs, making projects more financially viable. They reduce upfront capital requirements, accelerate project implementation, and promote innovation.
- *Green Bonds* diversify funding sources; they are debt instruments specifically issued to finance environmentally friendly projects, including those related to FS. Investors purchase green bonds, the proceeds are used to fund eligible projects, and bondholders receive interest payments until maturity. The French government is the largest green bond issuer in France, it is not the only player in the green bonds market, French banks have an important role in the issuance of green bonds. The strong involvement of the French government and banks in the issuance of green bonds makes France one of the leaders in the global green bond market.¹⁸⁶
- *Crowdfunding* allows individuals and organizations to contribute small amounts of money towards a larger project, often in exchange for equity or rewards. Once the target amount is reached, the project proceeds. This financing instrument engages the community, democratizes access to financing, and builds social capital. France is one of the biggest crowdfunding markets, offering a wide variety of investments¹⁸⁷.
- *Revolving Funds* are pools of money that are continuously replenished as loans are repaid, allowing for ongoing investment in new projects. Initial capital is used to make loans for energy efficiency or renewable energy projects. As loans are repaid, the funds

¹⁸⁴ Solar PV feed-in tariffs France 2024 | Statista

¹⁸⁵ Corporate Power Purchase Agreement (PPA) in Europe - Blog de l'ISIGE - MINES Paris

¹⁸⁶ Outstanding volume of the French green OAT 2024 | Statista

¹⁸⁷ The easiest way to invest in renewable energy projects starting with a few 100 euros! - Crowdinform

are reused for new investments. This is a self-sustaining source of financing; it leverages limited resources, and supports multiple projects over time.

- *Tax Incentives and Tax Credits* reduce the tax burden for individuals and businesses that invest in energy efficiency or renewable energy projects. Eligible expenses can be deducted from taxable income, lowering the effective cost of investment. For example, on 30 December 2023, the Government of France published Law 2023-1322 of 29 December 2023 on finances for 2024, which introduced a tax credit for investments in the production of batteries, solar panels, wind turbines, and heat pumps. The tax credit, ranging from 20 to 60 % depended on the size of the company and the location of the investments¹⁸⁸.
- *Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs)*¹⁸⁹ involve collaboration between public authorities and private entities to jointly develop and finance infrastructure projects. Public and private partners share risks and responsibilities, leveraging the strengths of both sectors. PPPs combine public resources with private expertise, accelerate project delivery, and ensure long-term viability.
- *European Union Funding*: The EU provides grants and loans through various programs to support projects aligned with EU priorities, such as renewable energy and energy efficiency, ensuring access to significant financial resources, thus supporting regional cooperation, and aligning national policies with EU goals.

By utilizing these diverse financing mechanisms, France aims to create a supportive environment for FS, attracting investment, fostering innovation, and accelerating the transition to a more sustainable and resilient energy system.

4.7.4. Awareness & actions to ensure high customer participation in the LFM

The high customer participation in LFMs in France has been ensured by a combination of awareness campaigns, targeted actions, and policy support. The used strategies to increase customer engagement and participation include: *Educational Campaigns* to inform consumers about the benefits of participating in LFMs by various channels such as social media, television, radio, and print media to disseminate information, as well as to organize workshops, webinars, and community meetings to educate consumers about LFMs.

¹⁸⁸ France - Introduces tax credits for investments in green energy projects | Investment Policy Monitor | UNCTAD Investment Policy Hub

¹⁸⁹ <https://www.lexology.com/library/detail.aspx?g=71d0142a-c112-4b55-8bf4-f68d0773b371>

Supportive policies and regulations that are implemented facilitate customer participation as simplification of permitting processes for installing energy storage systems and RES and establishing clear rules and guidelines for LFM to provide legal certainty.

The existing *financial incentives* encourage customer participation in the form of rebates, discounts, or tax credits for consumers who install smart meters, energy storage systems, or other technologies that all enable participation in LFMs.

The *Smart Meter Rollout* that provides real-time data on energy consumption helps educate consumers on how to use smart meter data to optimize their energy usage and participate in LFMs.

User-Friendly Platforms and mobile apps that have been developed make it easy for consumers to engage with LFMs, and allow consumers to monitor their energy usage, set preferences, and participate in DR programs.

Energy Communities actions and peer-to-peer learning also ensure high customer participation in the LFMs. They engage people by organizing community events, competitions, and challenges to encourage collective action; share success stories and testimonials from early adopters to inspire others.

Other actions that contribute to raising customers awareness on LFMs include *collaboration with the utilities* to promote LFMs and provide customer support, building trust by ensuring transparency in LFM operations and pricing, as well as *targeted marketing* to specific customer segments based on their interests and needs to understand customer motivations and barriers.

Customer Support and Assistance that include setting up helplines, online chat services, and email support to answer customer questions and resolve issues promptly; offering personalized assistance to guide customers through the process of participating in LFMs.

By implementing these strategies, France raises awareness, builds trust, and encourages high levels of customer participation in LFMs, ultimately contributing to a more resilient and sustainable energy system.

Here are some examples of successful initiatives and programs in France that have boosted customer participation in LFMs:

- Électricité de France (EDF) Demand Response Program¹⁹⁰.

¹⁹⁰ Saving energy with demand response | Environmental Defense Fund

- Engie's "My Energy" Platform¹⁹¹ allows customers to monitor their energy consumption in real-time, set alerts, and participate in demand response programs.
- TotalEnergies' Solar Panels and Battery Storage Solutions¹⁹²: TotalEnergies, a multinational energy company, offers integrated solar panel and battery storage solutions to residential and commercial customers. These systems enable customers to generate and store their own electricity, reducing reliance on the grid and participating in LFM. Customers benefit from reduced energy bills, increased energy independence, and the ability to sell excess energy back to the grid, thereby increasing their participation in LFM.
- Schneider Electric's EcoStruxure Platform¹⁹³ provides smart home and building solutions that integrate energy management, automation, and IoT connectivity. This platform helps customers optimize their energy usage and participate in demand response programs.
- Enedis' Linky Smart Meters¹⁹⁴: Enedis, the French electricity distribution network operator, has rolled out millions of Linky smart meters across the country that provides real-time data on energy consumption and enables dynamic pricing and demand response programs. With accurate and timely information, customers can better manage their energy usage, participate in demand response programs, and contribute to grid flexibility.
- ADEME's Energy Efficiency Programs¹⁹⁵: The French Environment and Energy Management Agency (ADEME) runs various programs to promote energy efficiency and renewable energy adoption. These programs include grants, subsidies, and technical assistance for homeowners and businesses. By providing financial incentives and expert guidance, ADEME encourages customers to invest in energy-efficient technologies and participate in LFM.
- Several local communities in France have launched cooperative energy projects, where residents collectively invest in renewable energy installations and share the benefits. These projects often include elements of DR and energy sharing. Bégawatts, a citizen-led cooperative in Béganne, Brittany, funded a community wind farm project, allowing local residents to invest in renewable energy and share the profits from the electricity produced.

¹⁹¹<https://mypower.engie.fr/espace-client-my-power.html>

¹⁹² <https://totalenergies.com/company/projects/electricity/battery-based-energy-storage-our-projects-and-achievements>

¹⁹³ <https://www.se.com/ww/en/work/campaign/innovation/platform.jsp>

¹⁹⁴ <https://www.enedis.fr/media/2208/download>

¹⁹⁵ <https://www.ademe.fr/en/ademe-the-french-ecological-transition-agency/>

- EcoWatt App¹⁹⁶, developed by Réseau de Transport d'Électricité (RTE), provides real-time information on electricity consumption and carbon intensity across France. Users can see when demand is high and choose to shift their energy usage accordingly. By raising awareness about the impact of energy consumption on the grid, the EcoWatt app encourages users to modify their behaviour and participate in demand response programs.
- Electricité de Strasbourg's Virtual Power Plant (VPP) aggregates the capacity of electric vehicles, solar panels, and battery storage systems to provide grid services. Customers who participate in the VPP can earn financial incentives. By integrating DER into a coordinated system, Electricité de Strasbourg demonstrates the potential of VPPs to enhance grid flexibility and customer participation.
- Peer-to-Peer Trading Platforms allow customers to buy and sell energy directly with each other. Some use blockchain technology to ensure secure and transparent transactions. By enabling localized energy trading, P2P platforms empower customers to become active participants in the energy market, contributing to grid flexibility and sustainability.

These examples highlight the diverse approaches being taken in France to boost customer participation in LFM, ranging from technological innovations to community-driven initiatives and supportive policy frameworks.

4.7.5. Strategic Planning Documents

*National Energy Climate - Plan (Updated June 2024)*¹⁹⁷

The National Energy and Climate (ENCP) Plan is a ten-year integrated document mandated by the EU addressing all five dimensions of the Energy Union: decarbonisation, energy efficiency, energy security, internal energy markets and research, innovation and competitiveness, in order for the EU to meet its overall greenhouse gases emissions targets (See Table 9). The plan is based on the following national energy and climate programming and governance documents:

- The Multi-Year Energy Program, which sets the priorities for actions of the public authorities in the field of energy for the next 10 years, divided into two 5-year periods. It deals with all energies and all the pillars of energy policy: control of energy demand, promotion of renewable energies, guarantee of security of supply, control of energy costs, balanced development of networks, etc.

¹⁹⁶ <https://www.rte-france.com/actualites/application-mobile-ecowatt>

¹⁹⁷ https://commission.europa.eu/energy-climate-change-environment/implementation-eu-countries/energy-and-climate-governance-and-reporting/national-energy-and-climate-plans_en

- The National Low-Carbon Strategy, which is France's roadmap for leading the climate change mitigation policy. It provides guidelines for implementing the transition to a low-carbon economy in all sectors of activity. It defines objectives for reducing greenhouse gas emissions at the scale of France in the short and medium term - carbon budgets - and aims to achieve carbon neutrality by 2050.
- The National Plan for Adaptation to Climate Change (PNACC) aims to protect citizens and prepare territories, the economy and the environment for the impacts of climate change. It is based for the first time on a reference warming trajectory of 2 °C in 2030, 2.7 °C in 2050 and 4 °C in 2100 in hexagonal France compared to the pre-industrial era. This trajectory, which corresponds to the trend scenario according to the IPCC, is intended to serve as a reference for all climate change adaptation policies and actions in France.

The National Low-Carbon Strategy (SNBC)¹⁹⁸

The National Low-Carbon Strategy (SNBC) was established by Law No 2015-992 on 17 August 2015 on the energy transition for green growth. It is a strategic document that sets out France's roadmap to pursue its climate change mitigation policy and meet its short-, medium- and long-term greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions reduction targets. It constitutes one of the two strands of French climate policy, alongside the National Plan for adapting to Climate Change (Plan national d'adaptation au changement climatique, PNACC)¹⁹⁹. This roadmap includes:

- A long-term objective: achieving carbon neutrality in 2050 and reducing the French carbon footprint;
- A target path to achieve this: the Government has to establish a credible path towards the long-term objective, based on a set of measures and assumptions;
- carbon budgets: ceilings for greenhouse gas emissions not to be exceeded, expressed as an annual average per 5-year period, in million tonnes of CO₂ equivalent, broken down by sector of activity and per greenhouse gas;
- Public policy guidelines to achieve these objectives (sectoral, governance and cross-cutting guidelines) and monitoring indicators.

The SNBC 2 in force, adopted by decree in April 2020, aims to reduce France's gross greenhouse gas emissions by at least 40% in 2030 compared to 1990, to achieve carbon neutrality in 2050.

The new SNBC 3 sets a path towards higher targets, in particular the 50 % reduction in the gross greenhouse gas emissions between 1990 and 2030, in line with the European Green Deal. The French government has focused on the 2030 horizon and has set a framework for action for

¹⁹⁸ National Low-Carbon Strategy (SNBC) | Ministries Spatial Planning Ecological Transition

¹⁹⁹ Presentation of the National Climate Change Adaptation Plan | Ministries Spatial Planning Ecological Transition

2030-2050 to guide collective action on the right path towards achieving carbon neutrality in 2050. Particular focus is placed on decarbonising the transport sector, one of the main GHG emitters in France. The aim is to reduce emissions by encouraging a transition to electric vehicles, with a target of 66% electric vehicles in sales and 15% in the overall vehicle fleet by 2030. In terms of housing, the National Low-Carbon Strategy 3 aims to renovate 400,000 single-family homes and 200,000 collective housing units annually to increase their EE.

The multi-year energy program

France's multi-year energy plan (known by its French acronym PPE) is a roadmap for the periods 2019-2023 and 2024-2028, setting out the country's main energy priorities. Its main focuses are:

- **Reducing Energy Consumption:** The PPE aims to reduce final energy consumption by 16.5% by 2028 compared to 2012 and 15.4% by 2028 compared to 2018.
- **Eliminating Fossil Fuels:** The consumption of fossil fuels is set to decrease by 35% in 2028 compared to 2012.
- **Developing Renewable Energies:** Renewable energy is expected to play a key role in the energy transition, with renewable electricity capacities reaching 101 to 113 GW by 2028, doubling the capacity compared to 2017. Biogas production is also expected to reach 24 to 32 TWh by 2028, an increase of 4 to 6 times compared to 2017 production.
- **Not Giving Up on Nuclear:** nuclear power's share in electricity production will gradually decrease to 50% by 2035 with the closure of 14 reactors while ensuring energy security.
- **Developing Renewable Heat:** The consumption of renewable heat is set to increase by between 40% and 60% by 2028, driven by the increased use of renewable heating sources such as biomass, geothermal energy, and district heating networks. The consumption of renewable heat is expected to reach between 218 and 247 TWh by 2028.
- **Clean Mobility:** the plan focuses on expanding infrastructure, including charging stations, hydrogen/GNV stations, broadening collective transport options and promoting active mobility while phasing out new thermal vehicles sales by 2040.
- **Economic growth and employment opportunities:** The economy is expected to grow by a 2.1-point increase in GDP by 2028, with a forecast of 440,000 jobs being created in the same year.

According to the Multi-Year Energy Programme electricity is expected to make up 39% of the energy mix by 2035 (compared to 25% in 2024), with 30% coming from non-electrical renewables. The goal is to follow a trajectory that would have electricity cover 54% of the total energy mix by 2050.

Table 9: France energy and climate objectives 2030 (2035) compared to 2012 (NECP)

Indicator	National target 2030	Horizon
Final energy consumption	- 30 %	EU target of -28.6 %
Primary energy consumption		EU target of -36 %
Primary energy consumption for energy use – Carbon	Reduce by 70%	Reduce by 75% in 2035
Primary energy consumption for energy use – Natural gas	Reduce by 40 %	Reduce by 60 % in 2035
Primary energy consumption for energy use – Petroleum products	Reduce by 50 %	Reduce by 70 % in 2035
Final renewable energy consumption	MINUTES: 54 to 60 GW Terrestrial wind: 33 to 35 GW; Wind at sea: 3.6 GW; Hydropower (incl. STEP): 26.3 GW ; RE heating and cooling: 297 TWh ; Biofuels: 48 Twh; Biogas: 50 TWh	
Share of renewable heating and cooling in H&C consumption	45 %	55% in 2035
Share of renewable energy in buildings	49%	
Nuclear production capacities	9,9 GWe of new capacities committed by 2026	
Carbon intensity of energy used in the transport sector	Greenhouse gas emissions reduction by 14.5 %	Reduction of greenhouse gas emissions by 25% in 2035
Renewable gas production capacity	Gas injection of 15 % renewable gases into the gas network	
Flexibility installed capacity	Aim to develop flexibilities	6.5 GW of DR (PPE 2019-2028) in 2028; Between 28 and 68 GW of additional flexibility requirements for 2030/2035
GHG emissions other than LULUCF	Reduction of greenhouse gas emissions by -50 % in 2030 compared to 1990	Reaching carbon neutrality in 2050

4.7.6. Policy Guidelines for Facilitating Deployment of LFMs and Exploitation of Flexibility

Enhancing RES development and LFMs in France by 2030 requires a mix of regulatory support, technological innovation, market design improvements, and local engagement that need to take place. Some key recommendations in that regard are mentioned below:

- **Strengthen Regulatory & Market Frameworks**

Adapt market rules to enable FS and support local RES integration. Establish standardized market rules for DSOs to procure flexibility from local actors. Introduce incentives for DR and decentralized energy trading.

Capacity Market Adjustments are needed by reforming France's capacity market to allow smaller flexibility providers (e.g., aggregators). Revise grid tariffs by incentivizing distributed energy production and self-consumption.

- **Enhance LFMs**

Develop decentralized markets where consumers, industries, and aggregators can trade flexibility. Some examples are: the Réseau de Transport d'Électricité (RTE) & Enedis piloting LFMs in Brittany and Nouvelle-Aquitaine to manage peak demand, and NODES market platform (European-based), which allows localized energy trading between producers and consumers.

Create a National LFM Platform: Develop a unified digital platform to facilitate local energy trading. Ensure transparent pricing and secure transactions for flexibility markets.

- **Aggregation & Demand Response Participation**

Encourage residential & industrial DR with dynamic pricing and ToU tariffs. Deploy real-time energy pricing and smart demand-side response mechanisms. Example: Tempo tariff by EDF: Encourages industrial and residential consumers to shift energy use based on peak hours.

Expand third-party aggregators to enable small energy consumers (homes, businesses) to participate.

- **Digital & Smart Grid Technologies**

Deploy smart meters, AI-driven demand prediction, and blockchain for efficient trading. Enable P2P energy trading for prosumers (solar PV owners, energy communities). France could allow decentralized energy trading via smart contracts in pilot zones.

- ***Energy Storage & Hydrogen for Grid Flexibility, Electric Vehicles***

Invest in battery storage and green hydrogen for balancing intermittent RES. Example: H2V Normandy & Dunkirk green hydrogen projects provide industrial-scale hydrogen storage and flexibility; Corsica's battery storage pilot, stabilizing solar power integration.

Develop V2G (Vehicle-to-Grid) and battery storage solutions to supply FS. Incentivize EV owners to sell energy back to the grid. Example: Renault's Advanced Battery Storage uses EV batteries as a decentralized flexibility resource.

- ***Expand Energy Communities and Peer-to-Peer (P2P) Trading***

Support decentralized energy-sharing schemes and local self-consumption. Incentivize local energy communities to invest in flexibility assets like batteries and EV. Provide financial support and tax benefits for energy communities participating in LFM. Example: Blockchain P2P pilot projects in France: Engie experimenting with blockchain-based energy exchanges.

- ***Pilot Projects & Scale Up***

- Conduct regional LFM pilot projects to test various models before national rollout. Ensure coordination between DSOs, TSOs (RTE), municipalities, and energy cooperatives.

4.8. Italy

As Europe experiences an energy transition, Italy is making significant efforts to enhance its use of RES benefitting from the diverse natural landscape of the country that has allowed for a range of RES development. The energy sector has undergone a significant change in the last ten years, with the total installed RES capacity almost doubling.

Italy is one of Europe's leaders in renewable energy, with a diversified mix that includes solar, wind, hydro, biomass, and geothermal energy. As reported by Terna²⁰⁰, the Italian TSO, electricity use in Italy rose by 2.2% in 2024, exceeding 312 TWh. Renewable energy achieved highest proportion to date, accounting for 41.2% of total power demand (up from 37.1% in 2023), generated by enhanced hydroelectric plants located in the northern region and solar PV installations²⁰¹. Approximately 83.7% of Italy's electricity demand in 2024 was satisfied through local production, with a net increase in national production of 2.7% compared to 2023. Hydropower generation rose by 30.4%, and solar energy production increased by 19.3%, achieving a peak of over 36 TWh in 2024. In contrast, electricity generation from wind (down 5.6%), geothermal (down 0.8%), thermal (down 6.2%), and particularly coal (down 71%) saw declines in 2024.

In general, in 2024 there was an increase in renewable energy generation and capacity, accompanied by substantial investments in clean energy infrastructure; however, challenges remain in balancing regional demand, supply, and storage.

4.8.1. State-of-the-art of LFM and FS, Transposition of EU Regulation

As stated in the Report of the RIA for LFM and Services²⁰², in Italy the regulation of renewable energy began in 2003 (Decree 387/2003²⁰³, and was further refined by the Romani Decree of 2011 (Decree 28/2011²⁰⁴). A number of mechanisms have been established to promote the development of RES like feed-in-tariff programme, Green Certificates, Conto Energia support scheme for PV plants²⁰⁵ that have contributed to a broader expansion of the electricity market.

In 2021, Law-Decree 77/2021²⁰⁶ was implemented to streamline processes for RES, and accelerate the attainment of renewable energy goals.

²⁰⁰ Renewable sources covered a record 41% of Italy's power demand in 2024 | Enerdata

²⁰¹ Renewable energy in Italy - statistics & facts | Statista

²⁰² D3.2: Regulatory Impact Analysis for Local Flexibility Markets and Services

²⁰³ Legislative Decree 387/2003 on the promotion of electricity produced from RES in the internal electricity market (2003)

²⁰⁴ Legislative Decree 28/2011 on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources (2011)

²⁰⁵ GSE – Renewable energy

²⁰⁶ Law-Decree 77/2021 – Governance of the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (2021)

The European RED II and IEMD Directives were transposed into the Italian legislation in 2021, respectively, via Legislative Decrees 199²⁰⁷ and 210²⁰⁸ on 8 Nov 2021. These decrees helped advance the electricity market by outlining the roles of participants and their relationships.

In line with the Clean Energy Package, Italy has also issued supplementary guidelines to ensure that national legislation remains fully compatible with evolving EU policy objectives. The Ministry of Economic Development (MISE) and ARERA have published updated technical guidelines and regulatory updates that detail the implementation of the Clean Energy Package measures. Stakeholders are advised to consult the latest MISE publications and ARERA's technical guidelines²⁰⁹ (see, for example, ARERA's document on grid modernization and smart metering updates, published in early 2024) for comprehensive operational details. This additional framework reinforces Italy's commitment to not only transposing but also actively updating its regulatory regime to reflect EU policy advancements²¹⁰.

The definition of energy communities is in line with EU legislation. The reference to the definition of RECs is included in the Legislative Decree 199/2021 (article 31), which is in line with the RED II definition. The responsible national energy agency published operational rules for energy communities in February 2024 after a test phase lasting several years. At the end of 2023, there were just over 100 energy communities in Italy, but a significant increase is now expected with the new regulation. The aim of the government in Rome is to install additional PV systems with a total output of 5 GW by 2027 by strengthening the energy communities. The industry association Italia Solare even expects at least 12 GW of PV to be added through energy communities by 2030²¹¹.

In Italy, the energy sector legislation is shared among the national authority and regional authorities²¹². Most of the Italian regions have started actions for promotion and support of REC developments; for example the first regional laws on energy communities come from the Piedmont and Puglia regions and many regions have enacted regional measures concerning renewable energy self-consumers and RECs promotion. Financial assistance aimed at maintaining their establishment and ensuring the feasibility of technical and economic designs is one of the most frequently used support mechanisms.

²⁰⁷ Legislative Decree 199/2021 – Implementation of (EU) Directive 2018/2001 (2021)

²⁰⁸ Legislative Decree 210/2021 – Implementation of (EU) Directive 2019/944 (2021)

²⁰⁹ ARERA, SUMMARY OF THE ANNUAL REPORT TO ACER AND THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION ON THE REGULATORY ACTIVITIES AND FULFILMENT OF DUTIES OF THE REGULATORY AUTHORITY FOR ENERGY NETWORKS AND ENVIRONMENT. https://www.arera.it/fileadmin/EN/publications/acer_and_ec/AR_2024_Summary_EN.pdf

²¹⁰ Italy Adopts a New Energy Decree to Boost Energy Security and Renewable Energy | Cleary Gottlieb

²¹¹ [EU project - Integrating energy communities into sector coupling](#)

²¹² Krug, M.; Alonso, I.; Anfinson, K.; Azevedo, I.; del Bufalo, N.; Di Nucci, M.; Dylag, A.; Gatta, V.; Massa, G.; Meynaerts, E.; et al. COME RES Project Comparative Assessment of Enabling Frameworks for RECs and Support Scheme Designs. D7.1 2022. https://come-res.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/Resources/Deliverables/COME_RES_Deliverable_7.1_Comparative_assessmet_report.pdf

LFMs aim at implementing a market based procedure to guarantee FS for DSOs. The Directive 2019/944 has settled the common rules for creating efficient, competitive, and sustainable LFMs. It has been implemented in Italy by the National Regulatory Authority (NRA) deliberations 322/2019/R/eel²¹³ and 352/2021/R/eel²¹⁴.

In addition, the Regulations of the local flexibility market in Italy²¹⁵ were issued, containing the operating rules of the local flexibility market. They were made available by GME (Manager of the Energy Markets in Italy) to DSOs to procure local ancillary FS, in the context of the pilot projects established pursuant to Resolution of the Regulatory Authority for Energy, Networks and the Environment (of 3 August 2021 no. 352/2021/R/eel)²¹⁶.

In 2024 the Italian legislative framework in the energy sector underwent further significant developments with the approval of Decree-Law 181/2023 converted into Law No. 11 of 2 February 2024, known as D.L. Energia 2²¹⁷. This decree introduces a series of measures aimed at promoting environmental sustainability, energy efficiency and innovation in the sector, reflecting the country's commitment to an increasingly urgent and necessary energy transition.

Some regulations on REC development

- *Decree Law 162/2019*²¹⁸ has created the possibility of using collective self-consumption of renewable energy produced by installations with a capacity of less than 200 kWh on an experimental basis;
- *Decree Law 199/2021*²¹⁹ implements EU Directive 2018/2001 on the promotion of the use of energy from RES (RED II); It simplifies administrative procedures related to the production and use of renewable energy and provides for new or adjusted incentive schemes for renewable electricity and thermal energy, for self-consumption and energy communities;
- *Decree Law 8/2020 ARERA* introduces a series of measures to be implemented in line with Decree 199/2021; it allows REC members to share energy under the same low voltage distribution substation;
- *Decree 24 01 2024 MASE CER*²²⁰ stimulates the creation and development of RECs and widespread self-consumption in Italy.

²¹³ ARERA, 322/2019/R/eel - Testo Integrato del Dispacciamento elettrico (TIDE) - Orientamenti complessivi . 2019.

²¹⁴ ARERA, 352/2021/R/eel - Progetti pilota per l'approvvigionamento di servizi ancillari locali. 2021. Accessed: Mar. 08, 2024. [Online]. <https://www.arera.it/atti-e-provvedimenti/dettaglio/21/352-21>

²¹⁵ 20240319_Regolamento_MLF_EN.pdf

²¹⁶ Arera EN: [Translate to English:] Homepage

²¹⁷ Italy: The main legislative provisions of the Decree-Law Energy 2 | Rödl & Partner

²¹⁸ <https://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legge:2019-12-30;162!vig=2024-11-15>

²¹⁹ <https://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legislativo:2021;199>

²²⁰ <https://www.mase.gov.it/comunicati/energia-mase-pubblicato-decreto-cer>

4.8.2. Smart Local Flexibility Services - Compliance and Safety

Compliance

The integration of the European markets, such as market coupling, and the adoption of European network codes aimed at harmonising national regulations on electricity markets and systems. According to the updated Electricity Market Rules under Decree No. 450/20.12.2024²²¹, issued by the Minister of the Environment and Energy Security, and as specified in Art. 23-3a of Legislative Decree 210/2021, DSOs are mandated to cooperate closely with the TSO (Terna SpA) to ensure network security. This cooperation primarily involves the management of ancillary and balancing services through the participation of electricity producers, consumers, and storage operators.

To further enhance grid stability, Ministerial Decree No. 379²²² has approved regulations for the capacity market, a mechanism designed to remunerate the capacity necessary for long-term system adequacy. The broader transformation of Italy's energy system aims to create a secure and flexible grid based on renewables, storage, energy efficiency, and smart grid expansion while also unlocking consumer demand.

In addition, ARERA has issued new technical guidelines on smart metering and grid safety, which are now integral to the operational protocols of both DSOs and TSOs. These guidelines, updated in early 2024, establish detailed standards for real-time monitoring and risk management of distributed energy resources. Stakeholders are required to consult these ARERA documents to ensure full compliance with safety and regulatory criteria.

Furthermore, to strengthen network security at the local level, Art. 23-3b of Legislative Decree 210/2021 introduces the experimentation of a self-dispatching system. This mechanism incentivizes producers and final consumers to balance their electricity consumption and production locally through a system of rewards and penalties, reducing the strain on centralized grid operations.

As early as 2006, ARERA recognised the potential of smart metering in adapting tariffs to end-customers in the residential sector as well as providing flexibility on the network. The main DSO, ENEL, had the ambition to install 30 million smart meters. With a significant advance on the EU objectives (80% of households equipped by 2020), almost the entire Italian residential sector is equipped with smart meters. ENEL, with the support of the regulatory authority, commenced

²²¹https://www.mase.gov.it/sites/default/files/Archivio_Energia/Energia_Elettrica/Mercato_Elettrico/dm_450_20-12-2024.pdf

²²² <https://www.mise.gov.it/index.php/it/normativa/decreti-ministeriali/2039896-decreto-ministeriale-28-giugno-2019-capacity-market>

the deployment of the second generation of smart meters.²²³ Regulated by Art. 8 of the Legislative Decree 210/2021, end-customers with smart meters have the right to conclude a contract with a dynamic electricity price with a supplier (which has more than 200 000 end customers). The pricing must be based on the customer's actual consumption data.

For Smart Meters installed after July 2019, end-consumers must have access to the data generated by the device or to an online interface in a secure way. Article 9-1 of Legislative Decree 210/2021 specifies that the data security measurement and communication systems must comply with EU legislation.

Safety

The security dimension concerning the energy system requires the security of energy supply to consumers at sustainable prices capable of maintaining the competitiveness of the industrial and manufacturing sector. In Italy the energy supply is mainly provided from renewable sources and gas, with a decreasing role of coal, in line with the phase-out objective. Security of energy supply has to be fostered by development of electricity and gas production from renewable sources, further improvements in energy efficiency and greater diversification of natural gas supply routes.

4.8.3. Business Models and Financing Mechanisms to Boost Stakeholder Motivation

Business models

Different models of RECs respond to the needs and benefits expected by their own members and to the specification of the site / city / area. Table 9 outlines the key features of three evolving models by highlighting various stakeholders and supporters, objectives and value offerings, as well as funding and subsidies accessible for the development of RECs; it also explains the schemes for distributing benefits among members.

²²³ Enel – The Circular Smart Meter: sustainable innovation (2022)

Table 10: Identification and categorization of Italian REC development models²²⁴

	Bottom-Up/ Citizen-Driven	Top-Down/ PA-Driven	Energy/Technical Operator Driven
Main stakeholder/ Proponent	Citizens, local private proponents, and SMEs	Public/local authority, PAs, and non-profit organizations	Technical player/energy operator
Purpose	Lowering energy bills, consumers empowerment, sharing energy/economic benefits, and fostering social cohesion and local economic development	Energy consumption reduction, tackling energy poverty, fostering social cohesion, value generation in the territory, and local economic development	Business opportunities, energy efficiency measure promotion and commissioning, local economic development, and energy consumption reduction
Available fundings and subsidies	Members’ investment, feed-in premium tariffs, bank loans, and tax deductions	Public (national and regional) funding (in the cumulable percentage) and feed-in premium tariffs	Developer/proponent and members’ investments, and feed-in premium tariffs
Benefits-sharing model	Equitable redistribution or according to the investment participation/amount of energy shared	Equitable redistribution, establishment of a social funds for disadvantaged members, community services, or energy efficiency measures	Mainly divided between energy/technical operator and members (depending on the level of investment participation)

Some barriers appear to be common to the three approaches used in Italy.

Some regulatory issues concerning the REC business model have to be solved like: defining the feed-in premium tariff (who can access it, limits to its application, combinability with other regional/ national funding schemes); the legal form - the REC can take any form of legal entity but the regulations define objectives and characteristics that direct the choice and circumscribe it. The REC is based on a statute defining its operation, administrative bodies, parameters and criteria for distribution of benefits and its establishment not only requires technical skills, but also legal and management skills, as well as related professional figures which can limit the community.

Another difficulty can rise when collecting information about members belonging to the same MV/HV substation, involved in the design process but not able to join, being outside the proximity perimeter, though ARERA’s regulatory document has outlined the criteria on the basis of which each DSO identifies the areas underlying each MV/HV substation and maps providing this information have been consequently released by DSOs in early 2023.

Other issues to be considered are:

- (i) Smart meters availability for monitoring and calculating shared energy on an hourly basis;

²²⁴ Tatti,A.;Ferroni,S.;Ferrando,M.;Motta,M.;Causone,F.The Emerging Trends of Renewable Energy Communities’ Development in Italy. Sustainability 2023, 15,6792. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15086792>

(ii) REC members' withdrawal possibility properly regulated for not compromising the stability of the energy community and, consequently, the economic return on investment, while still ensuring the freedom of withdrawal to each shareholder;

(iii) The possibility of deducting the amount of shared energy from the bill, which introduces operational complications; and

(iv) Financing to be considered, if not covered by national or state funds, for structural and energy renovation of the roof surfaces on which RES systems will be installed.

Financing mechanisms

Italy has some of the highest solar radiation in the EU. Its government can significantly reduce energy costs of its citizens by facilitating deployment and utilisation of the renewable source of energy. Increasing investments in RES can also generate much needed jobs for the economy, especially in rural areas and the South.

Italy has implemented different instruments to support renewable electricity generation, including support for produced electricity, grant aid and fiscal incentives.

In Italy, the energy sector legislation is shared among the national authority and regional authorities²²⁵. Most of the Italian regions have started actions for promotion of REC developments; for example the first regional laws on energy communities come from the Piedmont and Puglia regions and many regions have enacted measures concerning renewable energy self-consumers and RECs promotion. Financial assistance aimed at maintaining their establishment and ensuring the feasibility of technical and economic designs is one of the most frequently used support mechanisms. Most regions primarily provide financial assistance for setting up RECs, but few have designated funds for installing RES systems.

The Regional Operational Plans 2021-2027 explicitly envisage the setup of RECs as a specific objective and allocate funds to promote them. Certain regions that initiated specific initiatives, partially funded by EU structural funds, mainly cover costs for feasibility studies and the legal establishment of RECs in areas such as: Lombardia²²⁶, Emilia Romagna²²⁷, Lazio²²⁸, Campania²²⁹ (municipalities with less than 5.000 inhabitants), Sicilia²³⁰, Sardegna²³¹, and others.

²²⁵ Krug, M.;Alonso, I.;Anfinson, K.;Azevedo, I.;del Bufalo N.;Di Nucci,M.;Dyląg, A.;Gatta, V.;Massa, G.;Meynaerts, E.;et al. COME RES Project Comparative Assessment of Enabling Frameworks for RECs and Support Scheme Designs.D7.1 COME RES 2022.

²²⁶ [Regione Lombardia](#)

²²⁷ [Regione Emilia Romagna](#)

²²⁸ [Lazio innova](#)

²²⁹ [Regione Campania](#)

²³⁰ <https://www.regione.sicilia.it/la-regione-informa/avviso-pubblico-costituzione-comunita-energie-rinnovabili-solidali>

²³¹ <https://delibere.regione.sardegna.it/protected/64934/0/def/ref/DBR64702/>

Italy's National Recovery and Resilience Plan²³² allocates 2.2 billion euros to assist energy communities (RECs) and self-consumption schemes (SCSs), with the goal of generating 2,500 GWh of clean energy, driven by communities in municipalities with populations under 5,000. Grants are available for the development and use of renewable electrical and thermal sources. Italy's plan includes five reforms, and "up-scale" investments drawing on existing measures and investments to reduce its reliance on fossil fuels, with a tight timeframe till August 2026.

4.8.4. Awareness & Actions to Ensure High Customer Participation in the LFM

The development of RECs in Italy is supported by a combination of public and private initiatives, with the goal of increasing the renewable energy use, and at the same time, bringing social, environmental, and economic benefits to community members.

The leading role of the public administrations (PAs) in the dissemination of RECs has proved to be very important. The national and regional calls predefine PAs with the role of major aggregators and promoters of RECs; local authorities provide the assets for the initiative, e.g., they offer the public building roof tops for PV installation, create the local regulatory and financing framework conditions to develop RECs and encourage citizen participation in energy transitions activities.

The energy communities and prosumers are appropriate forms to engage citizens in the clean energy transition, to encourage energy efficiency measures application, to reduce energy costs of households, and, ultimately, help improve public acceptance of renewable energy projects. Energy communities are also a way to improve system flexibility. According to PNIEC the promotion of RECs will be pursued through information tools on locally available resources and the opportunities offered by support instruments. The development of standard tools for the establishment and management of communities and the valorisation of energy production will also be considered. A review will be carried out to verify the possibility of developing facilitation and support measures on the basis of monitoring and reconnaissance of the experiences.

4.8.5. Strategic Planning Documents

The National Energy Strategy²³³ is a ten-year plan that the Italian Government drew up in 2017 to manage the change of the national energy system: a document looking beyond 2030, and laying the groundwork for building an advanced and innovative energy model. Some of the main

²³² Italy's National Recovery and Resilience Plan <https://www.italiadomani.gov.it/it/home.html>

²³³ BROCHURE_ENG_SEN.PDF

targets include reduction of final energy consumption, increase of RES in total energy consumption as well as in electricity consumption, and others.

While Italy ranks among the top countries in Europe for renewable energy consumption, its **Integrated National Plan for Energy and Climate** (PNIEC)²³⁴ aims to raise the proportion of electricity derived from renewables to 63% by 2030, an increase from 37% in 2022.

Currently, RES accounts for roughly 19 % of energy consumption, with the PNIEC targeting an increase to 39% by 2030.

Even though Italy is a leader in the European green energy landscape, it still faces challenges in achieving its renewable energy targets and energy independence, as the nation remains significantly reliant on imported fossil fuels.

Italy aims to achieve a target of 39.4% of its gross final energy consumption from RES by 2030, establishing an ambitious growth path for these energy sources with complete integration into the national energy framework (See Table 10).

Table 11: Italy overall objective of total RES share at 2030 (ktoe)

ktoe	2021	2022	2025	2030
Numerator – Gross final energy consumption from RES	22.819	22.568	29.104	43.174
Gross electricity production from RES	10.207	10.370	13.624	19.585
Final RES consumption for heating and cooling	11.061	10.626	12.490	17.634
Final consumption of RES in transport	1.552	1.573	2.990	5.955
Denominator – Total gross final energy consumption	120.340	117.448	114.917	109.563
Total RES share (%)	19.0 %	19.2 %	25.3 %	39.4 %

Source: PNIEC

4.8.6. Policy Guidelines for Facilitating Deployment of LFM and Exploitation of Flexibility

The Italian wholesale markets are accessible to suppliers and large energy consumers. Large consumers and energy communities may access the market indirectly through a supplier. However, independent aggregators cannot explicitly monetize their customers' flexibility in the

²³⁴ Italy - Final updated NECP 2021-2030 (submitted in 2024) - European Commission

Day-Ahead and Intraday markets due to the absence of a dedicated framework for independent aggregators covering DA and ID markets.

For implicit access to wholesale prices, the country has fully deployed smart meters, and subscriptions to dynamic electricity contracts are on the rise. 33.2% of households have a variable-price contract (where the price changes over time according to the terms of the contract), which includes 3.3% on dynamic contracts where the energy price is indexed to the hourly PUN²³⁵. This trend is higher for non-household actors, with 68.3% subscribing to a variable-price contract, including 8.7% on dynamic contracts.

Developing FS and LFMs in Italy requires a combination of regulatory adjustments, technological advancements, market incentives, and stakeholder engagement. To align with EU 2030 objectives Italy should follow the following key recommendations:

- ***Strengthening Regulatory and Market Frameworks***

Implement clear and stable regulatory frameworks for flexibility service providers.

Expand DR programs and enable aggregators to participate in capacity and balancing markets.

Align with EU directives (e.g., Clean Energy Package, Fit for 55) by setting clear market access rules for prosumers and DERs.

Ensure DSOs have a framework to procure FS for grid stability.

Example: TERNA's UVAM (Mixed Enabled Virtual Units) Pilot: Italy's TSO, TERNA, launched the UVAM framework, allowing aggregators to provide demand-side FS to the electricity market. This model could be expanded to enhance LFMs.

- ***Expanding Distributed Energy Resources (DERs) Participation***

Promote solar PV, battery storage, electric vehicles (EVs), and smart home energy management systems.

Provide financial incentives for residential and industrial prosumers to participate in LFMs.

Encourage businesses and communities to form Energy Communities that trade surplus energy and offer flexibility.

Example: Energy Communities in Italy: Pilot projects like the one in Magliano Alpi allow local prosumers to share electricity, reducing grid dependency and enhancing local flexibility.

²³⁵ The Single National Price (PUN) is the reference value for electricity offers at an indexed price and affects the price of electricity bills.

- ***Development of Digital Market Platforms***

Deploy blockchain and AI-based flexibility trading platforms for real-time transactions.

Enable peer-to-peer (P2P) energy trading among local consumers and prosumers.

Utilize smart contracts for automated and transparent energy exchanges.

Example: NODES LFM project: Italy can adopt lessons from NODES platform tested in other EU countries, which facilitates local flexibility trading between DSOs, prosumers, and aggregators.

- ***Enhancing Demand Response & Smart Grid Technologies***

Expand time-of-use tariffs and real-time pricing for industrial and residential consumers.

Integrate AI and IoT for predictive load management and automated DR activation.

Upgrade smart grid infrastructure to support bidirectional electricity flows.

Example: Enel X Demand Response Program: Enel X enables Italian industries and commercial businesses to participate in flexibility markets by shifting loads based on market signals.

- ***Encouraging Electric Vehicles (EVs) & Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G)***

Promote V2G programs where EVs act as grid batteries.

Provide incentives for EV owners to participate in LFMs.

Encourage charging infrastructure operators to integrate FS.

Example: DROSSO V2G Project (Turin, Italy): A pilot project allowing EVs to return energy to the grid during peak times, supporting local flexibility.

- ***Strengthening Collaboration Between Stakeholders***

Foster cooperation between TSOs, DSOs, aggregators, prosumers, and policymakers.

Support cross-border LFM initiatives with neighbouring EU countries.

Organize public-private partnerships to de-risk investment in FS.

Example: TERNA and DSOs Coordination Mechanisms: Develop coordinated flexibility procurement mechanisms between TERNA and DSOs can enhance system-wide efficiency.

Since 2017, 40 BSPs have participated in the UVAM pilot program, which was aimed at testing the participation of DERs (including in aggregate form) - such as smaller generation assets (<1MW), consumers and batteries - in the ancillary services, redispatching and local flexibility markets.

The new Italian regulation, the Testo Integrato del Dispacciamento Elettrico (TIDE), effective from the 1st of January 2025, incorporates the experience gained through the UVAM pilot program into the general dispatching framework. In addition, TIDE introduces two key parties in the regulatory framework: the BRP and the BSP. Any resources participating in the energy and ancillary services markets must define their BRP and BSP (which may also coincide).

Looking ahead, the GME (Gestore dei Mercati Energetici) is expected to reduce product granularity to 15-minute intervals by 2025. This change is a positive development for future participation of DERs into the wholesale market. However, further reform should be implemented to ensure a level of playing field between DERs, including DR, in the Italian wholesale market²³⁶.

By implementing the recommendations and leveraging existing pilot projects, Italy can accelerate the adoption of LFMs, aligning with the EU's 2030 energy transition goals. The key is integrating DERs, engaging prosumers, leveraging digital technologies, and ensuring regulatory clarity.

²³⁶ [the_smarten_map_2024_DIGITAL-updated.pdf](#)

4.9. The Netherlands

Since the National climate agreement in 2019, which set binding climate targets for 2030 and 2050, there has been a remarkable transformation in ambitions and the pace of transition in the Netherlands. Most notably, strong policy support has helped the country become a frontrunner in renewable electricity deployment, particularly through significant advancements in solar PVs and offshore wind power. Beyond the power sector, the Netherlands is also making substantial progress in electrifying heating and mobility.

Despite the rapid growth in clean energy in recent years, the country heavily relies for most of its energy supply on fossil fuels. Nearly half of electricity generation comes from natural gas and coal, heating in buildings remains highly dependent on natural gas and the transport sector relies predominantly on oil products. In 2022, fossil fuels still accounted for 55% of total power generation. Though the country has historically relied on natural gas, benefiting from the large Groningen gas field, due to climate change concerns, seismic activity from gas extraction, and the EU's green transition goals, the Netherlands has to reduce fossil fuel dependence across all sectors to achieve decarbonisation of its energy system. The Netherlands has, in a joint statement with six other European countries²³⁷, set the ambition to decarbonise the electricity system by 2035. The Dutch government has been expanding the role of wind, solar, and biomass energy to meet climate goals developing offshore wind energy, solar power, hydrogen, biomass and geothermal energy.

Besides continued growth of renewable energy, the Netherlands intends to expand its nuclear fleet with four new nuclear reactors. The nuclear energy in a decarbonised system has the potential to contribute to flexibility, baseload security and inertia management that enable better integration in the energy system²³⁸.

The Netherlands aims to become climate neutral by 2050 with a focus on green hydrogen economy, energy storage solutions, more offshore wind developments and expanding interconnections with neighbouring countries.

4.9.1. State-of-the-art of LFM and FS, Transposition of EU Regulation

The challenges in the RES Policy come from the rapid RES expansion that is straining the electricity grid, requiring upgrades to resolve grid congestion, a need for energy storage and

²³⁷ Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Luxemburg, The Netherlands and Switzerland

²³⁸ The Netherlands 2024

flexible backup power to solve balancing. In addition, it has to cope with public opposition to wind farms and large-scale solar projects.

Nevertheless, the Netherlands is actively developing and implementing LFM and FS to enhance grid stability, integrate RES, and create new revenue streams for participants. Collaborations between grid operators and service providers are essential to these advancements, positioning the country as a leader in energy flexibility initiatives.

A key initiative in developing LFM and FS is the cooperation between the European Power Exchange (EPEX SPOT) and the Dutch platform GOPACS. In June 2023, EPEX SPOT's Localflex market successfully connected with GOPACS, enhancing the procurement of flexible energy resources and facilitating efficient congestion management²³⁹.

GOPACS²⁴⁰, established by the Dutch transmission system operator TenneT and regional DSOs, serves as a coordination platform to mitigate grid congestion. The integration with EPEX Localflex allows grid operators to access intraday locational liquidity, enabling better matching of supply and demand to alleviate congestion.

The Netherlands legally allows every type of actor to access the wholesale market, though the country did not implement a framework allowing independent aggregators to trade wholesale markets. Aggregators can only be managing supply-side units (CHPs, batteries). Dynamic electricity contracts are available in the country, and Dutch households and businesses can access wholesale price signals by subscribing to dynamic retail contracts based on Day Ahead prices thanks to the high smart meter rollout which reached 90% in 2023. The Netherlands has a wide range of dynamic contracts available and in 2023, 4% of households and 9% of non-household customers subscribed to dynamic offers²⁴¹.

Several companies are actively contributing to the advancement of FS in the Netherlands. Flexcity²⁴², a subsidiary of Veolia, specializes in leveraging electrical flexibility to ensure network reliability. By optimizing energy consumption and production, Flexcity supports industrial and tertiary sites in generating new revenue streams through DR and load shifting²⁴³.

Sympower²⁴⁴ offers tailored solutions for DR, battery energy storage systems (BESS), and RES. Their platform aggregates and monetizes energy flexibility across European markets, assisting businesses in optimizing energy usage and contributing to grid stability.

²³⁹ EPEX SPOT's Localflex Dutch market connection to GOPACS completed successfully

²⁴⁰ <https://www.gopacs.eu/en/>

²⁴¹ <https://smarten.eu/>

²⁴² Netherlands | Flexcity

²⁴³ What's Electrical Flexibility?

²⁴⁴ Turn your energy into profit

Axpo Solutions²⁴⁵ has partnered with Energy Pool²⁴⁶ to provide smart energy management services in the country. This collaboration focuses on optimizing energy consumption for large business customers and energy-intensive industries by leveraging DR capacities and on-site generation assets.

The FlexiSwitch project, launched in early 2023 by Nord Pool²⁴⁷ and Equigy²⁴⁸, aims to reduce barriers for small-scale flexibility service providers. It standardizes interfaces between smaller flexibility producers and the broader balancing and power markets, facilitating easier and more efficient access to trading. This initiative supports the integration of DER into the grid.

Additionally, initiatives, like the InterFlex²⁴⁹ project, have tested LFMs to manage grid congestion and postpone infrastructure reinforcements at the low or medium-voltage distribution level. These projects involve dedicated IT platforms that facilitate communication between DSOs and aggregators, enabling the efficient sourcing of flexibilities to optimize grid management.

The Dutch electricity sector is experiencing a growing demand for local flexibility. Private individuals and businesses capable of adapting to this demand can benefit from emerging opportunities in flexibility markets. Conversely, those who fail to address this need may face higher electricity costs, underscoring the importance of strategic engagement with FS²⁵⁰. The Netherlands has been actively transposing European Union regulations to enhance FS and establish LFMs, aiming to optimize grid management and integrate RES.

In April 2024, the Dutch House of Representatives discussed the proposed new Energy Act, intended to replace the current Gas Act and Electricity Act of 1998. This legislation aims to modernize and harmonize energy markets and systems in the country, with a focus on better protecting consumers and companies. Key elements include the implementation of EU directives, the promotion of active customer participation, and the embedding of new market initiatives such as energy communities and aggregators²⁵¹.

Through these legislative and collaborative efforts, the Netherlands is effectively transposing EU regulations to enhance FS and develop LFMs, thereby supporting the country's energy transition goals.

²⁴⁵ Home | Axpo Netherlands

²⁴⁶ Energy Pool Netherlands

²⁴⁷ <https://www.nordpoolgroup.com/en/>

²⁴⁸ [The Platform - Equigy](#)

²⁴⁹ Interflex - Home

²⁵⁰ [The Dutch electricity sector - part 3: Developments affecting electricity markets - Rabobank](#)

²⁵¹ [The new energy law: what is it about? - NedZero](#)

4.9.2. Smart Local Flexibility Services - Compliance and Safety

The Netherlands is actively developing FS to enhance grid efficiency and comply with European Union (EU) regulations. These services aim to manage electricity demand and supply more effectively, integrating RES and addressing grid congestion. The EU's Directive (EU) 2019/944 emphasizes the importance of flexibility in electricity markets. In response to EU directives, the Netherlands is updating its energy legislation. The proposed Energy Act aims to modernize and harmonize energy markets, focusing on consumer protection and the integration of renewable energy. Key aspects include:

Active Customer Participation: Encouraging consumers to become active participants in the energy market through self-generation, storage, and energy sharing.

Flexible Connection Agreements: Establishing frameworks for system operators to offer flexible connection agreements, allowing for non-firm connections in areas with limited network capacity.

Data Management: Improving data management and exchange systems to support the efficient operation of energy markets and the integration of DER.

These measures align with the EU's directives, promoting flexibility and consumer engagement in the energy transition.

The deployment of smart FS in the Netherlands is guided by regulations set forth by the Authority for Consumers and Markets (ACM) and the Dutch Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy. These regulations aim to ensure fair access to the energy market, protect consumer interests, and promote the integration of RES. For instance, the ACM has published draft code amendment decisions enabling network operators to offer contracts without fixed transmission capacity in congested areas, effective from February 1, 2024, with a mandatory implementation by February 1, 2025²⁵².

Organizations involved in providing FS adhere to these regulatory frameworks, ensuring that their operations align with national energy policies and contribute to the overall stability and sustainability of the Dutch energy grid. By participating in these initiatives and complying with regulatory standards, stakeholders are contributing to a more resilient and efficient energy system, capable of accommodating the increasing share of RES.

²⁵² annualreport.alliander.com

In the Netherlands, the integration of smart FS is advancing through various initiatives aimed at optimizing energy consumption and enhancing grid stability. These services enable consumers and businesses to adjust their energy usage in response to grid demands, thereby contributing to a more efficient and sustainable energy system.

As already mentioned in p.4.9.2., Axpo Solutions AG has partnered with Energy Pool to offer smart energy management services focusing on optimizing energy consumption for large business customers by leveraging DR capacities, energy storage, and on-site generation assets. The initiative aims to enhance grid stability and support the integration of RES.

The Interflex project, conducted in the Strijp-S district of Eindhoven, tests alternatives to reduce peaks in energy supply and demand. By implementing a local marketplace, the grid operator Enexis collaborates with service providers to steer energy consumption, encouraging practices such as charging electric vehicles during off-peak hours. This approach aims to alleviate grid congestion and defer the need for infrastructure upgrades²⁵³.

Liander, a subsidiary of Alliander, is actively promoting the flexible use of energy to maximize network capacity utilization. The company offers products like the 'Capaciteit Beperkend Contract' (Capacity-Limiting Contract) to large business customers, incentivizing them to reduce usage during peak times. This strategy helps manage congestion and delays the need for network expansion²⁵⁴.

These initiatives demonstrate the Netherlands' commitment to developing smart FS in compliance with EU regulations, contributing to a more efficient and sustainable energy system.

Safety

In the Netherlands, the development of smart FS is accompanied by a strong emphasis on safety to ensure the reliable and secure operation of the electricity grid and stringent data safety measures to protect consumer information and ensure secure grid operations. Essential are the following considerations:

- *Coordination between System Operators:* Effective communication and coordination between TSOs and DSOs are crucial for safe grid operations. The GOPACS platform exemplifies this by facilitating joint procurement of FS to manage congestion, ensuring that actions taken by one operator do not adversely affect another part of the grid.
- *Standardization and Interoperability:* The Netherlands participates in initiatives to harmonize FS, baseline methodologies, and flexibility registers at the national level. This standardization ensures that all participants adhere to established safety protocols,

²⁵³ flexible-energy.eu

²⁵⁴ annualreport.alliander.com

reducing the risk of miscommunication or incompatible systems that could compromise grid safety²⁵⁵.

- *Integration of Advanced Technologies:* Projects like Interflex involve deploying smart grid management techniques, such as local smart storage units and advanced measurement systems, to monitor and control the distribution network in real-time. These technologies enhance the ability to detect and respond to potential safety issues promptly.
- *Data Privacy and Protection:* The collection and exchange of data between DSOs and flexibility service providers are fundamental to grid digitalization. However, this process must comply with data protection regulations to safeguard consumer privacy. Compliance with national and European data protection laws, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), is mandatory. DSOs and other entities involved in FS must implement robust data governance frameworks to ensure that data handling practices meet legal requirements and protect consumer rights.
- *Secure Data Sharing Platforms:* Ensuring that data is shared securely among stakeholders is crucial to maintain trust and protect sensitive information.

By addressing these considerations, the Netherlands aims to balance the advancement of smart FS with the imperative of data safety, ensuring a secure and efficient energy system.

4.9.3. Business Models and Financing Mechanisms to Boost Stakeholder Motivation

Business models

LFMs in the Netherlands are emerging as a crucial component of the energy transition, enabling decentralized energy management and optimizing grid efficiency. Several business models and technical solutions are being explored and described as follow:

- *Aggregator-Based Model:* Aggregators pool flexibility from various DERs and offer it to grid operators or energy markets. Payments come from grid operators for congestion management. Trading flexibility happens on wholesale or imbalance markets. Prosumers pay service fees for optimizing energy use.

Example: Equigy²⁵⁶ (Blockchain-Based Flexibility Trading): Equigy is a European-wide blockchain-based platform initiated by TenneT (the Dutch TSO) to facilitate small-scale flexibility trading, including electric vehicles (EVs) and home batteries. Consumers with home batteries,

²⁵⁵ Smarten.eu
²⁵⁶ Home - Equigy

EVs, or other flexible loads can offer their flexibility to the grid via aggregators. Blockchain ensures secure transactions and transparency. It supports the integration of renewables, reduces grid congestion, and empowers prosumers to participate in energy markets.

- *Grid Operator-Facilitated Market Model:* DSOs or TSOs create market platforms where flexibility providers bid to provide grid services. Grid operators pay for flexibility to avoid costly grid reinforcements.

Example: GOPACS²⁵⁷ (Grid Operators Platform for Congestion Solutions): GOPACS is collaboration between Dutch grid operators (TenneT, Liander, Stedin, Enexis, and Westland Infra) to reduce congestion in the electricity grid by procuring flexibility from market participants. Market participants (such as industrial consumers, aggregators, and energy suppliers) can offer their flexibility through GOPACS. The platform matches bids with grid congestion needs, allowing grid operators to pay for FS. Helps prevent costly grid reinforcements while enabling businesses to earn revenue from their flexible energy assets.

- *Peer-to-Peer (P2P) Energy Trading:* Households, businesses, and communities trade excess energy and flexibility directly using digital platforms, often supported by blockchain technology. Transaction fees from energy trades. Subscription fees for platform access. Value-added services like forecasting and demand-side management.

Example: Energy Trading at Lochem Energy Cooperative²⁵⁸: The Lochem Energy Cooperative runs a local energy trading initiative where households with solar panels sell excess electricity to their neighbours via a digital marketplace. Participants use an app to set prices and trade energy within their community, facilitated by blockchain technology. Encourages local energy self-sufficiency, reduces dependence on the main grid, and gives consumers more control over energy costs.

- *Energy-as-a-Service (EaaS) Model:* Companies provide flexibility and energy optimization solutions, bundling technology (like batteries, smart chargers) with management services. Subscription-based or pay-per-use models for FS. Shared savings from energy cost reductions. Incentives for grid balancing participation.

Example: USEF²⁵⁹ (Universal Smart Energy Framework) Pilots: USEF is a Dutch initiative that provides a standardized framework for energy flexibility markets. It has been used in various pilot projects, such as demand response programs for businesses and households. Businesses and residential users sign up for FS, allowing a service provider to manage their energy

²⁵⁷ GOPACS - Platform for congestion management.

²⁵⁸ LochemEnergy

²⁵⁹ Usef Energy – Universal Smart Energy Framework

consumption and storage in exchange for financial rewards. It enables scalable and interoperable flexibility solutions that can be integrated into future smart grid developments.

- *Community-Based Flexibility Markets:* Energy communities manage local flexibility resources and trade within microgrids or with the broader grid. Revenues come from local balancing services, grid operators paying communities for congestion relief, membership fees for community participation.

Example: FLEXNET (Flexible Energy Network in Amsterdam): FLEXNET is a local flexibility project in Amsterdam that enables residents and businesses to trade FS. It integrates solar power, battery storage, and demand-side response to optimize energy use at the neighbourhood level. Smart algorithms predict energy demand and supply, allowing consumers to shift their consumption based on real-time price signals. This helps reduce peak demand and prevents grid congestion. Increases energy self-sufficiency in urban areas and provides financial incentives for consumers who adjust their energy usage.

- *Industrial Demand Response Market:* Large industrial consumers participate in flexibility markets by adjusting their energy consumption based on price signals. Revenue Streams come from payments from TSOs/DSOs for load reduction. Savings on energy procurement through optimized DR.

Financing mechanisms

In order to be on track to meet its 2030 target the Dutch government put forward *the Climate Package*²⁶⁰ in April 2023, setting out 120 measures directed at both demand and supply sectors. The total budget for implementing the Climate Package of EUR 28 billion until 2030 is mostly financed by the Climate Fund.

*The Sustainable Energy Transition Incentive Scheme (SDE+ and SDE++)*²⁶¹ is the policy support mechanism for emissions reductions, administered by the Netherlands Enterprise Agency (RVO). Established as a feed-in premium system in 2011, the SDE+ scheme supports companies and non-profit organisations in making renewable energy investments through competitive and technology-neutral auctions. In 2020, the scheme was expanded (SDE++) to support a wider range of technologies to reduce GHG emissions, including carbon capture and storage (CCS), renewable hydrogen, waste heat and heat pumps. Subsidies are awarded to technologies with the most cost-efficient per tonne of CO₂-equivalent emissions avoided and the subsidy levels are based on the unprofitable component of the technology that reduces GHG emissions

²⁶⁰ Letter to the House of Representatives on spring decision-making on Climate | Parliamentary Paper | [Rijksoverheid.nl](https://rijksoverheid.nl)

²⁶¹ Stimulation of sustainable energy production and climate transition (SDE++) | RVO.nl

compared to market value. Subsidies are granted for 12-15 years, depending on the technology. The budget for the SDE++ scheme in 2024 amounts to EUR 11.5 billion.

Besides the SDE++ scheme, *the Climate Fund*²⁶² is the primary mechanism for financing the energy transition. The two financing schemes are complementary, as the SDE++ supports the most cost-efficient solutions to reduce emissions, whereas the Climate Fund can support less mature technologies. The initial total budget of the Climate Fund for the period 2022-30 amounted to EUR 35 billion, as reported in the Multi-year Programme 2025 Climate Fund²⁶³

To boost stakeholder motivation in LFM's in the Netherlands, various financing mechanisms are employed that can help incentivize participation, reduce investment risks, and ensure financial sustainability, as follows:

Subsidies & Government Incentives: The Dutch government and the European Union provide grants and subsidies to support the development of flexibility markets and related technologies. Stakeholders benefit as grants reduce upfront costs for businesses investing in energy flexibility solutions. The incentive encourages municipalities and cooperatives to develop LFM's.

Examples:

- SDE++ (Stimulerend Duurzame Energieproductie en Klimaattransitie): Supports large-scale renewable energy projects, indirectly encouraging flexibility solutions like battery storage.
- MOOI (Missiegedreven Onderzoek, Ontwikkeling en Innovatie)²⁶⁴: Funds innovative energy projects, including local flexibility pilots.
- HER+ (Hernieuwbare Energie Regeling)²⁶⁵: Supports projects that improve energy efficiency and integrate flexibility into the grid.

Grid Operator Compensation Schemes: Dutch TSOs and DSOs provide financial incentives for FS, helping defer expensive grid reinforcements. The schemes encourage businesses and households to participate in flexibility markets, providing a steady revenue stream for flexibility providers.

Examples:

- Congestion Management Contracts (via GOPACS): Flexibility providers are paid to shift or reduce electricity demand during peak times.

²⁶² Dutch Fund For Climate and Development - Dutch Development Bank - FMO

²⁶³ Multi-year programme 2025 Climate Fund | Report | Rijksoverheid.nl

²⁶⁴ Mission-driven research, development and innovation - HGM

²⁶⁵ Renewable energy | [Top Sector Energy]

- DSO Flexibility Procurement: Grid operators (e.g., Stedin, Enexis) pay aggregators and consumers for local flexibility that prevents grid overload.

Private Investment & Venture Capital: Startups and established companies developing flexibility solutions attract private investments. This enables innovation by funding start-ups developing smart energy solutions; it encourages competition and efficiency in the flexibility market.

Examples:

- Venture capital funding: Dutch cleantech startups (like Sympower and Dexter Energy) have received funding for AI-driven flexibility solutions.
- Corporate investment: Large energy companies (e.g., Shell, Eneco) invest in flexibility technology, including battery storage and DR platforms.

Energy-as-a-Service (EaaS) & Performance-Based Contracts: Under this model, businesses and households do not need to invest upfront in flexibility solutions like smart batteries or EV charging but instead pay for services based on performance. They reduce financial barriers for small businesses and households, thus encouraging widespread adoption of flexibility solutions.

Examples:

- Third-party-owned battery storage: Companies like Alfen and Greener provide batteries on a lease or pay-per-use basis.
- Smart charging-as-a-service: EV fleet operators pay for flexible charging services rather than investing in infrastructure.

Peer-to-Peer (P2P) Energy Trading & Blockchain-Based Financing: Decentralized energy trading platforms allow consumers to sell excess energy and flexibility directly to their neighbours, creating a new revenue stream. The impact is an increase of consumer engagement by allowing households to profit from flexibility.

Examples:

- Lochem Energy Cooperative: Uses blockchain-based trading to facilitate local energy transactions.
- Equigy (TenneT Blockchain Project): Enables small-scale prosumers to monetize their flexibility in real-time.

Green Bonds & Sustainable Financing: Municipalities, cooperatives, and businesses issue green bonds to finance large-scale flexibility projects. Long-term financing for large-scale flexibility

solutions is provided; this model enables communities to invest in and benefit from local energy markets.

Examples:

- Energie Samen (Dutch Energy Cooperatives Network): Issues community bonds to fund local energy storage and flexibility initiatives.
- Eneco Green Bonds: Used to develop smart grid and battery storage projects.

Driving the growth of LFM in the Netherlands has been implemented by a combination of government funding, private investment, market-based incentives, and innovative financial models. These financing mechanisms reduce financial risk, encourage participation, and accelerate the adoption of flexibility solutions.

4.9.4. Awareness & Actions to Ensure High Customer Participation in the LFMs

LFMs in the Netherlands rely on active customer participation to balance supply and demand efficiently. Ensuring high customer participation requires raising awareness and taking strategic actions. Here are some examples:

Awareness Strategies

Educational Campaigns: Utilities and grid operators can launch informational webinars, explainer videos, and social media campaigns to educate customers on the benefits of LFMs. Example: TenneT's CrowdBalancing initiative²⁶⁶ engaged consumers in balancing the grid.

Community Engagement Programs: Collaborate with municipalities and local energy cooperatives to spread awareness. Example: Energie VanOns²⁶⁷ is a Dutch cooperative that promotes community-driven energy solutions.

Gamification & Incentives: Using applications that reward customers for participating in LFMs. Example: Equigy²⁶⁸ is a blockchain-based platform that incentivizes customers to provide FS.

Transparency & Trust-Building: Publishing real-time data and success stories to demonstrate the benefits of participation. Example: The GOPACS platform provides transparent market signals to customers.

²⁶⁶ [Crowd Balancing Platform](#)

²⁶⁷ [Energy FromUs](#)

²⁶⁸ <https://equigy.com/>

Actions to Boost Participation

Dynamic Pricing & Smart Contracts: Offering time-of-use tariffs and automated smart contracts to encourage participation. Example: FlexiDAO²⁶⁹ enables transparent transactions for flexible energy.

Seamless Integration with Smart Devices: Partnering with smart home device manufacturers to automate flexibility participation. Example: Jedlix²⁷⁰ is a platform that optimizes EV charging for FS.

Aggregator Business Models: Allowing third-party aggregators to pool small-scale flexibility resources. Example: Next Kraftwerke²⁷¹, which aggregates DER for grid services.

Regulatory Support & Simplification: Streamlining registration and participation processes through government policies. Example: The Energy Act 2023, which aims to simplify market access for small participants.

4.9.5. Strategic Planning Documents

The Netherlands has outlined comprehensive strategic plans to advance RES and develop LFM leading up to 2030. The key energy and climate policies of Netherlands are outlined in the following documents and ambitions:

Climate Agreement (Klimaatakkoord) - 2019²⁷², that is a national roadmap aligned with the EU Green Deal to cut CO₂ emissions by 49% by 2030 and 95% by 2050 (compared to 1990 levels). It is focused on offshore wind, electrification of industry, and phasing out coal-fired power plants, as well as in investment in hydrogen, carbon capture, and storage (CCS) technologies.

Renewable Energy Act (SDE++ Subsidy Scheme): A market-driven subsidy program for businesses investing in renewable energy projects expanding beyond renewables to low-carbon solutions like CCS and green hydrogen.

Offshore Wind Roadmap (2030 and beyond)²⁷³ with the following targets: 11 GW of offshore wind capacity by 2030 and plans for new zones in the North Sea, integrating wind power with hydrogen production. This expansion is expected to make offshore wind the Netherlands' largest power source, contributing substantially to the country's renewable energy goals.

²⁶⁹ [Innovative Renewable Energy Solution - Flexidao](#)

²⁷⁰ [Smart Charging Home Page - Jedlix](#)

²⁷¹ [Next Kraftwerke Virtual Power Plant \(VPP\) voor Renewables](#)

²⁷² [National Climate Agreement - The Netherlands | Publicatie | Klimaatakkoord](#)

²⁷³ [This is the Netherlands](#)

*Regional Energy Strategies (RES)*²⁷⁴: As part of the National Programme Regional Energy Strategies, energy regions across the Netherlands are collaborating to generate at least 35 TWh of large-scale sustainable electricity on land by 2030. These strategies involve local authorities and stakeholders to identify optimal locations for renewable energy projects and ensure grid capacity aligns with increased RES generation.

*Integrated National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP)*²⁷⁵: The Netherlands has outlined its energy and climate objectives for 2030 in its updated National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP), submitted in June 2024 (See Table 12). The primary goal is to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030 compared to 1990 levels, with an aspirational target of a 60% reduction. Key targets and measures include:

Renewable Energy: The NECP aims for renewable sources to constitute at least 39% of the Netherlands' energy mix by 2030. This includes a significant expansion of offshore wind capacity to 21 GW, which is expected to supply approximately 75% of the country's electricity needs by that year. The government plans to develop new offshore wind farms, adding an average of 1GW per year between 2024 and 2030, resulting in a total installed capacity of 11.5 GW by 2030.

Energy Efficiency: The NECP emphasizes increasing energy efficiency across various sectors, including making buildings more energy-efficient and implementing stricter energy-saving obligations for companies and institutions.

Transportation: The plan includes the ambition that by 2030, 100% of newly sold passenger cars will be zero-emission vehicles.

Coal Phase-Out: All remaining coal-fired power plants are scheduled to be closed by 2030, contributing significantly to the emission reduction targets.

²⁷⁴ [Dutch National Programme Regional Energy Strategies | Regionale Energiestrategie](#)

²⁷⁵ Netherlands - Final updated NECP 2021-2030 (submitted in 2024) - European Commission

Table 12: Dutch NECP objectives and targets for 2030

Renewable Energy Sources	%
National target for the share of energy from renewable sources in gross final energy consumption by 2030	39
Share of electricity from renewable sources in gross final consumption of electricity	75
Share of heating and cooling from RES in gross final consumption of heating and cooling	32
Share of energy from renewable sources in final energy consumption in the transport sector	100276
Energy Efficiency	
Reduction of primary energy consumption compared to Reference Scenario 2020	11,7277
Improve energy efficiency	32.5
Net Greenhouse Gas Emission	
Reduction of transport sector CO ₂ emissions	40
Reduction of net greenhouse gas emissions compared to 1990 levels	55

Despite these ambitious plans, recent assessments indicate that the Netherlands may fall short of its 2030 climate goals without additional measures. Current policies are projected to achieve a 44-52% reduction in CO₂ emissions by 2030, which is below the 55% target. Challenges such as delays in offshore wind projects and policy changes have been cited as contributing factors.

To address these challenges, the Dutch government has announced an investment of USD 28.1 billion in various measures aimed at ensuring the 2030 climate goals are met. These measures include transforming gas power plants to run on hydrogen, connecting RES to storage solutions, and promoting the adoption of electric vehicles. In summary, the Netherlands' updated NECP sets forth comprehensive targets and strategies to transition towards a more sustainable and climate-neutral energy system by 2030.

The strategic initiatives reflect the Netherlands' commitment to a sustainable energy future, focusing on substantial investments in renewable energy infrastructure and the development of local flexibility solutions to ensure a resilient and efficient energy system by 2030.

²⁷⁶ "The aim is to have all new cars and vans zero-emission by 2030. These include hydrogen and battery electric vehicles.", Netherlands - Final updated NECP 2021-2030 (submitted in 2024) - European Commission

²⁷⁷ "In March 2023, EC reached a political agreement on the EED recast and the final reduction rate was set at 11.7 % reduction. This target is binding at EU level for final energy use and indicative for primary energy use. At national level, both targets are indicative. The exact indicative national contribution for the Netherlands is still being worked out.", Netherlands - Final updated NECP 2021-2030 (submitted in 2024) - European Commission

4.9.6. Policy Guidelines for Facilitating Deployment of LFMs and Exploitation of Flexibility

LFMs are a key solution for managing grid congestion and integrating renewable energy. To effectively enable and regulate LFMs in the Netherlands, several recommendations can be considered:

- **Clear Regulatory Framework**

Ensure alignment with EU regulations, including the Clean Energy Package and Network Codes.

Define roles and responsibilities of DSOs, TSOs, and market participants in LFMs. The Netherlands could mandate DSOs to run transparent flexibility tenders, ensuring market fairness. Standardize LFM market rules, ensuring consistency across different regions.

- **Market Participation**

Develop transparent pricing mechanisms for FS.

Enable participation from various flexibility providers, including prosumers, aggregators, and storage operators. The Netherlands could implement a national or regional digital marketplace where DSOs buy flexibility from businesses, battery operators, and prosumers.

Remove regulatory barriers that hinder DR and storage integration. TSOs like TenneT (Netherlands/Germany) use Equigy (EU TSO Blockchain Platform) to integrate small-scale flexibility assets (like home batteries and EVs) into balancing markets. The Dutch government could promote wider adoption by making it mandatory for DSOs to provide a digital interface for small-scale flexibility providers.

- **Coordination Between DSOs and TSOs**

Implement data-sharing protocols between DSOs and TSOs to avoid conflicts in flexibility procurement.

Develop coordinated congestion management strategies that leverage LFMs at both distribution and transmission levels. GOPACS (Grid Operator Platform for Congestion Solutions) is a Dutch initiative where DSOs and TSOs collaborate to resolve grid congestion using market-based solutions. To enhance LFM effectiveness, the government could expand GOPACS to directly integrate with new local flexibility platforms.

- ***Standardized Data and Digitalization Protocols***

Introduce open-access data platforms to facilitate real-time market operations. The Netherlands could introduce a data-sharing platform to ensure real-time market operations and transparency in LFM transactions.

Adopt standardized communication protocols to integrate multiple LFMs and ensure interoperability. The Netherlands could require LFMs to adopt a standardized communication protocol that allows automated participation in DR and flexibility markets.

- ***Incentives for Flexibility Providers***

Offer financial incentives or compensation schemes for early market adopters.

Develop a level playing field where small-scale flexibility providers can compete with larger players. The Netherlands could introduce a flexibility remuneration scheme where industrial consumers and energy communities are rewarded for providing FS.

- ***Consumer Protection and Fair Pricing***

Ensure non-discriminatory access to LFMs for all market participants. Protect consumers from excessive pricing volatility through regulatory oversight.

- ***Regulatory Sandboxes and Pilot Projects***

Support innovation by allowing temporary exemptions from strict regulations in controlled environments. Use pilot projects to gather insights on best practices and potential market design improvements.

Example: TenneT has tested a blockchain-based system to integrate home battery storage into balancing markets. Expanding this sandbox approach across DSOs in the Netherlands would accelerate LFM adoption.

4.10. Romania

Romania²⁷⁸ uses a diverse energy mix, including coal, natural gas, nuclear, hydroelectric, and renewable sources. The largest share of electricity production historically came from coal and natural gas, followed by hydroelectric and nuclear power.

In the last few years, there has been a shift towards increasing the share of RES, such as wind and solar. Romania has set ambitious targets for renewable energy, aiming to increase its share in the total energy production. Wind energy has seen substantial growth, with numerous operated wind farms, while solar energy is becoming increasingly important, particularly in the southern regions of the country. Onshore wind and solar additions now account for a third of the country's total installed capacity.

Romania has two operational nuclear reactors at the Cernavodă Nuclear Power Plant, which contribute a significant portion of the country's electricity, but also significant natural gas reserves and production facilities, making it a key player in the regional natural gas market. Romania exports and imports electricity to and from neighbouring countries, and is also part of the European Union's internal energy market, which aims to create a single, competitive market for electricity and gas across EU member states.

The National Recovery and Resilience Plan calls for phasing out coal and lignite by the end of 2032 and replacing them with renewable and low-carbon energy sources, including, but not limited to, clean hydrogen.

Romania's installed electricity generation capacity is approximately 10,000 MW. In 2024, the country added approximately 1,200 MW of new capacity, including 950 MW from renewable sources such as solar and wind power.²⁷⁹

Romania also aims to introduce an additional 2,500 MW of capacity by the end of 2025 thanks to putting into operation 4 new power plants (Iernut Gas-Fired Power Plant, Răstolița Hydropower Plant, Năvodari Cogeneration Plant and Mintia Gas-Fired Power Plant). The first 1,000 MW could be connected to the national energy system by the end of 2025²⁸⁰.

Projects funded through the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR) are projected to add between 1,200 and 1,500 MW from renewable sources. Battery storage capacity is also expected to double, reaching 400-500 MWh, enhancing grid stability and energy security²⁸¹.

²⁷⁸ Romania - Energy, 12.01.2024

²⁷⁹ Romania-Insider.com, 27.01.2025

²⁸⁰ Romania-Insider.com, 7.01.2025

²⁸¹ Romanian Business Journal, 6.01.2025

These developments are part of Romania's broader strategy to double its installed power generation capacity to 40 GW by 2035, with over 80% derived from renewable sources. Through these investments, Romania is positioning itself as a regional energy hub, aiming for energy independence and a sustainable energy future.

4.10.1. State-of-the-art of LFM and FS, Transposition of EU Regulation

State-of-the-art of LFM and FS

LFMs enhance grid stability and integrate RES. Their development is driven by the increasing share of variable RES, such as wind and solar, in the national energy mix, necessitating improved mechanisms for balancing supply and demand.

Romania's NECP 2021-2030 outlines objectives to increase the flexibility of the national energy system. Key strategies include the digitization of the energy system, development of intelligent grids, and promotion of active consumer participation, particularly through the integration of prosumers. These measures are intended to facilitate the efficient integration of RES and enhance the resilience of the energy infrastructure²⁸².

DSOs operate the LFM with the aim to manage congestion in the distribution networks, particularly in regions like Dobrogea, which experience high wind power generation. The approach involves the collaboration between DSOs and the TSO to implement redispatch mechanisms that address potential network congestion. This strategy leverages existing balancing market frameworks, promoting efficient and cost-effective solutions for grid management²⁸³.

In addition, technological advancements play a crucial role in the development of LFM. Projects like the Blockchain-based TSO-DSO flexibility marketplace (EFLEX) aim to demonstrate the trading of FS among TSOs, DSOs, and prosumers in a transparent, secure, and cost-effective manner. By utilizing blockchain technology and smart contracts, EFLEX seeks to enhance the flexibility and coordination of energy flows, contributing to the overall stability of the grid²⁸⁴.

In summary, Romania's efforts to develop LFM encompass regulatory reforms, technological innovations, and strategic planning aiming to create a more adaptable and resilient energy system capable of accommodating the growing share of RES.

²⁸² Final updated NECP 2021=2030

²⁸³ G.Toma, A.Petruț, A.Valeriu *Development of a distributed flexibility services market to be operated by DSO*, EMERG, Vol. IX, Issue 1/2023

²⁸⁴ Mladenov, V.; Chobanov, V.; Seritan, G.C.; Porumb, R.F.; Enache, B.-A.; Vita, V.; Stănculescu, M.; Vu Van, T.; Bargiotas, D. A Flexibility Market Platform for Electricity System Operators Using Blockchain Technology. *Energies* 2022, 15, 539. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15020539>

Transposition of EU regulation

In line with the EU's Renewable Energy Directive (RED II) and the Electricity Market Directive, Romania has taken steps to facilitate the establishment and operation of energy communities.

In December 2021, Romania introduced provisions for CECs through Emergency Ordinance 143/2021, amending the Electricity and Natural Gas Law No. 123/2012. This ordinance incorporates definitions and concepts from the EU regulatory framework, such as active customers, citizen energy communities, and FS.

Emergency Ordinance 163/2022, published in December 2022, established the legal framework for RECs. This ordinance aims to promote the use of energy from renewable sources and aligns national policies with European standards.

For the practical implementation of energy communities in Romania there is a need to make additional legislative efforts in order to overcome some obstacles.

- **Legislative Clarity:** The current legal definitions for CECs and RECs are primarily transpositions of EU directives, lacking detailed national guidelines. This has led to ambiguities, making it challenging for stakeholders to establish energy communities with legal certainty.
- **Regulatory Support:** The National Energy Regulatory Authority (ANRE) is tasked with developing further regulations to allow smooth operation of energy communities. The specific duties to ensure compliance with the definitions are not clearly outlined, potentially hindering effective oversight²⁸⁵.

As of early 2024, there were only two operational energy communities in Romania, with several others in the planning stages. The slow adoption rate is attributed to limited dedicated funding, insufficient technical support, and low public awareness²⁸⁶.

To address these challenges, the Romanian Ministry of Energy has initiated measures to foster the development of energy communities:

In April 2024, a *working group* was established to develop energy communities in Romania. This initiative aims to create a legislative framework that empowers citizens to produce and consume locally generated renewable energy, thereby reducing electricity costs and enhancing energy autonomy.

²⁸⁵ Romania - REC/CEC definitions - REScoop

²⁸⁶ <https://www.legalproadvisory.com/en/blog/65-energie-regenerabila-retrospectiva-2023-2024-romania>

Emergency Ordinance 134/2024, enacted in November 2024, introduced amendments to the Energy Law. These changes aim to ensure the stability of the National Energy System, facilitate the transition to renewable energy, and enhance energy security. Notably, the ordinance clarifies the definition of energy storage and eliminates double charging for stored energy, reducing costs and encouraging investment in storage capacities.

On March 25, 2024 the Contracts for Difference (CfD) Mechanism was launched for a horizon of 15 years by *Government Decision no. 318/2024* approving the general framework for implementing and operating the support mechanism through contracts for difference for low-carbon technologies, effective from April 10, 2024. The Main Goals are: Long-term predictable revenues for producers and encouraging investments in renewable energy, with eligible production technologies including: a) onshore wind resources; b) offshore wind resources; c) PV solar resources; (d) hydro resources; (e) nuclear resources; (f) hydrogen; g) energy storage. Covering a total capacity of 2 GW for the first auction, EC approved a EUR 3 billion aid scheme to stimulate and support investments in this direction. For the second auction in 2025, the targeted total capacity is 3 GW.

In summary, while Romania has made legislative strides to transpose EU regulations on energy communities and flexibility markets, effective implementation requires further regulatory clarity, increased public awareness, and supportive infrastructure development.

4.10.2. Smart Local Flexibility Services - Compliance and Safety

The development of smart FS is guided by a comprehensive In Romania, regulatory framework aimed at ensuring compliance and safety.

The cornerstone of this framework is the Electricity and Gas Law (Law no. 123/2012), which has undergone several amendments to align with EU directives and to address the evolving energy landscape. This law establishes the fundamental principles governing Romania's electricity sector, including the roles and responsibilities of various stakeholders, licensing requirements, and the promotion of RES.

Government Emergency Ordinance No. 143/2021 introduced significant changes to the existing energy law, focusing on the integration of RES and the development of FS. It defines key terms like active customer, citizen energy community, and flexibility service, providing a clear legal basis for their implementation. The ordinance also outlines the roles of DSOs in managing energy storage and FS, ensuring that these activities are conducted safely and efficiently²⁸⁷.

²⁸⁷ [Overview Of The Recent Amendment Of The Energy Law By The Government Emergency Ordinance No. 143/2021 - Energy Law - Romania](#)

Smart FS in Romania are evolving as part of the broader transition to a more sustainable and efficient energy system. These services aim to optimize energy consumption, integrate RES, and enhance grid reliability by allowing for flexible and responsive energy usage.

The Romanian energy regulator (ANRE) has mandated the *roll-out of smart meters* across the country. The roll out rate of smart meters achieved in Romania accounts to 19% in 2022, with a target to reach was 80% in 2025²⁸⁸. These systems have to ensure data protection compliance in line with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) that governs use of personal data.

In Romania, *Demand response* is a key component of smart flexibility, allowing consumers to lower their consumption or shift it to off-peak times in response to market signals or incentives. Some large industrial users and commercial consumers (like Alro Slatina - aluminum producer or ArcelorMittal Galați - steel plant) are already participating in these DR programs, offering their flexibility to the grid. This helps balance supply and demand while reducing the need for additional power plants or energy imports.

Romania is working to integrate *Distributed Energy Resources (DERs)* into its grid. DERs include small-scale generation systems, such as rooftop solar panels, small wind turbines, or even energy storage systems like batteries (VPP projects). These systems provide local flexibility by allowing energy to be produced and consumed locally, reducing the need for energy transport and increasing grid resilience. Romanian regions are piloting community energy projects, where residents and businesses install solar panels and share excess energy within a local grid, thereby improving energy independence and reducing transmission losses.

Energy storage systems, like batteries, are being deployed to store excess energy produced by RES, particularly solar and wind. In some pilot projects, large-scale energy storage installations are being developed to balance the grid during periods of high renewable energy generation. ESS enhances grid flexibility, supports renewable integration, and improves energy security.

The growing adoption of *electric vehicles (EVs)* in Romania is opening new opportunities for FS. Pilot projects in urban areas are exploring the potential of using EV batteries for grid balancing. This system allows vehicles to charge during low demand periods and discharge energy when the grid is under stress.

In Romania, *citizen energy communities* are being encouraged as part of a broader effort to decentralize energy production and consumption. Small towns and villages are starting to form energy communities where locals invest in renewable energy projects, such as solar panel

²⁸⁸ ACER, Data Item Details

installations, and collectively manage their energy resources (Bucharest, Cluj, and Timișoara). This helps create a more resilient and flexible local energy system.

Part of the ENEL Romania group - E-Distribuție Dobrogea has launched *a market for flexibility services* aiming to optimize energy distribution, particularly for the integration of RES like wind power, into the local grid. By managing DERs like solar panels, batteries, and DR, the network becomes more resilient and flexible. The market operates under strict safety protocols and regulatory standards, ensuring that all FS comply with the Romanian Electricity and Gas Law (Law no. 123/2012) and European regulations.

Pilot projects are underway in Romania where *blockchain technology* is being explored to enable decentralized energy trading (EFLEX project). This would allow consumers (prosumer, communities) to sell excess renewable energy generated from home solar systems directly to other consumers in their locality, contributing to energy flexibility. The use of blockchain is being carefully monitored to ensure it complies with Romanian laws around energy trading, data privacy, and financial regulations.

While the regulatory framework provides a solid foundation, several challenges persist:

- The increasing penetration of variable RES necessitates advanced grid management solutions to maintain stability and safety. Developing robust FS is crucial to address the intermittency of renewables.
- The adoption of emerging technologies, such as blockchain and IoT, presents opportunities for decentralized energy management. Ensuring the security and interoperability of these technologies requires continuous effort and collaboration among stakeholders.
- Empowering consumers to become active participants in the energy market, either as prosumers or members of energy communities involves educational initiatives to raise awareness about the benefits and responsibilities associated with active participation.

In summary, Romania's smart FS focus on creating a more flexible, efficient, and sustainable energy system by integrating DR, renewable energy, storage, smart grids, and innovative technologies like blockchain. These initiatives are being developed under a strong regulatory framework to ensure compliance with safety standards and promote the effective transition to a green and flexible energy future.

4.10.3. Business Models and Financing Mechanisms to Boost Stakeholder Motivation

In Romania, the development of LFM is gaining momentum as the energy sector transitions towards decentralized and sustainable models. These markets enable various stakeholders—including consumers, producers, and prosumers—to actively participate in energy trading and grid stability efforts.

Business models

- *Energy communities and Prosumers in Romania* are collaborative networks where local stakeholders, such as residents, businesses, and authorities, collectively manage energy production and consumption. Despite being in the early stages, the growth of energy communities is supported by legislative frameworks like GEO nr. 143/2021, which defines their structure and roles. However, challenges persist, including the need for a cohesive legislative framework, financial incentives, and increased community awareness. Addressing these issues could foster a more decentralized and sustainable energy future in Romania²⁸⁹.
- *Aggregator Models* consolidate multiple small-scale energy resources to participate effectively in the energy market. For instance, Nano Energies, licensed in December 2023 as an independent electricity aggregator, offers services that allow companies to manage energy consumption and production efficiently. By remotely operating clients' equipment, Nano Energies helps balance the grid and provides additional revenue streams for participants. This model not only supports grid stability but also offers financial benefits to businesses contributing FS²⁹⁰.
- *DSO Initiatives*: Romanian DSOs are exploring the development of distributed FS markets to manage grid congestion and integrate RES more effectively. A notable example is E-Distribuție Dobrogea, part of the ENEL Romania group, which operates a 110 kV network heavily loaded with wind power generators. This approach involves creating platforms where FS can be traded, thereby improving the efficiency and reliability of the distribution network²⁹¹.
- *The Energy-as-a-Service (EaaS) Model* offers businesses access to renewable energy solutions without upfront investments. Companies like nextE develop, finance, and operate PV plants either on-site or off-site, providing clients with renewable energy tailored to their consumption needs. This approach enables industrial and commercial

²⁸⁹ <https://issuemonitoring.eu/en/energy-communities-in-romania-the-path-forward-for-a-decentralized-and-sustainable-future>

²⁹⁰ Nano Energies enters the Romanian market with energy consumption and production management services, 23.01.2024

²⁹¹ Development of a distributed flexibility services market to be operated by a romanian distribution system operator, 2023

consumers to benefit from sustainable energy sources, reduce costs, and minimize operational risks associated with energy management²⁹².

While these business models present significant opportunities for advancing Romania's energy transition, there are some issues that still need to be tackled in the coming years. The existing policies need to evolve to support innovative business models and ensure a level playing field for all market participants.

Enhanced financial mechanisms are necessary to encourage investments in FS and renewable energy projects. Enhancing the existing grid infrastructure to support decentralized energy resources and adopting advanced digital technologies are essential moves forward.

Financing mechanisms to boost stakeholder motivation

LFMs in Romania need strong financial mechanisms to encourage participation from key stakeholders, such as energy producers, aggregators, DSOs, and consumers. Here are some financing mechanisms that could boost stakeholder motivation:

Regulatory Incentives & Subsidies: DSOs and TSOs could offer fixed payments (Capacity Payments) to participants who commit to providing FS. The Romanian government or EU funds could support investment in grid upgrades, smart meters, and digital platforms for LFMs in the form of subsidies for Smart Grid Investments.

Contracts for Difference (CfD) Mechanism: In September 2024, Romania, with support from the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD), launched a CfD scheme to encourage investments in renewable energy. The first auction offered 1.5 GW of renewable energy capacities—500 MW for solar PV and 1 GW for onshore wind. This mechanism provides revenue stability to developers, thereby motivating participation in energy flexibility initiatives²⁹³.

EU Funding & Grants: Horizon Europe & Innovation Funds support pilot projects and innovative energy flexibility solutions. Modernization Fund and Just Transition Fund finance LFM-related infrastructure in Romania's coal-transition regions.

In Romania the Modernization Fund supports investments in renewable energy and energy storage. In July 2024, the Ministry of Energy signed 24 financing contracts totalling EUR 3.6 million to develop 9.5 MW of renewable energy capacity for self-consumption by public entities.

²⁹² [nextE to expand on the Romanian renewable energy market with the Energy as a Service approach](#), 27.06.2023

²⁹³ [With EBRD support, Romania launches renewable energy auctions](#), 11.09.2024

This fund aids stakeholders in upgrading infrastructure and integrating flexible energy solutions.²⁹⁴

Approved by the Romanian government in April 2024, the ElectricUp program offers grants up to EUR 150,000 to SMEs and businesses in the HoReCa sector. These funds support the installation of PV panels and electric vehicle charging stations, promoting decentralized energy production and flexibility at the consumer level²⁹⁵.

Performance-Based Contracts: Under the Pay-for-Performance contract market participants receive payments based on the actual flexibility delivered to the grid. Consumers and industries can get financial rewards for reducing consumption during peak periods when participating in Demand Response Programs.

Green Bonds & Private Investments: Private investors and banks can issue green bonds to finance LFM infrastructure. In the form of Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) joint investments between the government and private sector can boost the deployment of LFMs.

Blockchain & Tokenization for Flexibility Trading: Participants can trade FS using digital assets, increasing liquidity and financial attractiveness by Energy Tokens. Decentralized Finance (DeFi) like peer-to-peer financial platforms could facilitate small-scale investments in FS.

Tax Incentives & Carbon Pricing: Companies participating in LFMs could receive tax incentives in the form of Tax Breaks for Flexibility Providers. LFMs could be linked with Romania's carbon trading mechanisms to create additional revenue streams (Carbon Market Integration).

Implementing diverse financing mechanisms that encourage stakeholder participation in energy flexibility, Romania can foster a more resilient and flexible energy system, leveraging LFMs to integrate RES effectively and engage a broader range of stakeholders in the energy sector.

4.10.4. Awareness & Actions to Ensure High Customer Participation in the LFMs

In Romania, ensuring high customer participation in LFMs requires a combination of awareness-building initiatives and strategic actions to encourage engagement.

The **awareness** strategies include:

²⁹⁴ Ministry of Energy: 24 financing contracts through the Modernization Fund for investments in RE and energy storage, July 16, 2024

²⁹⁵ Grants up to €150,000 for Romanian SMEs for green energy transition, Green Forum, 24 April, 2024

- *Educational Campaigns* like launching national and regional awareness campaigns through TV, social media, and industry conferences.
- *Workshops & Training Programs*: Conduct webinars and local events to educate industrial consumers, businesses, and residential users. ANRE (Romania's Energy Regulatory Authority) partners with energy providers for hands-on training sessions.
- *Collaboration with Local Authorities and Businesses*: municipalities and industrial parks have to be engaged to promote LFM as a tool for cost savings and sustainability. Cluj-Napoca municipality incentivizes companies to participate in flexibility programs.
- *Transparent Communication of Benefits*: It is useful to provide clear case studies and real-world benefits of participating in LFMs, such as cost reductions and incentives. Enel Romania publishes a report on how businesses can reduce energy costs by 20% through FS.

Actions to Ensure High Customer Participation:

- *Financial Incentives and Dynamic Pricing*: Attractive compensation models for flexibility providers can be introduced like time-of-use tariffs rewarding consumers for reducing demand during peak hours.
- *User-Friendly Digital Platforms*: Mobile applications and online platforms that simplify LFM participation and offer real-time data insights have to be developed. For example Electrica²⁹⁶ launched a customer-friendly portal for energy trading and flexibility offers.
- *Demand Response Programs* encourage large consumers (factories, shopping malls) to adjust their energy consumption in exchange for financial rewards. Buzău's industrial zone participating in demand response programs for grid stability²⁹⁷.
- *Regulatory Support, Simplification*: bureaucratic barriers have to be reduced and the enrolment process for customers simplified. ANRE to introduce a streamlined registration process for LFM participants.
- *Integration with Smart Grids and IoT*: Leverage smart meters, AI-driven analytics, and IoT devices to optimize energy use. A pilot project in Timișoara used AI to predict and manage flexibility demand.

A successful LFM strategy in Romania depends on educating consumers, offering incentives, and leveraging digital technology. By implementing these measures, both residential and industrial users can be encouraged to actively participate in flexibility markets, ultimately leading to a more efficient and resilient energy system.

²⁹⁶ [Retele Electrice România offers suppliers a new modern platform for accessing customer consumption data](#)

²⁹⁷ [ROMANIA: Resolv Energy will connect the 450 MW Vifor wind farm in Buzau to the grid at the end of next year-ENERGY WORLD - ROMANIA](#)

4.10.5. Strategic Planning Documents

Romania's energy ambitions are linked with the EU's energy and climate policy objectives to achieve carbon neutrality by 2050 in line with the European Green Deal. This ambitious goal necessitates the energy sector transformation in Romania, following the EU directives and regulations within the Clean Energy for All Europeans Package. The relevant national strategic documents that contribute to these objectives include:

*Romania's Recovery and Resilience Plan*²⁹⁸ was approved by the EC in November 2021, and revised on 8 December 2023 to introduce a REPowerEU chapter foreseeing 66 reforms and 111 investments to be taken with the objective to make Romania more sustainable, resilient and better prepared for the challenges and opportunities of the green transition by August 2026. 44.1% of the planned investments support sustainable transport / urban mobility, building renovation, biodiversity protection, industry decarbonisation and deployment of renewables (phasing-out of coal and lignite power production, deployment of various RES, and hydrogen).

*Romania's Just Transition Programme*²⁹⁹ helps the transition to a climate-neutral economy by 2050. Some areas to be supported in six Romanian counties are: development of renewable energy projects, such as solar and wind farms; improvement of energy efficiency in buildings, industry, and transport; creation of green jobs in the renewable energy sector, energy efficiency sector, and other sectors that are helping to reduce greenhouse gas emissions.

*Romania General Transport Master Plan*³⁰⁰ adopted by the Government in September 2016 and covering a 15-year period (until 2030) provides a clear strategy for the development of Romania's transport sector for the next 20 years promoting efficient transport modes, reducing GHG emissions, and enhancing connectivity.

*The National Strategy for Adaptation to Climate Change for the period 2024-2030*³⁰¹, with a perspective towards 2050 and the *National Action Plan for Adaptation to Climate Change*³⁰² are based on the key international and European policy frameworks providing strategic guidelines for adaptation to climate change effects, integrating findings from extensive studies on climate variability and projected changes up to 2050.

²⁹⁸ [Romania's recovery and resilience plan - European Commission](#)

²⁹⁹ [Following the money: Romania : Just Transition](#)

³⁰⁰ https://2015-2019.kormany.hu/download/4/5c/20000/RO_kozlekedesi_strategia_es_kornyezeti_ertekeles_osszefoglalo_2014_nov_EN.pdf

³⁰¹ [STRATEGY 14/08/2024 - Legislative Portal](#)

³⁰² [Microsoft Word - National Action Plan on Climate Change of Romania.doc](#)

Romania's Long-term Strategy³⁰³, adopted in 2023, sets a target of achieving climate neutrality by 2050, provides a framework for interim targets, and proposes policies to achieve a cohesive and sustainable approach to climate change mitigation.

The Integrated National Energy and Climate Plan of Romania 2025-2030 Update³⁰⁴ serves as a blueprint for aligning national energy and climate priorities with EU objectives, ensuring that Romania contributes to the EU's collective climate and energy goals while addressing its specific national challenges. Romania's NECP is structured along the following lines:

- **Renewable Energy Expansion:** A substantial increase in the share of RES within its energy mix by extending to various renewable sources, including wind and solar power, biomass, and hydropower is envisaged. The wind potential, especially in regions like Dobrogea, is a focal point for wind energy development. Biomass and hydropower are also part of the strategy, aiming to further diversify the renewable energy portfolio.
- **Fostering Energy Efficiency:** These measures include the retrofitting of buildings for improved energy performance and the modernization of industrial processes to minimize energy consumption. The goal is to optimize energy use, reduce waste, and lower energy costs for businesses and households.
- **Emissions Reduction:** Romania is committed to reducing greenhouse gas emissions across industrial, transportation, and residential sectors adopting cleaner technologies and practices, thereby mitigating the environmental impact of economic activities.
- **Just Transition:** This entails supporting communities and workers affected by the shift to a climate-neutral economy by increasing the level of employment through investment measures in upskilling, developing skills for green jobs and the circular economy, and/or providing support and active measures to aid job seekers.
- **Infrastructure Development:** This encompasses enhancements to the energy grid, interconnection projects to improve regional and cross-border energy flows, and the development of electric vehicle charging networks. The aim is to ensure a robust and reliable energy system capable of accommodating the increased capacity of RES and facilitating the transition to electric mobility.

The NECP main objectives and targets regarding RES are summarised in Table 13.

Romania plans to reach at least 38.3% of renewable energy in gross final energy consumption by 2030. Increased wind and solar energy generation capacities, along with heat pumps for heating and cooling will contribute significantly to this percentage to reach 31.0% by 2025. The

³⁰³ [Romania's Long-Term Strategy for Reducing Greenhouse Gas Emissions - Climate Change Laws of the World](#)

³⁰⁴ [Integrated National Energy and Climate Plan updated , October 2024](#)

estimated share of RES in the transport sector has to reach 29.4% in 2030, which will be obtained mainly by increasing the use of electricity in this sector (Figure 6).

The RES share in the electricity sector has also to increase by 2030, reaching 57.8% in 2030, as a result of the construction of new RES (mainly wind and solar) capacities for electricity generation, the RES share in the heating and cooling sector may slightly increase throughout the whole analysed period, reaching 41.1% in 2030 (See Figure 6).

Source: 2015-2022 SHARE tool EUROSTAT, 2023-2030 LEAP-RO model,

Note: Data after 2023 include heat pumps which are not included in the SHARE tool for the period 2015-2022

Figure 6: Estimated trajectories for the share of renewable energy in final energy consumption in the electricity, heating and cooling and transport sectors

Based on the guiding principle of prioritizing energy efficiency, the primary energy consumption target for Romania, according to the recast EED from 2023, is set at 30.2 Mtoe with projections showing that this target may be achieved in 2030 with 9% reduction compared to 2022. Similarly, final energy consumption is expected to have a decrease of 6% in 2030, implementing measures to increase the share of energy produced from RES.

By 2050, Romania plans to lower its primary energy consumption by 25%, while the final energy consumption is projected to decrease further by 28% compared to the 2022 level of consumption. These targets reflect a dedicated commitment to a sustainable greener future.

Table 13: Romania NECP targets by 2030

Renewable Energy	%
National target for the share of energy from RES in gross final energy consumption	38.3
Share of electricity from RES in gross final consumption of electricity	57.8
Share of heating and cooling from RES in gross final consumption of heating and cooling	41.1
Share of energy from renewable sources in final energy consumption in the transport sector	29.4
Energy Efficiency	
Reduction in primary energy consumption	52
Reduction in final energy consumption	47
Net Greenhouse Gas Emission	
Net GHG emission reduction compared to the 1990 level	85
GHG emission reduction in energy by decommissioning coal/lignite fired power plants and building RES	87

4.10.6. Policy Guidelines for Facilitating Deployment of LFM and Exploitation of Flexibility

To effectively enable LFM in Romania, it's essential to establish a comprehensive regulatory framework that promotes flexibility, encourages investment, and ensures efficient market operations. The following recommendations are proposed:

- **Align National Policies with European Directives**

Ensure that Romania's regulatory framework for LFM is consistent with EU directives and regulations. This alignment facilitates cross-border cooperation, attracts investment, and promotes best practices in FS. The recent amendments to Romania's Energy Law via Government Emergency Ordinance No. 143/2021 were aimed at transposing provisions of Directive (EU) 2019/944, ensuring compliance with EU regulations and promoting a competitive internal energy market.

- **Clear Legal Framework for Flexibility Services**

Romania should define FS within its national legislation by establishing the roles and responsibilities for all market participants, such as DSOs, TSOs, aggregators, and prosumers. The framework should facilitate the integration of flexible resources like DR, energy storage, and distributed generation into the energy market. The Government Emergency Ordinance No. 143/2021 amended Romania's Energy Law to align with Directive (EU) 2019/944, introduced concepts like active customers and CECs, aiming to empower consumers to participate actively in the energy market, and laying the groundwork for FS.

Develop policies that support the deployment of energy storage systems, including removing double taxation on stored energy and providing incentives for storage infrastructure development³⁰⁵. Permit DSOs and TSOs to own and manage energy storage installations under specific conditions, enhancing grid stability and flexibility³⁰⁶.

- **Market-Based Mechanisms for Flexibility Procurement**

Establish transparent and competitive platforms where FS can be traded. This involves creating standardized products and contracts that allow flexibility providers to offer services to DSOs and TSOs, ensuring grid stability and efficient energy use.

Define the roles and responsibilities of aggregators who can pool resources from multiple consumers and producers to participate in flexibility markets. Create pathways for aggregators to offer bundled FS, enhancing market efficiency and resource optimization.

Introduce dynamic electricity pricing to reflect real-time supply and demand conditions, encouraging consumers to adjust usage patterns and provide flexibility. Enable consumers to engage in contracts with dynamic pricing terms, fostering active participation in flexibility markets.

- **Grid Infrastructure and Digitalization:**

Invest in the development of *smart grids* equipped with advanced metering and communication technologies to monitor and manage DER effectively. This infrastructure is essential for the accurate measurement and verification of FS, ensuring that participants are compensated fairly.

Establish robust data management systems to handle the increased data flow from various market participants, ensuring security and privacy. Establish robust data management protocols to enable real-time monitoring and control of energy flows.

Develop protocols that ensure effective communication and coordination between TSOs and DSOs. This collaboration is crucial for managing flexibility resources efficiently, preventing conflicts, and maintaining grid stability. Example: The EFLEX project aims to demonstrate a blockchain-based platform in Romania and Bulgaria, enabling TSOs and DSOs to trade FS with prosumers. This initiative seeks to enhance coordination and streamline energy flows on the network³⁰⁷.

³⁰⁵ <https://www.tpa-group.ro/news/harmonisation-of-the-legislative-framework-on-electricity-and-natural-gas>

³⁰⁶ <https://brcconline.eu/overview-of-the-recent-amendment-of-the-energy-law-by-the-government-emergency-ordinance-no-143-2021>

³⁰⁷ <https://www.mdpi.com/1996-1073/15/2/539>

- **Financial Incentives and Support Mechanisms**

Introduce *subsidies, grants, or tax incentives* to encourage investment in technologies and projects that offer FS. Financial support can accelerate the adoption of energy storage systems, demand response programs, and other flexible resources.

Example: Romania's "Casa Verde Fotovoltaice" program offers non-reimbursable funding to prosumers for installing PV panels, promoting distributed generation and potential participation in flexibility markets³⁰⁸.

Support *R&D initiatives* focused on innovative flexibility technologies and business models.

- **Energy Communities and Prosumers**

Support the development of CEC and REC by providing a *regulatory framework* that facilitates their creation and operation. These communities can aggregate flexible resources, participate in LFM, and enhance local energy resilience.

Example: The National Authority for Energy Regulation in Romania (ANRE) proposed models for energy communities, offering frameworks that empower local stakeholders to generate, manage, and consume renewable energy collectively. This initiative aligns with the goals of decentralizing energy systems and promoting local flexibility³⁰⁹.

Implement streamlined processes - simplified procedures - for prosumers to connect to the grid, including simplified notification procedures for small-scale installations³¹⁰.

- **Consumer Protection**

Protect consumer interests by enforcing transparency in pricing and ensuring access to dispute resolution mechanisms.

By implementing these recommendations, Romania can create a robust regulatory environment that facilitates the development and operation of LFM, contributing to a more resilient and efficient energy system.

In conclusion, Romania's renewable energy sector faces challenges that are common globally. Key impediments include regulatory changes creating investor uncertainty, lengthy and complex permitting processes causing delays and higher costs, and limited grid capacity with technical challenges. Ambiguity in regulatory procedures, financing difficulties for smaller

³⁰⁸ <https://iclg.com/practice-areas/renewable-energy-laws-and-regulations/romania>

³⁰⁹ <https://interreg-danube.eu/projects/nrgcom/news/anre-proposes-new-models-for-energy-communities-in-romania>

³¹⁰ <https://www.ccifer.ro/actualites/n/news/recent-changes-to-the-legal-framework-for-promoting-the-use-of-energy-from-RES.html>

developers, and a shortage of skilled professionals also hinder progress. Additionally, delays in securing necessary technology components and equipment, particularly for emerging technologies, impede development. Legislative and regulatory support is crucial to overcome these obstacles and support sector growth.

5. POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS FOR ENABLING REGULATIONS OF THE LFMS IN EUROPE

As seen in Table 14 and Figure 7 there are considerable differences in the state and ambitions of the examined countries which are based on their energy policy, economic and technological condition and trends of development of RES.

5.1. Main Objectives of the Countries under Scrutiny for 2030

Table 14: National targets for 2030 in the EU countries' updated NECPs and in Türkiye (%)

TARGETS BY 2030	EU*	BG	GR	IE	PT	ES	FR	IT	NL	RO	TR
Share of RES in GFEC	42.4 (45)	34.5	43	30.9	51	48	41.3	40	39	38.3	50
Share of RES - E in GFEC	69 Not explicitly stated	55.5	75.7	68.9	93	81	35	65	75	57.8	na
Share of RES H&C in GFEC	49 In buildings	43.7	52.6	21.7	47	35	45	37	32	41.1	na
Share of RES - T in GFEC	29	29.7	13.4	16.3	23	28	-	31	40	29.4	na
Reduction of PEC/FEC (EE saving)	11.7 in FEC	11.6 PEC 10.7 FEC	-	20.1 PEC 12.7 FEC***	35	39.5 PEC 43 FEC	30 To 2012 level	-	-	47 in FEC	16
CO2 Reduction	55**	10 Relative to 2005	58	42 Relative to 2005	45-55	32	50	66	55	85	21

*Calculation according to RED III projections, using Eurostat Sharestool Draft_version 5, as stated in [Greece NECP](#)

** Reduction of GHG emissions by 1990 * (with LULUCF)

*** Relative to 2022

In regard to the targets in the national NECPs about the share of RES in the final energy consumption for 2030 Spain, Portugal and Greece plan to achieve the objectives of the EU, and even strive to reach the desirable 45%. France, Italy, the Netherlands and Romania tend to almost fulfil the EU targets, Ireland and Bulgaria do not reach the EU goal and actions will be needed in order to comply with the EU requirements. Türkiye has a very ambitious goal to reach 50% share of renewables in the final energy consumption in 2030 and 80% in 2053.

The targets of the share of RES-E in the final energy consumption for 2030 of Greece, Portugal, Spain, the Netherlands and Ireland are in line with the EU ones, but Bulgaria, France, Romania and Italy do not plan to achieve the EU objectives in share of electricity from RES.

The target of the share of RES-H&C in the final energy consumption for 2030 in Greece is the highest (52.6%). In Bulgaria, Portugal, France and Romania it is from 41.1% to 47% which is near to the EU objective of 49%. The target to be achieved in Ireland, Spain, Italy and the Netherlands is lower.

5.2 Demand Side Flexibility in the Examined Countries

The 2023 Market Monitor for Demand Side Flexibility of SMARTEN (Fig.7) shows that France and the Netherlands (in addition to Great Britain, Germany, Belgium and Sweden) have high development of the demand side flexibility, the other examined countries have moderate to low level of development.

Source: [smarten.eu/2023 Market Monitor for Demand Side Flexibility](https://smarten.eu/2023-Market-Monitor-for-Demand-Side-Flexibility)

Figure 7: Current state of demand side flexibility in EU

With the increase of RES the demand side flexibility is growing and mechanisms like dynamic pricing or market-based mechanisms are needed. Based on these two mechanisms, there are implicit DR when consumers choose to be exposed to time-varying electricity prices and/or network tariffs, and explicit DR, when consumers choose to participate in energy markets (e.g. through an aggregator) and receive payments in return for the load offered on the market.

With the Clean Energy Package, every energy user is entitled to access at least one energy supplier with dynamic pricing contracts, and every energy supplier with over 200,000 customers should include a dynamic tariff in their range of offers. Dynamic tariff is a means to better manage the energy issue of secure, sustainable, affordable energy.

As stated in the Internal Market for Electricity Directive (IMED), dynamic pricing is a central demand response tool for the European Union to meet its renewable energy targets and manage high energy costs and equal access to energy. It is the key to participating in demand response and smart meters rollout has to be accomplished for that reason in Europe as they can have significant impact on how effective dynamic tariffs can be. Dynamic tariffs motivate consumers to engage with and better manage their energy consumption. Currently Spain, Italy, France and the Netherlands offer dynamic contracts, in Portugal they are allowed by law but there are no offers, and Greece intends to offer them from 2025.

IMED entitles all final customers who have a smart meter installed to conclude a dynamic electricity price contract with a supplier. The rollout of smart meters in Western Europe and the Nordics is well advanced or largely completed; in the East and Southeast European countries the process is underway. Spain, Italy, the Netherlands have full rollout of smart meters, France and Portugal have also almost finalised it. Ireland has reached 57% rollout of smart meters, Romania - 19%, Greece - 4% in 2023. Bulgaria recently started the installation of smart meters; Türkiye plans to achieve 80% rollout in 2035.

In addition, the flexibility potential of the demand side has not yet been fully exploited. The demand response programmes have not been fully realised in practice and different barriers exist. Among others, these include a fragmented regulatory framework and a lack of market products suitable for small end users, although they can access markets through aggregators; roles and responsibilities of traditional and new market players like demand-side aggregators are still unclear.

New flexibility products and marketplaces, development of new digital platforms enabling the aggregation of flexibility from small end users and its trading on energy markets can represent a new business case for market players such as retailers and producers.³¹¹

5.3 Harmonisation of National Legislations

Countries need further to work on the harmonization with EU energy directives (e.g., Clean Energy Package, Electricity Market Design). A *standardized legal framework* has to be developed to define LFM and their role in the electricity system, as well as the roles and responsibilities for Distribution System Operators, energy communities, aggregators, and flexibility providers.

The countries have to further work on transposing the new Electricity Market design rules into national law, namely the new provisions of the amending Directive EU/2024/1711 that specifically concern the *dynamic pricing contracts*, in order to benefit from price variability to use electricity when it is cheaper, and to solve the issue of energy sharing, for example, to be able to share surplus rooftop solar power with a neighbour.

Countries should align their national laws with EU directives to provide *clear definitions and operational frameworks for RECs and CECs*. The transposition of EU directives into national legislation varies among member states.

³¹¹ F. D'Ettoire, M. Banaei, R. Ebrahimi, S. Ali Pourmousavi, E.M.V. Blomgren, J. Kowalski, Z. Bohdanowicz, B. Łopaciuk-Gonczaryk, C. Biele, H. Madse, Exploiting demand-side flexibility: State-of-the-art, open issues and social perspective - ScienceDirect; Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews Volume 165, September 2022, 112605

Figure 8: REScoop Transposition Tracker of REC/CEC definitions, 2024

There are currently many different forms of energy communities across Europe - their total number is estimated to be over 9000. However, the binding EU regulation of RED II on their non-discriminatory treatment has not yet been implemented in many cases. The framework conditions are very different in many EU countries and there are numerous obstacles and challenges. In some countries, such as Spain, Portugal and France, there is already a separate legal framework for energy communities, while in some other countries this is currently being developed.

Figure 8 presents the progress of the transposition of the provisions on definitions for RECs and CECs, and there is a similar assessment about the enabling frameworks and national support schemes for RECs and CECs under the first generation EU energy communities' legislation in the European countries.

Based on the trackers' assessment it can be stated that France and Spain have good progress; Italy, the Netherlands, Portugal, Ireland and Greece achieve moderate progress; Bulgaria and Romania still have substantial deficiencies. The review of Turkish legislation under RED II and IEMD 2019 reveals that the adoption of the energy communities' concepts and the requirements are not met, except for cursory regulations on energy cooperatives.

Most countries have to further *develop an enabling framework* allowing energy communities to participate in the market without discrimination compared to other market actors. Barriers that still exist include issues with accessing the grid, lack of funding opportunities, and complex administrative and regulatory procedures.

Since the CEP, Europe has experienced a global crisis and the European policymakers have worked on solutions like the Fit for 55 (2021) and the REPowerEU (2022) Packages, and the revision of the Electricity Market Design. These laws reinforce the model of energy communities, further acknowledging that citizens no longer need to depend on corporate power for their renewable electricity, heating, or renovations. The second-generation EU legislation for energy communities clarifies that citizen-led initiatives actively contribute to activities that include renovations, energy efficiency, heating and cooling, and the alleviation of energy poverty.

5.4 Simplification of Administrative Procedures

Streamlining bureaucratic processes can further facilitate the establishment and operation of energy communities. Bureaucratic burdens, non-transparent processes, a lack of legal coherence and an incomplete framework and guidelines that lead to unclear interpretations of existing legislation by the competent authorities slow down the process of RES development for citizens and businesses. In some countries there is a lack of support from policy decision makers or opposition from public or private institutions (i.e. in case of wind power) due to a lack of necessary experience or technical skills. Issues related to grid connections and operation procedures very often result from inadequate grid capacities delaying RE projects deployment.

The revised RED (Directive 2023/2413 amending Directive 2018/2001) entered into force in November 2023 and certain provisions had to be transposed into national law by 1 July 2024. These provisions include measures *to simplify and accelerate permitting procedures* both for RE projects and for the necessary infrastructure projects to integrate the additional RE into the electricity system. RED aims to shorten permit-granting procedures for RE installations, in particular thanks to the provision to identify renewable acceleration areas as well as to specific

rules for solar installations with low capacity³¹², which are very relevant for energy communities.

To simplify administrative and validation processes, EU Member States have implemented one-stop shops (OSS) for energy communities at national, regional, or municipal levels. This approach enhances the monitoring of energy community development, facilitates interactions with public authorities, and streamlines specific administrative procedures.

Developing standardized frameworks and taxonomies for LFM can reduce complexity and promote broader participation. Research has proposed multi-layered taxonomies focusing on congestion management at the distribution level, aiding in the design and implementation of effective LFMs³¹³.

The European Commission's RES Simplify project offers guidance to Member States on addressing bottlenecks related to permitting and grid connection procedures. By drawing on examples from various EU countries, the project aims to simplify these processes, thereby accelerating the deployment of renewable energy projects.³¹⁴

Market Access and Participation

Transparent and open access rules for all market participants, including prosumers, storage operators, and demand-side response providers should be ensured. This includes:

- simplified entry requirements to reduce bureaucratic hurdles for small-scale flexibility providers, including energy communities and households;
- standardized market rules to ensure a uniform regulatory framework across all EU member states to avoid market fragmentation;
- data-sharing frameworks establishing clear protocols for real-time data exchange between TSOs, DSOs, and market participants.

Good example is the Piclo Flex platform³¹⁵ that provides an open marketplace for distributed flexibility services, allowing storage operators, demand response providers, and prosumers to participate in flexibility tenders.

³¹² Article 16. European Parliament and Council (2023a). Dir. (EU) 2023/2413 of 18/10/2023 amending Dir.(EU) 2018/2001, Reg.(EU) 2018/1999 and Dir.98/70/EC as regards the promotion of RES energy, and repealing Council Directive (EU) 2015/652, Official journal of EU.

³¹³<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306261923015672>

³¹⁴ https://www.researchgate.net/publication/376550604_Technical_support_for_RES_policy_development_and_implementation_-_Simplification_of_permission_and_administrative_procedures_for_RES_installations_RES_Simplify_Final_report

³¹⁵ [Piclo Flex – Leading end-to-end marketplace for local flexibility](#)

Develop incentive mechanisms to encourage participation in LFM, such as dynamic pricing and flexibility contracts.

- Dynamic pricing models to implement real-time or time-of-use tariffs to incentivize flexible energy consumption;
- Flexibility contracts that offer long-term agreements between DSOs and flexibility providers to ensure a stable revenue stream;
- Capacity-based remuneration to reward energy storage and demand-side response participants for availability, not just activation.

Example: In France, the NEBEF (Notification d'Échanges de Blocs d'Énergie de Flexibilité)³¹⁶ mechanism allows demand response providers to sell flexibility directly on the electricity market, creating financial incentives for participation.

5.5 Support to the Flexibility Providers

Implement remuneration schemes (e.g., capacity payments, locational price signals) to attract investment in flexibility resources.

- Capacity Payments: Offer financial compensation for flexibility providers who commit to being available when needed (e.g., peak demand hours).
- Locational Price Signals: Implement price signals that reflect grid congestion levels, incentivizing flexibility in areas where it is most needed.
- Market-based Compensation: Allow demand-side response and storage operators to bid into capacity and balancing markets, ensuring fair payment for their services.

Example: Germany's Grid Booster Initiative³¹⁷ supports large-scale battery storage deployment by providing locational incentives to relieve grid congestion.

Encourage the deployment of DERs like batteries, EVs, and demand-side response programs.

- Investment Support by providing grants and low-interest loans for battery storage, EV charging infrastructure, and smart grid technologies.
- Regulatory Sandboxes by creating controlled environments where DERs can participate in LFM without full regulatory constraints, allowing innovation to thrive.
- Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) Programs to enable electric vehicles to provide flexibility services by storing and discharging energy based on grid demand.

³¹⁶ [Mécanisme NEBEF - Réseau Electrique | Enedis](#)

³¹⁷ [Grid booster - Innovation - Portrait - Company - TransnetBW](#)

Example: The UK's Power Potential Project³¹⁸ allows small-scale energy resources to provide flexibility services to the transmission grid, ensuring better DER integration.

Grid Infrastructure and Digitalization for LFM's Enhancement

Investment in Smart Grids and Digital Platforms

- Upgrade of grid Infrastructure by deploying advanced sensors, smart meters, and automation tools to optimize real-time energy flow and flexibility services.
- Real-Time Data Exchange by developing digital platforms that allow TSOs, DSOs, and flexibility providers to share real-time grid data efficiently.
- AI & Machine Learning for Grid Management by utilising AI-driven predictive analytics to optimize demand response, congestion management, and asset utilization.

Example: Italy's Areti Smart Grid Project³¹⁹ enhances distribution grid efficiency through digitalization, predictive maintenance, and automation technologies.

Support Standardization of Flexibility Trading

- Interoperable Platforms: Ensure different flexibility market platforms can communicate using standardized protocols and data formats.
- Integration with Wholesale Markets by facilitating flexibility provider participation in national and regional electricity markets, enhancing liquidity.

Example: The EU's OneNet Project³²⁰ is working on a unified digital architecture for electricity markets to improve coordination between TSOs and DSOs.

Strengthen Cybersecurity for Digital Energy Transactions

- Robust Cybersecurity Standards: EU-wide cybersecurity guidelines for digital energy platforms, ensuring resilience against cyber threats need to be established.
- Blockchain for Secure Transactions: The use of decentralized ledger technology (DLT) to enhance trust, transparency, and security in flexibility transactions need to be explored.
- Regular Cyber Risk Assessments: Mandatory risk evaluations for grid operators and flexibility market participants have to be implemented.

Example: Spain's Red Eléctrica³²¹ Cybersecurity Initiative integrates advanced threat detection and response systems to protect digital grid operations.

³¹⁸ [Power Potential - UKPN Innovation](#)

³¹⁹ [RomeFlex, il progetto per i servizi di flessibilità locale | Areti](#)

³²⁰ [Homepage - OneNet Project](#)

³²¹ [Our services | Redeia](#)

Promotion of Fair Competition and Consumer Protection in LFM

Establishment of Transparent Pricing Mechanisms

- Standardized Market Rules by defining clear methodologies for pricing flexibility services to ensure fair compensation for all participants.
- Real-Time & Locational Pricing by implementing dynamic pricing that reflects grid congestion and supply-demand conditions, ensuring fair market value.
- Regulatory Oversight by strengthening market monitoring to prevent price manipulation and unfair practices.

Example: Nord Pool's Market Model ensures transparent pricing for electricity markets across Nordic and Baltic countries, allowing flexibility providers to compete fairly.

Development of Consumer Education & Engagement Programs

- Public Awareness Campaigns: Launching educational initiatives to help households, businesses, and energy communities understand the benefits of LFM.
- Simplified Participation Processes: Reduction of the technical and regulatory complexities for consumers to participate in flexibility markets.
- Consumer Incentives by providing financial rewards or subsidies for households and businesses that actively engage in demand-side flexibility.

Example: The UK's "Power Responsive" Program³²² educates businesses on demand-side response opportunities, increasing participation in flexibility markets.

5.6 Strengthening the Coordination between Stakeholders in LFM

Encouraged Collaboration between Key Stakeholders

- Regular Multi-Stakeholder Dialogues by establishing forums where national regulators, DSOs, TSOs, flexibility providers, and energy communities can align on market needs.
- Joint Planning & Investment Strategies to ensure coordinated grid investments between TSOs and DSOs to optimize flexibility resources and avoid costly grid reinforcements.
- Integrated Flexibility Market Models by developing frameworks that allow both DSOs and TSOs to procure flexibility services in a coordinated way.

³²² Power Responsive | National Energy System Operator

Example: The Dutch GOPACS (Grid Operators Platform for Congestion Solutions)³²³ facilitates collaboration between TSOs and DSOs to optimize congestion management and market-based flexibility solutions.

Establish Data-Sharing Protocols for Transparency & Efficiency

- Standardized Data Formats to ensure that flexibility providers, TSOs, DSOs, and market operators use common data formats to improve interoperability.
- Real-Time Data Access to enable market participants to access real-time grid and price data to optimize their flexibility offerings.
- Consumer Data Protection by implementing strict cybersecurity and privacy regulations to safeguard consumer energy data.

Example: The EU Common Information Model (CIM)³²⁴ supports standardized data exchange across different electricity market participants, enhancing transparency and interoperability.

By adopting these recommendations, EU countries can enhance the effectiveness of LFM, contributing to a more decentralized and sustainable energy system able to enhance the RES development.

³²³ [GOPACS - Platform voor congestiemanagement.](#)

³²⁴ [Common Information Model \(CIM\)](#)

6. CONCLUSIONS

Ensuring high-quality regulation for the Energy Transition must keep pace with rapid technological advancements and increasing globalization, both of which create significant challenges in determining the direction that has to be followed. Global demand for electricity is growing rapidly as a result of the efforts for industrial decarbonisation, development of electromobility and energy storage and rapid penetration of artificial intelligence. This is a serious challenge for the entire chain from production through distribution and supply to electricity trading.

The legislative changes identified in the report enable a standardized approach to the role of customers, allowing for their improved integration into electricity markets. By rationalising specific regulatory and administrative barriers, these changes enhance user engagement, encouraging more active participation in the LFM.

The analysis conducted within the framework of the current EU energy regulations, along with the proposed recommendations, provides a roadmap for the widespread implementation of local flexibility markets in the examined countries. The findings highlight essential policy and regulatory adjustments that can facilitate consumer participation as an empowered stakeholder in the grid, ultimately supporting the achievement of the EU's 2030 and 2050 energy targets.

LFMs represent a fundamental tool in achieving Europe's decarbonisation and energy security goals. A standardized approach, robust regulatory oversight, effective business models, and consumer engagement are essential issues in unlocking the full potential of flexibility markets. By implementing the recommended measures and following the outlined roadmaps, the European Commission and national authorities can accelerate the integration of LFMs, paving the way for a smarter, more resilient, and consumer-centric energy system.

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